

**Inferring the 3D gravitational field of the Milky Way
with stellar streams**

Adrian Michael Price-Whelan

Submitted in partial fulfillment of the
requirements for the degree
of Doctor of Philosophy
in the Graduate School of Arts and Sciences

COLUMBIA UNIVERSITY

2016

© 2016

Adrian M. Price-Whelan

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

ABSTRACT

Inferring the 3D gravitational field of the Milky Way with stellar streams

Adrian M. Price-Whelan

We develop two new methods to measure the structure of matter around the Milky Way using stellar tidal streams from disrupting dwarf galaxies and globular clusters. The dark matter halo of the Milky Way is expected to be triaxial and filled with substructure, but measurements of the shape and profile of dark matter around the Galaxy are highly uncertain and often contradictory. We demonstrate that kinematic data from near-future surveys for stellar streams or shells produced by tidal disruption of stellar systems around the Milky Way will provide precise measures of the gravitational potential to test these predictions. We develop a probabilistic method for inferring the Galactic potential with tidal streams based on the idea that the stream stars were once close in phase space and test this method on synthetic datasets generated from N-body simulations of satellite disruption with observational uncertainties chosen to mimic current and near-future surveys of various stars. We find that with just four well-measured stream stars, we can infer properties of a triaxial potential with precisions of order 5–7 percent.

We then demonstrate that, if the Milky Way’s dark matter halo is triaxial and is not fully integrable (as is expected), an appreciable fraction of orbits will be chaotic. We examine the influence of chaos on the phase-space morphology of cold tidal streams and show that streams even in weakly chaotic regions look very different from those in regular regions.

We discuss the implications of this fact given that we see several long, thin streams in the Galactic halo; our results suggest that long, cold streams around our Galaxy must exist only on regular (or very nearly regular) orbits and potentially provide a map of the regular regions of the Milky Way potential. We then apply this understanding of stream formation along chaotic orbits to the interpretation of a newly-discovered, puzzling stellar stream near the Galactic bulge. We conclude that the morphology of this stream is consistent with forming along chaotic orbits due to the presence of the time-dependent Galactic bar.

These results are encouraging for the eventual goal of using flexible, time-dependent potential models combined with larger data sets to unravel the detailed shape of the dark matter distribution around the Milky Way.

Contents

List of Figures	v
List of Tables	xviii
Acknowledgements	xxi
1 Introduction	1
1.1 The Milky Way	3
1.1.1 Disk	4
1.1.2 Bulge & Bar	5
1.1.3 Halo	7
1.2 The Milky Way in the context of cosmology	9
1.3 Surveys of the Milky Way halo	12
1.3.1 Stellar tracers	12
1.3.2 Surveys past, present, and future	15
1.4 Outline of thesis	18
2 Spitzer, Gaia, and the Potential of the Milky Way	20
2.1 Introduction	20
2.2 Context and motivation	22

2.2.1	<i>Spitzer</i> and 2% distance errors to RR Lyrae in the halo	23
2.2.2	Gaia and the age of astrometry	23
2.2.3	The Sagittarius debris system	25
2.3	Description and test of our algorithm	26
2.3.1	The algorithm: Rewinder	29
2.3.2	Application to Simulated Data	30
2.4	Discussion, strengths, and limitations	32
2.5	Conclusions and motivation for future work	33
3	Inferring the gravitational potential of the Milky Way with a few precisely measured stars	35
3.1	Introduction	35
3.2	Simulations	41
3.3	Method (Rewinder)	44
3.3.1	Motivation: tidal debris	45
3.3.2	Probabilistic model	49
3.4	Experiments	53
3.4.1	Data with negligible uncertainties	54
3.4.2	Data with near-future uncertainties	55
3.4.3	Precise distance measurements with missing proper motions	57
3.5	Discussion	58
3.6	Conclusions	60
4	Chaotic dispersal of tidal debris	71
4.1	Introduction	71
4.2	Review of nonlinear dynamics	75

4.2.1	Orbits in integrable potentials	76
4.2.2	Orbits in near- and non-integrable potentials	79
4.2.3	The behavior of chaotic orbits in non-integrable potentials	81
4.2.4	Mixing of orbit ensembles	82
4.3	Numerical methods	83
4.3.1	Potential choice	83
4.3.2	Orbit integration	86
4.3.3	Lyapunov exponents	87
4.3.4	Frequency diffusion rate	87
4.4	Results	89
4.4.1	Part I: Lyapunov and frequency diffusion times	90
4.4.2	Part II: Ensemble properties and mixing	95
4.4.3	Part III: Short-time frequency evolution	104
4.5	Discussion: limitations and future work	106
4.5.1	The progenitor mass scale	106
4.5.2	Potential choice	110
4.5.3	Stream modeling	112
4.5.4	Ophiuchus stream	113
4.6	Summary and Conclusions	113
4.A	Lyapunov exponents	116
4.B	SuperFreq	119
5	Chaotic fanning of the Ophiuchus stream	122
5.1	Introduction	122
5.2	Methods	126
5.2.1	Potential models	126

5.2.2	Fitting orbits to the Ophiuchus stream	129
5.2.3	Generating mock streams	131
5.3	Results 1: Orbit fits and chaos	133
5.4	Results 2: Stream models for the Ophiuchus stream	135
5.5	Discussion	140
5.5.1	Future work: Modeling the Galactic bar	141
5.5.2	Future work: The orbits and survivability of inner Milky Way globular clusters	142
5.6	Conclusions	143
5.A	Transformation from Galactic to Ophiuchus stream coordinates	144
5.B	Fitting orbits to stellar streams	149
5.B.1	Likelihood	149
5.B.2	Priors	151
6	Conclusion	153
6.1	Summary of Results	153
6.2	Future Work	156
6.2.1	Rewinder	156
6.2.2	Chaotic stream dispersal as a potential constraint	156
	Bibliography	158

List of Figures

1.1	Estimates for the astrometric precision of the end-of-mission data release from the <i>Gaia</i> mission for individual stars of different types. <i>Left</i> : Fractional parallax or distance uncertainty for different stellar tracers as a function of distance. When the <i>Gaia</i> parallax uncertainty becomes larger than the distance uncertainty for an alternate distance measurement method, the minimum uncertainty is assumed. For example, for RR Lyrae (RRL) stars, distance measurements from the period-luminosity relation are $\approx 2\%$. For other stars, photometric distance uncertainties range from $\approx 8\text{--}50\%$. <i>Right</i> : Tangential velocity uncertainty using the fractional distance uncertainties in the left panel and the proper motion uncertainties from <i>Gaia</i> for a star with a tangential velocity $v_{\text{tan}} = 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$	16
-----	--	----

2.1	Expected <i>Gaia</i> distance and tangential velocity errors as a function of heliocentric distance for RR Lyrae stars. Errors are a function of color and magnitude of the source, and hence the metallicity: each line is computed by Monte Carlo sampling from the empirical metallicity distribution of the Galactic halo from Ivezić et al. (2008). Parallax distance errors from <i>Gaia</i> are larger than the line-of-sight size of both Sgr and Orphan (Orp), but photometric distance errors are comparable to the the Sgr scale (assuming 10% errors, dotted line). Bottom panel shows that the <i>Gaia</i> tangential velocity errors are smaller than the internal velocity dispersion of nearer regions of both Sgr and Orp.	24
2.2	Particle density (blue) of the first leading and trailing wraps from the final time-step of the Law & Majewski (2010) simulation of the Sgr stream. Point markers (black) show positions of a random sample of 100 stars drawn from this density distribution. The position of the Sun is shown with the solar symbol.	27
2.3	Phase space distance (D_{ps}) for 10 randomly selected stars integrated backwards in the correct potential (top) and a potential where q_z is 25% larger (bottom). The same 10 particles are used in both figures, so the initial conditions are identical. Horizontal (dashed) line shows $D_{\text{ps}} = 2$, for reference.	28
2.4	1D slices of the objective function (generalized variance) for each halo potential parameter. The parameter values are normalized by the true values show the effect of varying each parameter by $\pm 10\%$. The values of the objective function (vertical axis) are not interesting but note the minima around the truth (1.0).	31

2.5	Blue points show the “best-fit” parameters resulting from each resample of 100 stars from the Sgr stream particle density shown in Figure 2.2. Green (vertical and horizontal) lines show the true values of the parameters. Grey ellipses show one- and two-sigma margins, assuming the points are normally distributed.	32
3.1	Equipotential contours for the LM10 potential (Eq. 3.7) in Galactocentric, cartesian coordinates for various halo parameter choices. For all panels, $v_h = 121.858$ km/s, $r_h = 12$ kpc, and $q_2 = 1$. Left to right, each column represents a new choice of parameters. If not specified, other parameters are fixed to $q_1 = q_z = 1$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$ (far left panels). Panels on far right show the best-fit parameter values from LM10.	43
3.2	Particle positions (grey dots) in Galactocentric cartesian coordinates from the final time-step of four N -body simulations (Section 3.2) with the same progenitor orbit initial conditions over a range of progenitor masses (columns). Black crosses indicate eight particles chosen from each mass simulation and used in the experiments described in Section 3.4.	44
3.3	Orbits of 2000 randomly-drawn, disrupted particles projected into the instantaneous orbital plane coordinates (Eqs. 3.11-3.13), normalized by the tidal radius (Eq. 3.9), and only shown within half a satellite crossing time around $t = t_{ub}$ for each of the four progenitor masses. The orbits were integrated backwards from their present-day positions (final time step of the N -body simulations) as test particles without the potential of the progenitor. Horizontal black line shows $x_2 = 0$ (top panels) and $x_3 = 0$ (bottom panels), and the unit circle (black circle) illustrates the classical disruption radius in these coordinates.	47

3.4	Same as Figure 3.3 but for particle velocities normalized by the velocity scale (Eq. 3.10).	48
3.5	Positions of all 64 MCMC walkers (see Section 3.4) for each parameter at each step of the inference (black lines). The MCMC chains do not display any bulk movement or stray walkers, implying, by eye, that the chains have converged. We also compute the autocorrelation functions for each parameter and find that, for this experiment, the autocorrelation times are short (as shown on each panel in this figure). Projections of the binned samples (posterior densities) are shown in Figure 3.6.	56
3.6	Projections of the posterior probability distribution over the five potential parameters (q_1, q_z, ϕ, v_h, r_h) and Lagrange point offset (α) assuming negligible uncertainties on the observed phase-space coordinates of eight stars and the progenitor, visualized as two-dimensional histograms of MCMC samples. Solid contours (black lines) show approximately 1σ and 2σ levels of the distribution. Vertical and horizontal lines (blue) show the true, input values for the potential parameters used in the N -body simulations. For the potential parameters, the axis ranges are chosen to be the same for this and the potential posterior plots to follow.	64
3.7	Projections of the marginal posterior over the triaxial potential parameters for observed stars and progenitor with near-future uncertainties (Section 3.4.2). Axis ranges show the lower and upper bounds on the uniform priors over these parameters.	65
3.8	Projections of the marginal posterior over the progenitor parameters for observed stars and progenitor with near-future uncertainties (Section 3.4.2).	66

3.9	Projections of the marginal posterior over parameters for one of the stars for observed stars and progenitor with near-future uncertainties (Section 3.4.2).	67
3.10	Same as Figure 3.7 but for data with no proper motion measurements. . . .	68
3.11	Same as Figure 3.8 but for data with no proper motion measurements. . . .	69
3.12	Same as Figure 3.9 but for data with no proper motion measurements. . . .	70
4.1	An illustrative demonstration of the orbit structure for integrable (left), near-integrable (middle), and non-integrable (right) potentials in terms of the ratios of the fundamental frequencies. In an integrable potential, only resonant and non-resonant orbits exist, and all orbits are regular (resonances appear as lines in frequency-ratio-space). If the potential is perturbed mildly, resonance layers form around the resonances that host near-resonant orbits which behave like resonant orbits but have an additional frequency corresponding to libration about the resonance. Where resonances overlap or near separatrices, stochastic layers form and orbits will be chaotic. For more strongly perturbed potentials, many of the non-resonant orbits may become chaotic but resonance layers may grow and still remain regular.	78
4.2	Equipotential contours (left) and isodensity contours (right) for the triaxial NFW potential considered in this work. For the potential plot there are eight contour levels evenly spaced and linear in the value of the potential. For the density plot there are eight contour levels logarithmically spaced from $10^4 M_{\odot} \text{ kpc}^{-3}$ to $10^7 M_{\odot} \text{ kpc}^{-3}$	85

4.3 A grid of isoenergy orbits initialized on the xz plane. All distances are normalized by the potential scale radius. Each pixel in these panels represents a single orbit, and the shading of each pixel corresponds to the median pericentric distance (left) or median apocentric distance (right) computed over 64 orbital periods. The central black band in the left panel and white band in the right panel are tube orbits with apocenter-to-pericenter ratios close to one. The four arrows are explained in Section 4.4.2 and the caption of Figure 4.4. 91

4.4 The same grid of orbits as shown in Figure 4.3, but now each pixel is colored by the logarithm of the Lyapunov time (in units of orbital periods). Orbits are integrated for a total of 10000 orbital periods. Chaotic orbits with $t_\lambda/T \gtrsim 700$ appear regular because the integration time for each orbit is insufficient to resolve weak chaos. Four orbits are pointed out with arrows—from top to bottom, these are the strongly chaotic (D), near-resonant (A), weakly chaotic (C), and non-resonant (B) orbits of Table 4.2 (see Section 4.4.2). 92

4.5 The same grid of orbits as shown in Figure 4.3, but now each pixel is colored by the logarithm of the frequency diffusion time (again in units of orbital periods). The frequencies are computed in two consecutive windows, each of which has length equal to 40 orbital periods. The frequencies are measured precisely so that small changes in the frequencies can be detected over just ≈ 10 s of orbits. Four orbits are pointed out with arrows—from top to bottom, these are the strongly chaotic (D), near-resonant (A), weakly chaotic (C), and non-resonant (B) orbits of Table 4.2 (see Section 4.4.2). 94

4.6	Four representative orbits chosen from the orbit grid (e.g., Figure 4.3): a regular, near-resonant orbit (A), a regular, non-resonant orbit (B), a weakly chaotic orbit (C), and a more strongly chaotic orbit (D). All orbits are long-axis tubes with similar pericenters and apocenters. Orbits in this Figure were integrated for 1024 orbital periods and are shown in projection.	97
4.7	Final particle positions after integrating unbound, globular-cluster-sized ensembles of orbits generated around each of the three N -body orbits (Figure 4.8). The ensembles each contain 1024 particles and are initialized at pericenter. The particle positions qualitatively match the morphology of the ‘oldest’ debris from the corresponding N -body simulations (Figure 4.8). . .	98
4.8	We use the Self-Consistent Field (SCF) basis function expansion code (Hernquist & Ostriker 1992) to run N -body simulations of globular-cluster-mass progenitor systems on the three orbits of Figure 4.7. The progenitor in each simulation is initialized as a 10^4 particle Plummer sphere and the background triaxial NFW potential is turned on slowly over 250 Myr to reduce artificial gravitational shocking. We start the progenitor systems at apocenter and integrate for ≈ 64 orbital periods so that each simulation finishes again at subsequent apocenter. The mass of the progenitor is set to $10^4 M_{\odot}$, and the length-scale of the Plummer sphere is set to 5 pc to get ≈ 50 –75% mass loss over the integration time. Panels show particle positions from the final snapshots of the simulations—for visualization the positions have been rotated so that the angular momentum of the progenitor at the final snapshot are aligned with the z -axis. These simulations confirm that the test-particle orbit ensembles (Figure 4.7) do (qualitatively) capture the nature of the early-stripped tidal debris.	99

4.9 Evolution of the mean density (normalized by the initial density) of orbit ensembles around the four orbits (Figure 4.6) over 64 orbital periods. Overplotted are various power-laws that qualitatively show the decay of the mean density for the ensembles: the mean density of the near-resonant orbit (A) follows nearly t^{-2} ; the non-resonant orbit (B) is slowly transitioning from t^{-2} to t^{-3} ; the weakly chaotic orbit (C) initially follows t^{-2} but then exponential decay takes over; the strongly chaotic orbit (D) is roughly exponential with fairly erratic density evolution. 102

4.10 The same grid of orbits as shown in Figure 4.3, but now the greyscale intensity is set by the mean density of a of small ensembles of orbits after integration for 64 orbital periods. The orbit ensembles are generated around each parent orbit in the grid (Section 4.4.2) and the mean density is a kernel density estimation (KDE) with an adaptive Epanechnikov kernel. Given the extremely long chaotic timescales of the weakly chaotic orbits in the upper half of the grid, it is surprising that any of the high-order resonant structure is visible in this map. Four orbits are pointed out with arrows—from top to bottom, these are the strongly chaotic (D), near-resonant (A), weakly chaotic (C), and non-resonant (B) orbits of Table 4.2 (see Section 4.4.2). 103

4.11 Evolution of the fundamental frequencies computed over a total of 256 orbital periods for the four orbits, A, B, C, D. Plotted are the per cent deviations of the frequencies computed in window relative to the value in the initial window—that is, if j is the index of a given time window, $\delta\Omega_{1,j} = (\Omega_{1,j} - \Omega_{1,0})/\Omega_{1,0}$. The initial value is shown as a blue plus sign and the final value is shown as a red x. The frequencies are computed with a window width of ≈ 128 orbital periods, and the window is shifted by one orbital period between each computation (each grey point represents the fundamental frequencies computed in a single window). For the regular orbits (A,B), the fractional variation is around 10^{-6} and thus all points overlap on this scale. The weakly chaotic orbit (C) displays frequency variations comparable to the spread in frequencies in globular-cluster-like tidal debris. The frequency variations of the strongly chaotic orbit (D) have a larger characteristic spread. 107

4.12 Distributions of the fundamental frequencies for all orbits in 128-orbit ensembles generated around the four orbits, A, B, C, D. Plotted are the per cent deviations of the frequencies of each ensemble orbit relative to the frequencies of the parent orbit—that is, if i is the index of a given orbit and $i = 0$ is the parent orbit, $\delta\Omega_{1,i} = (\Omega_{1,i} - \Omega_{1,0})/\Omega_{1,0}$. All orbits are integrated for 128 orbital periods to compute the frequencies. The near-resonant ensemble frequency distribution (A) is nearly 1D, and thus the ensemble appears one-dimensional in configuration-space (Figure 4.7). The two largest eigenvalues of the non-resonant ensemble frequency distribution (B) are closer, and thus the ensemble spreads quicker, leading to a two-dimensional spread of debris in configuration-space. Around both the weakly chaotic orbit (C) and strongly chaotic orbit (D), chaotic diffusion increases the spread of the debris significantly, leading to faster 3D spreading in configuration-space. 108

4.13 Same as Figure 4.12 but after integrating the same orbits for another 128 orbital periods. The ensemble frequency distributions around the regular orbits (A,B) appear nearly identical, whereas both the weakly and strongly chaotic ensemble frequency distributions spread significantly. 109

4.B.1A reproduction of Figure 3.45 from (Binney & Tremaine 2008) as a validation of our frequency analysis code: Frequency ratios for 100000 isoenergy orbits integrated in a triaxial logarithmic potential. Linear features are resonances—stable resonances appear as dark lines, unstable resonances appear as linear gaps. 120

- 1 *Left column:* Circular velocity curves along the Sun-Galactic center line for a representative barred MW potential model (top left) and for the static MW potential model (bottom left). Solid black line shows total (sum of all components), lines below show a decomposition by potential components. Vertical grey bar shows approximate position of the Sun, horizontal grey bar shows roughly the range in measured circular velocity of the Sun. *Right column:* Contours of constant surface density for a barred MW potential (top right) and the static MW potential model (bottom right). Four contours are drawn per decade in surface density between 10^7 and $10^{12} \text{ M}_{\odot} \text{ kpc}^{-3}$. Note the perturbation from the bar potential within Galactocentric radius $r \lesssim 4 \text{ kpc}$. The Sun’s position is indicated by the ‘ \odot ’ symbol. 124
- 2 Results from fitting orbits to BHB stars associated with the Ophiuchus stream in the static and barred potential models. Data used for computing the likelihood are shown as black points with grey error bars. The four “fanned” BHB stars from S16 excluded from the likelihood computation are shown as grey squares. Error bars may sometimes be smaller than the point size. Lines (blue) show sections of orbits integrated forward and backwards from initial conditions drawn from the posterior samples generated by MCMC (See Section 5.B). Note that the four higher dispersion stars (the four stars with highest longitude) were not used when computing the likelihood and are only shown for completeness. Though these four stars are significant outliers relative to the extrapolated orbit, they are (1) at the correct distance and sky position relative to the stream and (2) have velocities $\approx 2.5\sigma$ discrepant with the halo velocity distribution in this region. 132

3	Projections of orbits integrated from the mean orbital parameters estimated from the orbit fitting posterior distributions in each potential model. Orbits are integrated for 6 Gyr and shown in Galactocentric, Cartesian coordinates. Even though the mean orbital parameters have nearly identical values (e.g., the initial conditions are nearly identical in heliocentric coordinates), the orbits in each potential model are different in appearance.	135
4	Histograms of estimated Lyapunov time, $t_\lambda = 1/\lambda_{\max}$, for posterior samples from the orbit fitting procedure (Section 5.B). More chaotic orbits, i.e. those with shorter Lyapunov times, typically occur in barred potentials with higher pattern speeds. There is little dependence on bar angle. All orbits in these barred potential models are strongly chaotic with $t_\lambda \ll t_{\text{Hubble}}$ and $t_\lambda \sim t_{\text{orbit}}$, where the typical orbital period for Ophiuchus stream stars is a few hundred Megayears.	136
5	Sky position, distance, and line-of-sight velocity in heliocentric, Galactic coordinates for star particles (contours or grey points) from the maximum-likelihood mock streams in each potential. Top panels show surface density of mock stream star particles in each potential. Contours are spaced logarithmically from 10^{-2} to 10 particles per sq. deg—that is, each color represents a factor of 10 difference in surface density. In the static potential (top left), the density remains high along the center of the stream, but for some of the barred potentials the density drops sharply because of chaotic stream-fanning. Vertical, dashed lines show the approximate extent of the densest part of the stream visible in main-sequence stars (the segment originally detected in Bernard et al. 2014).	145
6	Same as Figure 5 for the other five barred potentials.	146

- 7 Simulated maps of the 2D density of star particles from the maximum-likelihood mock streams in each potential with a noisy background of stars binned into 10' by 10' pixels. The background star density is assumed to be Poisson with $\lambda = 42$ (see Figure 3 in Bernard et al. 2014, where the typical background density is $\approx \frac{60}{(0.2 \text{ deg})^2}$). The mock stream particles are down-sampled so that the total number of particles in the region of sky that the stream is seen as an over-density matches the observed number of stars ($N \approx 500$ Bernard et al. 2014). Color-scale is stretched so that white to black is 2nd to 98th percentile. 147
- 8 Star particles (grey points) from mock streams generated on the mean orbits in each potential model shown in projections of Galatocentric, Cartesian coordinates. The position of the Sun is shown as the symbol at $(x, z) = (-8, 0)$ kpc. The volume of the sky position and distance plots of Figures 5–6 are shown transformed to these coordinates as the blue wedge near $(x, z) = (-2, 4)$ kpc. This demonstrates that the stream is nearly aligned our viewing angle. . . . 148

List of Tables

- 3.1 Parameter values used in the experiments of Section 3.4. \mathcal{N} is the normal (Gaussian) distribution, and \mathcal{U} the uniform distribution. There are 11 parameters for the Milky Way potential, but only the halo parameters are left free to vary; some parameters are fixed (denoted by “(fixed)”) at the true values used in the N -body simulations that generated the fake test data. The progenitor has nine parameters—the position, \mathbf{r}_p , and velocity, \mathbf{v}_p , vectors each contain three components—but only five are left free to vary. The sky coordinates (e.g., Galactic l , b) are assumed to be known with negligible uncertainty. Each star has eight associated parameters, five of which are allowed to vary. Sky coordinates are fixed, along with the tail assignment (whether the star belongs to the leading or trailing tail). For inference with eight stars, there are $4 + 5 + 8 \times 4 = 41$ free parameters. 63
- 4.1 Summary of parameters for the triaxial NFW potential (Equation 4.8) used in this work. Triaxiality is introduced in the density (rather than the potential) to ensure that the density is physical at all radii. Velocity scale, scale radius, and axis ratios are chosen to match the median halo parameters for a $M_{\text{vir}} \approx 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ halo from (Jing & Suto 2002). The triaxiality parameter, $T_{abc} = \frac{a^2 - b^2}{a^2 - c^2}$, is also given. 86

4.2	Orbital initial conditions from the xz grid for orbits with a range of chaotic timescales—A is a regular, near-resonant orbit, B a regular, non-resonant orbit, C a weakly chaotic orbit, and D a strongly chaotic orbit. Positions (x, y, z) are given in units of scale radii, r_s , and velocities (v_x, v_y, v_z) in units of scale velocity, v_c . Chaotic timescales are expressed (t_λ, t_Ω) in number of orbital periods. Recall that the frequency diffusion time, t_Ω , is the time over which we expect order-unity changes in the fundamental frequencies, hence why the timescales appear quite long.	100
5.1	The disk potential scale lengths (a, b) were adopted following (Bovy 2015) to match the exponential scale length of the disk (Bovy & Rix 2013) and local dark-matter density (e.g., Bovy & Tremaine 2012). The halo mass scale is set by specifying the circular velocity at the scale radius, v_c , and the scale velocity in Equation 5.1 is given by $v_h^2 = v_c^2 / (\ln 2 - 1/2)$. The bar mass is taken from recent 3D density modeling of red clump stars in the Galactic bulge (Portail et al. 2015b). The other bar parameters are listed in Table 5.2 next to the corresponding model name.	129
5.2	Present-day bar angle (α) and pattern speed (Ω_p) for the nine parameter pairs considered in this work. These values span the range of recent measurements from a variety of techniques (Dwek et al. 1995; Wang et al. 2012, 2013; Wegg & Gerhard 2013).	130
5.3	Same as Table 5.1, except: the disk mass is increased to account for removing the bar component, a spheroidal bulge component is added.	131

5.4 Estimated mean and standard deviation of samples from the marginal posterior distributions over each parameter in our orbit fit model (the posterior distributions are very close to Gaussian). For the barred potentials, all mean values are the same because the time-dependence of the bar doesn't impact the orbit fit over the short length of the stream. We have made samples from the full posterior distribution available with this *Chapter* and provide code to transform to and from stream coordinates (see <http://adrian.pw/ophiuchus> for more information). 137

(This page left intentionally blank.)

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I am privileged to have had Kathryn Johnston as my advisor and mentor for the last four years. I am so grateful to have had an advisor who supports me both in my work and in life. Her intuition and ease at coming up with creative new ideas is easily matched by her supportive, patient, and light-hearted nature. Kathryn constantly (and accidentally) reminds me why I love doing science and has been a huge influence on my growth as a scientist. I can't imagine a better mentor—thanks for putting up with me!

Thanks to David Hogg for getting me interested in astronomy. I've always loved science and have been fascinated by astronomy, but I didn't think I wanted to be or could be a scientist. I started as an undergraduate in technical theater at the Tisch School for the Arts at NYU. After one semester I knew that I wanted to switch majors, but it wasn't until I took Physics 1 (taught by Hogg) that I knew I wanted to do *whatever that guy did*. Over the last ten years, he has been an invaluable mentor, good influence, bad influence, and friend.

New York can be caustic, but I am lucky to have had friends, advocates, and peers who have helped me tremendously throughout my life in the city. From the scientific world, thank you Kelle Cruz, Dan D'Orazio, and Josh Peek for being there. In the other world, huge thanks to Jared Hiller for putting up with me in our (but really his) musical ventures. Thanks to my band, *Operator Music Band*, for getting me out of the office and letting me play music (Jared Hiller, Dara Hirsch, Jon Young, and Landen Griffith). Thanks Adam, Peter, and Sean for being there no matter what. Thanks also to the Ding Dong Lounge (RIP) for the late nights and grime.

I've received advice and guidance from so many people throughout graduate school. Thanks especially to (then) graduate students Jeff Andrews, Ana Bonaca, Steph Douglas, Dan Foreman-Mackey, David Hendel, Cameron Hummels, Duane Lee, Munier Salem, Jonathan Sick, but also to all of the Columbia graduate students that I've been privileged to know,

chat with, play pool with, and learn from. To officemates Lauren Corlies and Sarah Pearson. To postdocs Andy Casey, Andreas Küpper, Chervin Laporte, Dustin Lang, Melissa Ness, Robyn Sanderson, Branimir Sesar, Allyson Sheffield, Nick Stone, Erik Tollerud, Matt Turk, Lucianne Walkowicz. Thanks to faculty Marcel Agüeros, Arlin Crotts, Julianne Dalcanton, Marla Geha, Jacqueline van Gorkom, Zoltan Haiman, Jules Halpen, Jerry Ostriker, and David Schiminovich for ideas, discussion, debates, and support, some of which have happened primarily through *Twitter*.

Special thanks to Hans-Walter Rix for supporting me in Germany each summer and for welcoming me to his house and garden.

Huge thanks to Summer Ash for her friendship and for organizing outreach events at Columbia. Herding cats is *hard!*

Thanks to everyone in the Astropy community for letting me share in something that has made me a better programmer and person. Especially Tom Robitaille, Perry Greenfield, and Erik Tollerud (who gets a second thank you!). Thanks also to the .astronomy community for the enthusiasm, crazy ideas, and fantastic conferences. Especially Alyssa Goodman, Chris Lintott, and Rob Simpson.

I'm quite certain I would not have made it this far without the support and assistance of Millie and Ayoune, the astronomy department staff. Thanks so much for all of the help! Thanks also to the staff at MDM observatory, especially Eric Galayda.

As an undergraduate, I had the pleasure of working with and learning from Michael Blanton, Demitri Muna, and Ben Weaver.

I am fortunate to have lived so close to my family for so many years who have always been there for love, support, and encouragement. Thanks to my parents, Audrey and Michael, who taught me to wonder. Thanks to my grandmother Pat and my sister Alexa and her amazing family, Lars and Seren, for the laughs, advice, and help on so many occasions. Also

for letting me use her car!

Finally, thanks to Lauren for the love, adventures, patience, and for keeping me balanced over the last two and a half years. I can't imagine trying to do this without the love we have for each other.

2016, New York, NY

Chapter 1

Introduction

There is a theory which states that if ever anyone discovers exactly what the Universe is for and why it is here, it will instantly disappear and be replaced by something even more bizarre and inexplicable. There is another theory which states that this has already happened.

– Douglas Adams

To many, the Milky Way represents the faint, fuzzy band of light that arcs across a dark, moonless sky.¹ Long suspected to be a collection of unresolved stars (as early as the 1200s), Galileo Galilei confirmed this idea using the first astronomical telescopes in the 1600s. By 1755, Immanuel Kant speculated that the Milky Way may appear thin across the sky because we are viewing a large disk of stars from within, like a scaled-up version of the solar system with many more bodies (stars). Between then and the early 1900s, hundreds of “spiral nebulae” were discovered that were initially believed to be either star-forming regions within the Milky Way or external “island universes.” It took Edwin Hubble’s distance measurements to the nearby galaxies M31 and M33—enabled by the concerted efforts of

¹But not visible in New York City, where the majority of the research presented in this *Thesis* was conducted.

many astronomers—to clearly place them outside of the Milky Way and thus place our own Galaxy in the context of a universe of other galaxies.

Since the mid-1900s, through decades of research studying the structure of stars and gas at ever-increasing distances, we now know a great deal more about the Milky Way. Its scales are vast: the Galaxy hosts at least 100 billion stars over a distance of about 3 billion billion kilometers and took about 13 billion years to form to present day. But even more surprising than what we have observed is what we haven't: from the motion of gas in the outer Galaxy, the velocities of stars in external galaxies, and the gravitational lensing of distant galaxies, we now know that—by mass—the dominant substance in the universe is unseen, *dark matter*.

Constraints on cosmological parameters from many independent sources—e.g., the cosmic microwave background (Planck Collaboration et al. 2015), Type Ia supernova distances (Riess et al. 1998; Perlmutter et al. 1999), and baryon acoustic oscillations (Eisenstein et al. 2005)—have found that the energy density of the universe is dominated by dark energy ($\approx 73\%$) and dark matter ($\approx 23\%$). Ordinary baryonic matter constitutes a meager 4% of this energy density and at present is the only observable tracer of the vastly more numerous dark matter (though the search for the dark matter particle is underway; Xenon100 Collaboration et al. 2012; Akerib et al. 2012). Dark matter dominates the mass of galaxies on large scales and choreographs their interactions. Therefore, the basis for expanding our understanding of the universe will come through characterization and detection of dark matter. The goal of the work presented in this *Thesis* is to develop methods to further our understanding of the global gravitational potential of the Milky Way in order to connect the Galaxy to cosmological predictions and— for the first time—precisely measure the structure of dark matter around a galaxy.

In what follows, Galactocentric quantities are generally shown with no subscript, e.g., spherical radius r , cylindrical radius R . Heliocentric quantities use the solar symbol, \odot , in

subscript—e.g., radial distance from the sun r_{\odot} . Capital, italicized galaxy components such as *Disk*, *Bulge*, and *Halo* refer to components of the Milky Way, whereas in lower-case these words refer to the components in general.

1.1 The Milky Way

In its global properties, the Milky Way is a fairly typical disk galaxy. It is, however, the one galaxy for which it is presently possible to measure detailed chemical abundances and 3D positions and velocities for large samples of individual stars: (see Section 1.3 for an overview of surveys that are measuring or will measure these chemo-dynamical quantities for stars in the Galaxy). This is of great interest to modeling the formation and evolution of the Galaxy: while a given star is born with a unique, frozen-in chemical “tag” apparent in its surface chemical abundances, the kinematics of the star will evolve from its birth location (in phase-space) due to dynamical processes such as radial migration, mixing, and heating. By comparing the observed spatial structure, kinematics, and chemical abundance patterns of stars in the Galaxy with hydrodynamical simulations, it is hoped that these stellar parameters will provide strong constraints on galaxy formation mechanisms. The Milky Way plays a key role in this goal: unlike other galaxies where it is only possible to measure integrated properties, it is possible to directly measure the distribution function of the Milky Way.

Though many fundamental aspects of the formation of the Galaxy are still not understood², recent advancements have led to great strides in understanding for all of the major components of the Galaxy: the *Disk*, *Bulge*, and *Halo*. These components are briefly reviewed below.

²For example, were disk stars with large velocity dispersion born in that state or were their orbits heated?

1.1.1 Disk

The most massive baryonic component of the Milky Way is its disk. The mass in the *Disk* ($M_d \approx 5 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$; McMillan 2011) is dominated by stars which have an approximately exponential density profile in both the radial and vertical directions (with scale lengths of ≈ 2 – 3 kpc and ≈ 250 – 800 pc, respectively, from thin to thick disk; Ojha 2001; Jurić et al. 2008; McMillan 2011; Bovy et al. 2012b). There is an appreciable amount of gas, the majority of which is present in a clumpy disk of neutral Hydrogen, HI ($M_{\text{HI}} \approx 8 \times 10^9 M_\odot$; Kalberla & Kerp 2009) with a larger radial scale length (≈ 3 – 4 kpc) and radially increasing scale height (≈ 100 pc at $R = 8$ kpc to ≈ 1 kpc at $R = 25$ kpc; Wouterloot et al. 1990; Merrifield 1992). Outside of $R \gtrsim 12.5$ kpc the gas disk is warped up to ≈ 5 kpc away from the stellar midplane (Henderson et al. 1982; Kalberla et al. 2007) and possibly indicates a dynamical reaction to some external perturbation (e.g., Bekki 2012).

Within $R \approx 12$ kpc, the HI and younger, more metal-rich stars orbit the Galaxy on approximately circular orbits with stellar circular velocities $v_c \approx 220$ km s $^{-1}$, velocity dispersions $\sigma_v \approx 25$ km s $^{-1} \ll v_c$, and relatively small vertical excursions.³ Older and more metal-poor stars tend to have larger velocity dispersions and larger scale-heights. These sub-components of the *Disk* are commonly referred to as the “thin” and “thick” *Disks*, respectively (Gilmore & Reid 1983), though more recent work has instead argued that the disk is more naturally decomposed into *mono-abundance populations* that form a continuum of spatially super-imposed populations from younger, alpha-poor, and vertically compact to older, alpha-enhanced, and vertically extended (see, e.g., Figure 12 and Section 6 in Rix & Bovy 2013; Bovy et al. 2012a). Classically, the thin *Disk* was believed to truncate around

³Stars in the thin disk have typical azimuthal orbital periods of $T_\phi \approx 200$ – 300 Myr. A typical star of the sun’s age, ≈ 5 Gyr, has only completed ≈ 20 orbits around the Galaxy, in stark contrast with the billions of orbits the Earth has completed around the Sun.

$R \approx 15$ kpc (e.g., Robin et al. 1992), but recent studies of the outer disk suggest that the *Disk* may extend farther and oscillate above and below the projected midplane measured in the inner Galaxy (Xu et al. 2015; Price-Whelan et al. 2015). There could therefore be a significant number of *Disk* stars at $15 \text{ kpc} \lesssim R \lesssim 40 \text{ kpc}$ with heights $|z| \gtrsim 1 \text{ kpc}$, but it is unclear how this population would connect to the midplane of the disk. In comparison, gas associated with the HI disk has been estimated to be as large as $R \approx 60$ kpc (Kalberla & Dedes 2008).

In the opposite direction—towards the inner Galaxy—dust extinction severely hampers studies of the Galaxy. Only the brightest and reddest stars observable in the infrared can pierce through the thick veils of interstellar dust associated with the gas in the thin *Disk*. For this reason, while there is evidence for the existence of non-axisymmetric disk features along particular sight lines in both gas and stars (e.g., Levine et al. 2006; Reid et al. 2014), there is, e.g., still no consensus on even the number of spiral arms in the *Disk* let alone a global picture of their structure. Young stars in the thin disk within $R \lesssim 2$ kpc are almost entirely extinguished; fortunately, the *Bulge* contains a significant number of old, metal-rich giant stars that have recently enabled precise reconstructions of the stellar density and kinematics of bulge stars from $0 \text{ kpc} \lesssim R \lesssim 2 \text{ kpc}$.

1.1.2 Bulge & Bar

The Milky Way *Bulge* is characterized by its predominantly old, metal-rich stellar population ($t_{\text{age}} \gtrsim 10$ Gyr, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \gtrsim -1$; Zoccali et al. 2003), its smaller physical size ($R \lesssim 1\text{--}2$ kpc; Binney et al. 1997), and its large velocity dispersions relative to the *Disk* ($\sigma_v \sim 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; Ness et al. 2013b). There has long been evidence from, e.g., its boxy shape and from anomalous neutral gas motions near the Galactic center that the *Bulge* is a “pseudobulge” rather than a spherical “classical” bulge, and that there is likely a barred structure in the

central Galaxy (Blitz & Spergel 1991; Binney et al. 1991; Weiland et al. 1994; Binney et al. 1997).

Recent work has developed a convincing and complete picture of the barred *Bulge*. What is typically attributed to the cylindrically-rotating, boxy *Bulge* ($R \lesssim 2$ kpc) is likely the inner component of a much longer bar that could extend up to 5 kpc from the Galactic center (Wegg & Gerhard 2013; Wegg et al. 2015). The extension of the boxy *Bulge* into the disk is referred to as the “long bar” and is thinner in both vertical height and along the line of sight. Young, thin disk stars do extend farther inwards and appear to form a thin, barred disk parallel to but vertically compact relative to the boxy bulge (Dékány et al. 2015). The inner bar component is triaxial with exponential scale lengths $(h_x, h_y, h_z) = (0.70, 0.44, 0.18)$ kpc, whereas the long bar component extends out to $R \approx 5$ kpc and is much flatter with scale lengths $(h_x, h_y, h_z) \approx (3.0, 0.7, 0.1)$ kpc (Wegg et al. 2015).

The total mass in the *Bulge* is measured to be $M_b \approx 1.5\text{--}3 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$ from both stellar population modeling (Dwek et al. 1995; Valenti et al. 2016) and dynamical mass measurements (Zhao et al. 1995; Portail et al. 2015b); the long bar contains $\approx 10\%$ of this mass (Wegg et al. 2015). These models are consistent with the existence of an additional classical (spherical) component that could account for up to $\lesssim 25\%$ of the bulge mass. Though observational constraints on a classical bulge component are difficult because of dust extinction, there is some indication of more a spherical stellar distribution that is chemically distinct from the barred population (Ness et al. 2013a,b).

The mass of the barred *Bulge* is fairly well constrained, but its kinematic properties are not well known. Bars are generally assumed to rotate like solid bodies⁴ and can therefore be characterized by their pattern speed, Ω_b . For the *Bulge*, an additional kinematic quantity is the present-day angle of the bar relative to the sun-Galactic center axis, ϕ_b . Many different

⁴Otherwise they would not be so numerous and prominent in disk galaxies.

methods have been applied to inferring the pattern speed and bar angle and have generally found that $25 < \Omega_b < 60 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$ and $20^\circ < \phi_b < 30^\circ$ (but individual measurements are generally inconsistent in that they are separated by values much larger than their estimated uncertainties; Dwek et al. 1995; Stanek et al. 1997; Debattista et al. 2002; Shen et al. 2010; Wegg & Gerhard 2013; Cao et al. 2013; Wegg et al. 2015; Portail et al. 2015b).

1.1.3 Halo

The *Halo* here refers to anything not kinematically associated with the *Disk* or *Bulge* that is still gravitationally bound to the Milky Way. This includes the gaseous *Halo*, the stellar *Halo*, and the dark matter *Halo*. The stellar *Halo* is the only of these three sub-components that is directly observable: the presence of the dark matter *Halo* that dominates the total mass of the Galaxy on large scales is inferred indirectly (e.g., van der Marel et al. 2012), and the gaseous halo is low-density and has thus far been studied using absorption line features in background sources (Miller & Bregman 2013). The gaseous *Halo*—though important for mediating inflows and outflows of gas to and from the *Disk*—is likely unimportant for the orbits of halo stars and will be largely ignored in this *Thesis*.

The stellar *Halo* contains a tiny fraction of the baryons in the Galaxy ($\approx 1\%$; Bell et al. 2008) but is of great importance for studying the global structure of the Milky Way and its history. First, the stellar populations in the halo provide key insights about the early history of the Galaxy and led to the realization that a significant portion of the stellar *Halo* was formed *hierarchically* from the disruption and subsequent mixing of dwarf galaxies (e.g., Searle & Zinn 1978; Bullock & Johnston 2005; Bell et al. 2008). Second, *Halo* stars orbit the Galaxy where dark matter dominates the mass profile and can therefore be used to measure the properties of the dark matter *Halo*. In the *Disk*, it is difficult to measure the global dark matter density distribution because it is degenerate with, e.g., the scale length and mass of

the baryonic components (Dehnen & Binney 1998; Sofue et al. 2009). In the halo, the number of stellar tracers is smaller and they therefore contribute little to the gravitational potential. Third, the dynamical times in the *Halo* are long ($\approx 0.5\text{--}1$ Gyr or longer) and significant kinematic substructure has not had enough time to phase-mix away (Helmi & White 1999). In fact, a significant fraction ($\approx 40\text{--}50\%$; Bell et al. 2008) of the stellar halo is likely associated with substructure in the form of tidal streams and shells formed from disrupted or disrupting dwarf galaxies and, to a lesser extent, globular clusters (e.g., Newberg et al. 2002; Majewski et al. 2003; Belokurov et al. 2006). As will be discussed in Chapters 2–3, tidal debris features are extremely powerful for dynamical modeling because they are kinematically cold.

The stellar *Halo* is generally split into the inner and outer *Halo* based on the steepening of the spherically- or axisymmetrically-averaged density profile observed in many different tracer populations (e.g., RR Lyrae stars, red giant branch stars, blue horizontal branch stars). The *Halo* density profile appears to follow a double power-law ($n(r) \propto r^{-\alpha}$) where the inner halo slope $\alpha_{\text{in}} \approx 2\text{--}3$ and the outer halo slope $\alpha_{\text{out}} \approx 4\text{--}6$ with a break radius of $r_{\text{break}} \approx 20\text{--}30$ kpc (Watkins et al. 2009; Sesar et al. 2010; Deason et al. 2011; Sesar et al. 2011, 2013a). The kinematics of these populations have been used to measure the velocity dispersion profile of the stellar *Halo* and have found an analogous break: the radial velocity dispersion appears to decline steeply from $\sigma_r \approx 150 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at $r \approx 10$ kpc to $\sigma_r \approx 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at $r \approx 20$ kpc, after which the decline slows until it reaches $\sigma_r \approx 50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at $r \approx 100$ kpc (Battaglia et al. 2005; Xue et al. 2008; Brown et al. 2010; Deason et al. 2012c, 2013). Together, the density and velocity dispersion profiles of the stellar *Halo* have been used to constrain the shape and mass of the dark matter halo, finding that the virial mass of the Milky Way is $M_{\text{vir}} \approx 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ and the inner halo is flattened with a flattening parameter $q \approx 0.6\text{--}0.7$ (Sesar et al. 2011; Deason et al. 2011; Sesar et al. 2013a; Xue et al. 2015).

Many of the dynamical measurements that use stellar *Halo* stars as tracers fundamentally

assume that the observed sample of stars are drawn from a random or at least well-mixed distribution function (e.g., Battaglia et al. 2005; Kafle et al. 2012, 2014). However, the phase-space distribution of the stellar *Halo* is intricate and clumpy: the breaks and abrupt changes in moments of the stellar *Halo* distribution function may result from the presence of a few dominant, unmixed merger remnants such as the Sagittarius stream (which contains almost as much stellar mass as the rest of the stellar *Halo* combined; Niederste-Ostholt et al. 2010). The existence of substructure has been shown to bias mass inferences made with random-tracer methods by up to 20% (certain orbits will be represented more than others as opposed to being random; Yenko et al. 2006).⁵

A complimentary approach to measuring the dark matter distribution is to instead take advantage of the non-random nature of the Galaxy’s stellar distribution and utilize the knowledge that stars in tidal debris structures were once all part of the same object. Such approaches can require orders of magnitude fewer tracers than a randomly sampled population to achieve comparable accuracy. In Chapters 2–3, we develop and introduce a new method for using stellar tidal streams to infer the underlying mass distribution that properly handles uncertainties or missing data in the kinematics of the individual stream stars.

1.2 The Milky Way in the context of cosmology

Though the composition of dark matter (DM) is still unknown, the large-scale properties of the universe are precisely characterized by the Λ Cold Dark Matter (Λ CDM) cosmological model: fluctuations in the cosmic microwave background and the clustering of galaxies across hundreds of megaparsecs are fit to extreme precision with Λ CDM (Planck Collaboration et al. 2015; Sánchez et al. 2012). On smaller scales, simulations of galaxy formation have

⁵This bias is likely smaller than the systematic uncertainties in the velocity and mass profile measurements, but these uncertainties are typically not included in constraints made by such methods.

not converged on a set of concrete predictions, however a number of consistencies do appear across a range of DM models and even with inclusion of baryonic physics: DM halos (1) have spherically-averaged density profiles that seem to follow a universal profile across a large dynamic range in mass, (2) are permeated with substructure on many scales, (3) are triaxial in shape, and (4) have shapes and orientations that vary with radius (Dubinski & Carlberg 1991; Navarro et al. 1996; Jing & Suto 2002; Kuhlen et al. 2007; Vera-Ciro et al. 2011).

Within this paradigm, the Milky Way has grown to its present-day size and shape through a combination of steady accretion of gas and dark matter from the cosmic web and, to a lesser extent, through the accretion and merging of ≈ 100 –1000 small galaxies that have fed gas and stars to the *Disk* and *Halo*. Evidence of the former is difficult to measure directly, but gas flows into high-redshift galaxies are starting to be detected (Martin et al. 2015). There is, however, clear evidence of the latter: to date, ≈ 45 satellite galaxies have been discovered around the Milky Way with a large range in masses, Galactocentric distances, and at different stages of merging with the Galaxy (Belokurov et al. 2007b; Bechtol et al. 2015).

The largest mass satellites are the pair of massive dwarf galaxies visible to the naked eye from the southern hemisphere: the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds (LMC/SMC). The LMC–SMC system has already deposited nearly $2 \times 10^8 M_\odot$ of gas into the *Halo* (Putman et al. 2003), removed through a combination of ram-pressure and tidal stripping (Salem et al. 2015). The system appears to be on its first infall to the Milky Way (Besla et al. 2010) so stars from this system have not been significantly stripped, but after several more orbits around the Galaxy the stellar *Halo* will be completely dominated by the $M_{\text{LMC+SMC}} \approx 4\text{--}8 \times 10^9 M_\odot$ (Jones et al. 1994) of stars from this system.⁶

⁶Compare this mass to the stellar mass in the halo today, $M_{h:s} \approx 5 \times 10^8 M_\odot$ (Section 1.1.3).

In contrast to the LMC and SMC, most Milky Way satellite galaxies are dwarf spheroidal or elliptical galaxies that have metal-poor stellar populations. It has been argued that a significant fraction show evidence of tidal distortion or extra-tidal stars (e.g., Belokurov et al. 2007b; Coleman et al. 2007) and are thus in the early stages of tidal destruction. Other satellites like the Sagittarius dwarf spheroidal galaxy are already long into the process of merging as evidenced by its large stellar stream.

In addition to the satellite galaxies, there are a handful of massive tidal debris structures with no known progenitor systems: to highlight a few,⁷ the Hercules-Aquila stellar cloud (Belokurov et al. 2007c), the Orphan stream (Grillmair 2006), and the Virgo over-density (Jurić et al. 2008).⁸ Finding and modeling streams and substructure is important because they constrain the dark matter distribution, but also because many of these features were once satellite galaxies: to measure the accretion history and satellite population around the Milky Way, we will need to account for those that have already been destroyed (e.g., Johnston et al. 2008). Luckily, these structures are long-lived because of the long dynamical times of the halo (e.g., the Sagittarius stream will take 10s of Gigayears to fully mix into a smooth *Halo* component). A naive comparison to cosmological simulations suggest that— even after correcting for observational biases—this number is an order of magnitude lower than the expected number of subhalos around Milky Way-mass galaxies in dark-matter-only simulations. Higher resolution simulations that include baryonic physics appear to shrink this expected number to within a factor of a few of the observed number (e.g., Zolotov et al. 2012; Brooks et al. 2013; Sawala et al. 2016), however, it is not known whether this tension has been fully resolved.

Along with the satellite galaxies and their remnants, the Milky Way hosts ≈ 160 glob-

⁷For a complete overview of all known tidal streams and stellar clouds, see Tables 1–2 in Grillmair & Carlin (2016).

⁸Though its close association with the *Disk* may suggest that it is instead *Disk* material perturbed away from the midplane rather than material from a destroyed satellite.

ular clusters with masses between $\approx 10^4\text{--}10^6 M_\odot$ (Harris 2010), many of which also display evidence for short tidal tails (Grillmair et al. 1995; Leon et al. 2000). Tidal streams from globular clusters are dynamically much colder than those from dwarf galaxies. These systems have typical internal velocity dispersions around $\lesssim 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; globular cluster streams tend to remain thin and dense, which makes them visually apparent in filtered number-count maps of stars (Grillmair 2008). ≈ 10 thin streams have been discovered that have no known progenitor clusters by visually inspecting maps of data from large photometric surveys like the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) or Pan-STARRS (e.g., Grillmair & Dionatos 2006; Bonaca et al. 2012; Bernard et al. 2014).

1.3 Surveys of the Milky Way halo

The sun’s position in the Galaxy provides us with a three-dimensional view of the *Halo*. Soon it will be possible to measure full-space kinematics and detailed chemical abundances for large samples of stars in the *Halo*, thanks to the ongoing *Gaia* mission and future spectroscopic surveys. It is critical to develop and test modeling methods to fully leverage the information content in this data to understand the Milky Way and its place in the broader story of galaxy formation.

1.3.1 Stellar tracers

Ongoing and future surveys will measure kinematics for millions of stars associated with kinematic substructure in the *Halo*. Certain types of stars are better kinematic tracers because of their brightness and dependence on stellar population. In order to understand the information in these surveys, it is important to first understand the tracers. The stellar tracers described below are used because it is possible to select them using photometric

colors or variability, measure their distances, and consequently use them as indicators of the underlying stellar populations (e.g., Bell et al. 2010; Price-Whelan et al. 2015).

Main-sequence turnoff (MSTO) stars are the most numerous tracers that are useful for dynamical studies of the halo because they are found in all stellar populations. These stars form a horizontal feature in a Hertzsprung-Russell diagram where stars evolve off the main sequence before ascending the giant branch; these stars typically have F spectral types and absolute V -band magnitudes around $M_V \approx 4$. For a given age and metallicity, the turnoff point therefore has a well-defined location in color-magnitude space and can be used to measure distances to stars. From studies of globular cluster color-magnitude diagrams, MSTO stars from a single stellar population have a scatter in magnitude of around $\sigma_{\text{mag,MSTO}} \approx 0.9$ (Bell et al. 2008, 2010). This sets the lower-limit on the uncertainty in absolute distances that can be derived from MSTO photometry $\sigma_d/d \gtrsim 50\%$. From isochrone fitting of many MSTO stars in a single structure, the mean distance modulus (DM) can usually be measured with uncertainties $\sigma_{\text{DM,MSTO}} \approx 0.2$, corresponding to $\approx 10\%$ distance uncertainties for populations at the same distance. MSTO stars have been used to study large-scale structure in the *Halo* (e.g., Newberg et al. 2002) but because of their large distance errors they can't be used to resolve small-scale features. The *Gaia* mission will measure parallaxes better than 50% and 10% out to ≈ 5 kpc and ≈ 2 kpc, respectively.

Horizontal branch (HB) stars are considerably less numerous than MSTO stars; a typical metal-poor globular cluster will contain a few to a few tens of HB stars but will contain thousands of MSTO stars. However, because of their luminosity ($M_V \approx 0.5$) and significantly smaller distance uncertainties, these are extremely powerful kinematic tracers.

Blue horizontal branch (BHB) stars are post-main-sequence stars that have evolved off of the red giant branch (RGB) and onto the HB, which has a small scatter in absolute magnitudes for a wide range of initial stellar masses and metallicities ($\sigma_{\text{mag,BHB}} \approx 0.15$). BHB

stars typically have low metallicities $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \lesssim -1$, but the details of stellar evolution that lead to the formation of HB stars is still not well understood (Percival & Salaris 2011). These stars are very useful for studying the *Halo* because they are intrinsically bright and good distance indicators ($\sigma_d/d \approx 10\%$; see, e.g., Xue et al. 2008; Deason et al. 2011); outside of ≈ 4 kpc, *Gaia* parallaxes uncertainties will be worse than photometric distance measurements for BHB stars.

RR Lyrae (RRL) stars are also HB stars but lie in the region where the HB crosses the instability strip and are therefore pulsating variable stars. RRL star periods range from around $T \approx 0.2\text{--}0.8$ days and are easily identifiable from the distinct shapes of their optical light curves (e.g., Sesar et al. 2010). The mean metallicity of RRL stars is slightly higher than for BHB stars but have $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \lesssim -1$ (more metal-rich stars at this luminosity do not fall in the instability strip). RRL stars also follow a period-luminosity relation (tightest in the mid-infrared; Madore & Freedman 2012) that enables extremely precise distance measurements to individual stars ($\approx 1\text{--}2\%$; Klein & Bloom 2014). In existing surveys, these stars are seen out to ≈ 120 kpc (Sesar et al. 2010) and have been used extensively to map the structure of the *Halo* (e.g., Sesar et al. 2013a).

Red clump (RC) stars form the metal-rich end of the HB and lie near the giant branch because these stars lose less of their envelopes before the core begins helium burning. The intrinsic scatter in RC star distances is comparable to that of BHB stars so that distance measurements to individual stars have uncertainties $\sigma_d/d \approx 10\%$ (e.g., Bovy et al. 2014).

Red giant (RG) stars are present in old stellar populations and can be seen to extreme distances because of their large luminosities ($M_V \approx 1$ to -3). Lower-metallicity giants will fall in the K spectral type (K giants) and high-metallicity giants will fall in the M spectral type (M giants). The Milky Way halo is dominated by K giants because the mean metallicity is so low, but there are still an appreciable number of M giants (many of which

are associated with the Sagittarius debris system). The most luminous M giant stars are currently detected as far as ≈ 300 kpc into the *Halo*, enabling searches for distant Milky Way satellites and debris structures (Bochanski et al. 2014). K giants have been used to study the density profile of the inner $r \lesssim 80$ kpc of the *Halo* (Xue et al. 2015), but discrimination between dwarf stars and giant stars at these spectral types is often difficult and can lead to significant contamination.

1.3.2 Surveys past, present, and future

Large-area, precise photometric surveys like the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS; York et al. 2000), Two Micron All Sky Survey (2MASS; Skrutskie et al. 2006), and Dark Energy Survey (DES; Flaugher et al. 2012) have revolutionized our view of the *Halo*. These surveys have enabled the discovery and characterization of nearly all known dwarf satellites of the Milky Way and the majority of the known tidal debris structures in the *Halo*. The vast majority of these structures have been discovered as over-densities in configuration-space alone (e.g., in distance and sky position). This is largely because the number of *Halo* stars with radial velocity measurements is a factor of ≈ 1000 smaller than the number of photometrically identified stars, and the number with proper motion measurements is even smaller. When tangential velocity measurements from the *Hipparcos* mission (Perryman et al. 1997)—which measured proper motions and parallaxes to $\approx 10^5$ stars in the solar neighborhood—were supplemented with radial velocities from the Geneva-Copenhagen survey (Nordström et al. 2004), a significant amount of velocity substructure was uncovered even in this small volume (e.g., Bovy et al. 2009; Minchev et al. 2010).

The *Gaia* mission will provide this kind of revelation for the Milky Way *Halo*. *Gaia* is currently measuring parallaxes, proper motions, and radial velocities for $\approx 10^8$ stars in the Milky Way. The end-of-mission data release from *Gaia* (expected in 2022) will provide astro-

Figure 1.1: Estimates for the astrometric precision of the end-of-mission data release from the *Gaia* mission for individual stars of different types. *Left*: Fractional parallax or distance uncertainty for different stellar tracers as a function of distance. When the *Gaia* parallax uncertainty becomes larger than the distance uncertainty for an alternate distance measurement method, the minimum uncertainty is assumed. For example, for RR Lyrae (RRL) stars, distance measurements from the period-luminosity relation are $\approx 2\%$. For other stars, photometric distance uncertainties range from $\approx 8\text{--}50\%$. *Right*: Tangential velocity uncertainty using the fractional distance uncertainties in the left panel and the proper motion uncertainties from *Gaia* for a star with a tangential velocity $v_{\text{tan}} = 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.

metric measurements for $\approx 10^9$ stars. At distances $\gtrsim 10$ kpc in the *Halo*, the radial velocity and parallax uncertainties will be large for all stellar types, but the proper motion uncertainties will still be useful. Figure 1.1 shows a summary of the expected distance and tangential velocity uncertainties for each of the stellar tracers reviewed in the previous section. Of particular note are the RR Lyrae stars, which will have precise distance measurements and tangential velocity uncertainties $\lesssim 10 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ out to 25 kpc.

Another highly anticipated survey for Milky Way *Halo* science is the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST; LSST Science Collaboration et al. 2009). The telescope design and large mirror of the LSST will enable deep imaging over a huge field of view (magnitude

limits of ≈ 24.5 for single-epoch images, ≈ 27.5 for coadded images after 10 years). The LSST will image most of the visible sky in five filters every few nights, which will allow identification of faint time-variable stars like RR Lyrae stars at extreme distances (out to $\approx 2\text{--}3$ times the virial radius of the Milky Way). At the faint end, the LSST will supercede the *Gaia* astrometry and provide proper motions better than $\lesssim 1 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$ for stars with r -band magnitudes $20 \lesssim r \lesssim 24$. The survey will begin science operations in 2022 with the first data release expected about a year later.

Much of the *Halo* will be mapped in sky position, distance, and proper motion by the combination of *Gaia* and LSST; the last kinematic quantities needed are radial velocities. Unlike multi-object spectroscopy—needed to obtain large samples of radial velocities—imaging surveys do not scale in complexity with the number of sources. Robotic fiber-positioner spectrographs (Saunders et al. 2012) have and will make it possible to simultaneously observe 1000s of stars, but are expensive to maintain and don’t scale much above this number. Combined with the longer exposure times needed to obtain high signal-to-noise spectra, obtaining spectroscopy for a volume of stars comparable to the astrometric sources in *Gaia* will be an enormous technological challenge. However, it will be necessary in order to fully map out the chemical-abundance structure of and measure radial velocities for these sources. Many ongoing efforts (e.g., Steinmetz et al. 2006; Lee et al. 2008; Majewski et al. 2015; De Silva et al. 2015) have obtained spectra of varied resolution for ≈ 1 million stars around the Galaxy. The future Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI; Levi et al. 2013) will take spectra of an additional $\approx 10^7$ stars, but this is still orders of magnitude below the number needed to have complete 6D phase-space coverage for the entire Milky Way halo. Other proposed surveys such as WEAVE (Dalton et al. 2012), the Subaru prime-focus spectrograph (PFS; Sugai et al. 2015), and 4MOST (de Jong et al. 2012) would greatly aid in this effort but are currently being planned.

1.4 Outline of thesis

To take advantage of the enormous volume of imminent and near-future data for substructure in the Milky Way *Halo*, this *Thesis* develops two new, complimentary approaches (Chapters 2–3 and Chapters 4–5) for studying the structure of matter around the Milky Way using stellar streams.

Chapter 2 introduces a new method—**Rewinder**—for measuring parameters of a gravitational potential by integrating orbits of the progenitor of a stellar stream and its stars backwards in time. This leverages the precise tangential velocity measurements expected for RR Lyrae stars from the *Gaia* survey combined with accurate distances measured using the mid-infrared period-luminosity relation of RR Lyrae stars. The method is tested with synthetic observations of 100 stars from the end point of a simulation of satellite destruction and is shown to recover the shape, orientation, and mass scale of the input, true potential. This chapter has been published as (Price-Whelan & Johnston 2013).

In Chapter 3, the concepts developed in Chapter 2 are used to develop a likelihood function for the stellar streams so that the method can be used for statistical inference. With this critical update, **Rewinder** can properly account for finite observational uncertainties and missing data dimensions. **Rewinder** is tested on synthetic datasets generated from N -body simulations of satellite disruption in a static, multi-component Milky Way model with observational uncertainties chosen to mimic current and near-future surveys of various stars. With just a few stream stars and knowledge of the progenitor system kinematics, **Rewinder** can infer properties of a complex input potential with precisions of just a few percent. This chapter has been published as (Price-Whelan et al. 2014).

Chapter 4 examines the influence of chaos on the phase-space morphology of cold tidal streams and suggests a promising new direction for the use of tidal streams to constrain the

distribution of dark matter around our Galaxy. We show that streams even in weakly chaotic regions look very different from those in regular regions and that streams can be sensitive to chaos on a much shorter time-scale than predicted from the Lyapunov or frequency-diffusion times. We describe how the enhanced diffusion of the stream stars can be understood by looking at the variance in orbital frequencies of orbit ensembles centered around the parent (progenitor) orbit. This chapter has been published as (Price-Whelan et al. 2016).

In Chapter 5, we study a particular stellar stream—the Ophiuchus stream—that is plausibly showing signs of chaotic “stream-fanning” due to its proximity to the Galactic bar. We explore this hypothesis with models of stream formation along orbits consistent with the streams’ properties in a Milky Way potential model that includes a rotating bar, and find that in all choices for the rotation parameters of the bar, orbits fit to the stream are strongly chaotic. We show that these strongly chaotic orbits lead to simulated streams with properties that qualitatively match the observed properties of the stream. We discuss how the existence of or lack of “stream-fans” around the Ophiuchus stream would provide interesting constraints on the properties of the Milky Way bar and would help distinguish between formation scenarios for the stream.

Finally, in Chapter 6 we summarize our key results and describe several possible directions for future work.

Chapter 2

Spitzer, Gaia, and the Potential of the Milky Way

2.1 Introduction

The existence of vast halos of unseen *dark* matter surrounding each galaxy has long been proposed to explain the surprisingly large motions of the *baryonic* matter that we can see (e.g., Rubin & Ford 1970). Dark-matter-only simulations of structure formation lead us to expect that these dark matter halos should have density distributions that are described by a universal radial profile (Navarro et al. 1996) with a variety of triaxial shapes (Jing & Suto 2002). The inclusion of baryons in the simulations tends to soften the triaxiality of the dark matter in the inner regions of the halo (e.g., as the disk forms, Bailin et al. 2005) and can alter the radial profile through a combination of adiabatic contraction and energetic feedback (e.g., Pontzen & Governato 2012). Hence, measurements of the shape, orientation,

This section contains text from an article published in The Astrophysical Journal Letters, Volume 778, Issue 1, article id. L12, 6 pp. (2013). Portions of this paper’s introduction now appear in the introduction to this dissertation.

radial profile, and extent of dark matter halos provides information about the formation of these vast structures, as well as the messy baryonic processes that continue to shape them.

The Milky Way is the best candidate for such a detailed study of a dark matter halo since we can resolve large samples of stellar tracers. Thousands of blue horizontal branch stars selected from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) have been used to probe the Milky Way mass out to tens of kpc (SDSS, see Deason et al. 2012a; Kafle et al. 2012), and estimates with combined tracers extend to 150 kpc (Deason et al. 2012c).

This approach assumes that the tracers represent a random sampling of phase-mixed orbits drawn from a smooth distribution function, however large area surveys have revealed the existence of large-scale spatial inhomogeneities in the form of giant stellar streams (Newberg et al. 2002; Majewski et al. 2003; Belokurov et al. 2006), demonstrating that a significant fraction of the stellar halo is neither randomly sampled nor is fully phase-mixed.

Approaches that instead exploit the coherence of dynamical structures require many fewer tracers to reach similar accuracy compared to inferences made using and assuming a random population. One method is to simply fit orbits to observations of streams (e.g., Koposov et al. 2010). However, the assumption that debris traces a single orbit is actually incorrect (see Johnston 1998; Helmi & White 1999) and changes in orbital properties along debris streams can lead to systematic biases in measurements of the Galactic potential (Eyre & Binney 2009; Varghese et al. 2011). Sanders & Binney (2013a) recently demonstrated that this bias is equally problematic for the very thinnest, coldest streams, whose observed properties may be indistinguishable from those of the parent orbit (e.g. such as the globular cluster, GD1 — see Koposov et al. 2010), as for the much more extended and hotter streams (e.g. such as debris from the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy — see Majewski et al. 2003) where offsets from a single orbit are clearly apparent.

One way to address these biases is to run self-consistent N-body simulations of satellite

destruction in a variety of potentials with the aim of simultaneously constraining both the properties of the satellite and the Milky Way. Many studies of the Sagittarius debris system (hereafter Sgr) have adopted this approach, with the most recent work attempting to place constraints on the triaxiality and orientation of the dark matter halo (Law & Majewski 2010).

The promise of near-future data sets including full phase-space information has also inspired other approaches. Binney (2008) and Peñarrubia et al. (2012) demonstrate that the distribution of energy and entropy in debris, respectively, will be minimized only for a correct assumption of the form of the Galactic potential. Sanders & Binney (2013b) examine the distribution of debris in action-angle co-ordinates and show that stars stripped from the same disrupted object must lie along a single line in angle-frequency space, providing a constraint that can be used as a potential measure.

In this *Chapter* we re-examine and update a complimentary approach that uses tidal debris as a potential measure (originally proposed by Johnston et al. 1999b) in the context of current and near-future observational capabilities, and apply it to a simulation of the Sagittarius debris system (hereafter Sgr). In Section 2.2 we outline the observational prospects and Sgr properties that motivated this re-examination. In Section 2.3 we present the updated potential measure and test it with synthetic observations of simulated Sgr debris. In Section 2.4 we highlight the advantages and shortcomings of this method. We conclude in Section 2.5.

2.2 Context and motivation

The method presented in Section 2.3 takes advantage of three distinct developments: (i) the demonstration of a technique for deriving distances to individual RR Lyrae stars with 2%

accuracies (Section 2.2.1); (ii) the prospect of proper motion measurements of the same stars with $\sim 10 \mu\text{as}/\text{yr}$ precision (Section 2.2.2); and (iii) the tracing of debris associated with Sgr around the entire Galaxy (Section 2.2.3)

2.2.1 *Spitzer* and 2% distance errors to RR Lyrae in the halo

There is a long tradition for using RR Lyrae stars in the Galaxy to study structure (e.g., Shapley 1918), substructure (e.g., Sesar et al. 2010), and distances to satellite galaxies (e.g., Clementini et al. 2003). However, studies of RR Lyrae at optical wavelengths are limited by both metallicity effects on the intrinsic brightness of these stars and variable extinction along the line of sight. Moreover, systematic differences between instruments make it difficult to tie observations across the sky to a common scale.

At longer wavelengths, RR Lyrae promise tighter constraints on distances. Madore & Freedman (2012) have recently shown, using five stars with trigonometric parallaxes measured by Hubble (Benedict et al. 2011), that the dispersion in the mid-IR Period-Luminosity (PL) relation (first mapped by Longmore et al. 1986) at wavelengths measurable by NASA's *Spitzer* mission is ~ 0.03 mag. This implies that it is possible to use *Spitzer* to determine distances that are good to 2% for individual RR Lyrae stars out to ~ 60 kpc (*Spitzer*'s limit for detecting and measuring RR Lyrae). For comparison, distance measurements of Blue Horizontal Branch stars typically achieve ~ 10 -15% uncertainties (if appropriate color measurements are available, e.g., Deason et al. 2012c).

2.2.2 *Gaia* and the age of astrometry

The *Gaia* satellite (Perryman et al. 2001) is an astrometric mission which aims to measure the positions of billions of stars with 10-100 μas accuracies. Combined with expected proper motion accuracies, this will enable full six-dimensional phase-space maps of the Galaxy with

Figure 2.1: Expected *Gaia* distance and tangential velocity errors as a function of heliocentric distance for RR Lyrae stars. Errors are a function of color and magnitude of the source, and hence the metallicity: each line is computed by Monte Carlo sampling from the empirical metallicity distribution of the Galactic halo from Ivezić et al. (2008). Parallax distance errors from *Gaia* are larger than the line-of-sight size of both Sgr and Orphan (Orp), but photometric distance errors are comparable to the the Sgr scale (assuming 10% errors, dotted line). Bottom panel shows that the *Gaia* tangential velocity errors are smaller than the internal velocity dispersion of nearer regions of both Sgr and Orp.

<10% distance errors for heliocentric distances of up to ~ 6 kpc for RR Lyrae stars.

Figure 2.1 shows the *Gaia* end-of-mission distance and tangential velocity error estimates for RR Lyrae. Within 2 kpc, *Gaia* will measure distances to these stars with better than 2% accuracy — RR Lyrae in this volume can be used to test and calibrate the *Spitzer* PL relation described above. Beyond the 2 kpc threshold, the mid-IR PL relation for RR Lyrae will provide better distance measurements.

The combination of *Spitzer* and *Gaia* data will extend the “horizon” of where precise, six-dimensional phase-space maps of the Galaxy are possible from <10 kpc to 60 kpc. This enormous increase in volume will greatly refine data on debris systems in the halo.

2.2.3 The Sagittarius debris system

Sgr was discovered serendipitously during a radial velocity survey of the Galactic bulge (Ibata et al. 1994). Signatures of extensive stellar streams associated with Sgr have since been mapped across the sky in carbon stars (Totten & Irwin 1998), M giants selected from 2MASS (Majewski et al. 2003), main sequence turnoff stars from SDSS (Belokurov et al. 2006), and RR Lyrae in the Catalina Sky Survey (Drake et al. 2013).

Sgr stream data has inspired a rich set of models (e.g., Johnston et al. 1999a; Fellhauer et al. 2006). Most recently, Law & Majewski (2010, hereafter LM10) combined all the (then) current data on the Sgr debris to constrain both a model of its evolution and the potential in which it orbits. (Note that new observational work by Belokurov et al. (2013) suggest that the trailing tail of Sgr debris does not match the LM10 model.) Figure 2.2 shows particle positions from the final time-step of the LM10 N-body simulation of dwarf satellite disruption along the expected Sgr orbit in the best-fitting Milky Way halo model. The simulation was

run in a three-component potential, with a triaxial, logarithmic halo model of the form

$$\Phi_{halo} = v_{halo}^2 \ln(C_1 x^2 + C_2 y^2 + C_3 xy + (z/q_z)^2 + R_c^2) \quad (2.1)$$

where C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 are combinations of the x and y axis ratios (q_1 , q_2) and orientation of the halo with respect to the baryonic disk (ϕ):

$$C_1 = \frac{\cos^2 \phi}{q_1^2} + \frac{\sin^2 \phi}{q_2^2} \quad (2.2)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{\sin^2 \phi}{q_1^2} + \frac{\cos^2 \phi}{q_2^2} \quad (2.3)$$

$$C_3 = 2 \sin \phi \cos \phi (q_1^{-2} - q_2^{-2}). \quad (2.4)$$

A comparison of simulations and data enabled LM10 to make an assessment of the three-dimensional mass distribution of the Milky Way’s dark matter halo through constraints on the potential parameters v_{halo} , q_1 , q_z , and ϕ . Combined *Spitzer* and *Gaia* measurements of distances and proper motions of RR Lyrae in the Sgr debris will open up new avenues for potential constraints. Figure 2.1 shows that a 2% distance error is smaller than the distance range in the stream (top panel). Similarly, *Gaia* proper motion error estimates correspond to tangential velocity errors less than the velocity dispersion for much of the stream (bottom panel). The next section outlines a new method to take advantage of this information.

2.3 Description and test of our algorithm

With access to 6D information for stars in a tidal stream, each star becomes a powerful potential measure by exploiting the fact that the stars must have come from the same progenitor: if the orbits of the stars and progenitor are integrated *backwards* in a potential

Figure 2.2: Particle density (blue) of the first leading and trailing wraps from the final time-step of the Law & Majewski (2010) simulation of the Sgr stream. Point markers (black) show positions of a random sample of 100 stars drawn from this density distribution. The position of the Sun is shown with the solar symbol.

that accurately models the Milky Way, the stars should recombine with the progenitor (imagine watching satellite destruction in “rewind”). If the potential is incorrect, the orbits of the stars will diverge from that of the progenitor and thus will not be recaptured by the satellite system (Figure 2.3).

This approach was originally proposed by Johnston et al. (1999b) and was tested on the proposed characteristics of the Space Interferometry Mission (Unwin et al. 2008). Below we present an updated version of the algorithm: the promise of 2% distances to RR Lyrae stars (see Section 2.2.1) enables a direct measurement (rather than approximate estimate, as previously assumed) of the position of a star within its debris structure. The test statistic

that quantifies how well stars recombine with the satellite has also been rigorously redefined.

Figure 2.3: Phase space distance (D_{ps}) for 10 randomly selected stars integrated backwards in the correct potential (top) and a potential where q_z is 25% larger (bottom). The same 10 particles are used in both figures, so the initial conditions are identical. Horizontal (dashed) line shows $D_{ps} = 2$, for reference.

2.3.1 The algorithm: Rewinder

Quantifying this method requires a sample of stars with known full space kinematics $(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{v}_i)|_{t=0}$ (e.g., measurements of all position and velocity components for these stars *today* at $t = 0$), the orbital parameters for the progenitor system $(\mathbf{x}_p, \mathbf{v}_p)|_{t=0}$, and a functional form for the potential, $\Phi(\boldsymbol{\theta})$. For a given set of potential parameters, $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, the orbits of the stars and progenitor are integrated backwards for several Gigayears. At each timestep t_j , for each particle i , a set of normalized, relative phase-space coordinates are computed

$$\mathbf{q}_i = \frac{\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_p}{R_{\text{tide}}} \quad , \quad \mathbf{p}_i = \frac{\mathbf{v}_i - \mathbf{v}_p}{v_{\text{esc}}} \quad (2.5)$$

where $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v})_i$ and $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v})_p$ are the phase-space coordinates for the particles and progenitor, respectively. These definitions require an estimate of the mass of the satellite, m_{sat} , which, combined with the orbital radius of the satellite, R , and the computed enclosed mass of the potential within R , M_{enc} , sets the instantaneous tidal radius and escape velocity,

$$R_{\text{tide}} = R \left(\frac{m_{\text{sat}}}{3M_{\text{enc}}} \right)^{1/3} \quad , \quad v_{\text{esc}} = \sqrt{\frac{2Gm_{\text{sat}}}{R_{\text{tide}}}}. \quad (2.6)$$

These quantities are computed at each time step to take the time dependence into account, neglecting mass-loss from the satellite. Qualitatively, when the distance in this normalized six-dimensional space, $D_{\text{ps},i} = \sqrt{|\mathbf{q}_i|^2 + |\mathbf{p}_i|^2} \lesssim 2$, the star is likely recaptured by the satellite (in the absence of errors, we find that $\sim 90\%$ of the initially bound particles come within this limit when integrating all orbits backwards). Johnston et al. (1999b) imposed a similar condition as a hard boundary and maximized the number of recaptured particles in a given backwards-integration. What follows is a description of an updated procedure with a statistically-motivated choice for an objective function.

For each star, i , the phase-space distance, D_{ps} , is computed at each timestep t_j , and the vector with the minimum phase-space distance is stored

$$t_i^* = \operatorname{argmin}_t D_{\text{ps},i} \quad (2.7)$$

$$\mathbf{A}_i = (\mathbf{q}_i(t_i^*), \mathbf{p}_i(t_i^*)). \quad (2.8)$$

Thus, the matrix \mathbf{A}_{ik} contains these minimum phase-space distance vectors for each star, where $k \in [1, 6]$. Intuitively, the variance of the distribution of minimum phase-space vectors will be larger for orbits integrated in an incorrect potential relative to the distribution computed from the ‘true’ orbital history of the stars: in an incorrect potential, the orbits of the stars relative to the orbit of the progenitor spread out in phase space. Thus, the *generalized variance* of the distribution — computed for a given set of potential parameters, $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ — is a natural choice for the scalar objective function, $f(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, used in constraining the potential of the Milky Way

$$\Sigma_n = \operatorname{Cov}(\mathbf{A}_{ik}) \quad (2.9)$$

$$f(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \ln \det \Sigma_n. \quad (2.10)$$

2.3.2 Application to Simulated Data

The LM10 simulation data (see Section 2.2.3) is a perfect test-bed for evaluating the effectiveness of this method. We start by extracting both particle data and the satellite orbital parameters from the present-day snapshot of the simulation data. We then “observe” a sample of 100 stars from the first leading and trailing wraps of the stream. The radial velocity and distance errors are drawn from Gaussians ($\varepsilon_{\text{RV}} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 0, \sigma = 10 \text{ km/s})$) and

www.astro.virginia.edu/~srm4n/Sgr/data.html

Figure 2.4: 1D slices of the objective function (generalized variance) for each halo potential parameter. The parameter values are normalized by the true values show the effect of varying each parameter by $\pm 10\%$. The values of the objective function (vertical axis) are not interesting but note the minima around the truth (1.0).

$\varepsilon_D \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.02 \times D)$) and the proper motion errors are computed from the expected *Gaia* error curve.

The generalized variance defines a convex function over which we optimize four of the six logarithmic potential parameters: v_{circ} , ϕ , q_1 , and q_z (q_2 and R_c are degenerate with combinations of the other parameters). Figure 2.4 shows one-dimensional slices of the objective function produced by varying each of the potential parameters by $\pm 10\%$ around the true values and holding all others fixed.

In anticipation of extending the above method to include a true likelihood function, we use a parallelized Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm (Foreman-Mackey et al. 2013) to sample from our objective function. We use the median value of the converged sample

http://www.rssd.esa.int/index.php?page=Science_Performance&project=GAIA

Though MCMC is typically not an efficient optimization tool, in this case objective function is both

Figure 2.5: Blue points show the “best-fit” parameters resulting from each resample of 100 stars from the Sgr stream particle density shown in Figure 2.2. Green (vertical and horizontal) lines show the true values of the parameters. Grey ellipses show one- and two-sigma margins, assuming the points are normally distributed.

distribution as a point estimate for the potential parameters. To assess the uncertainty in the derived halo parameters, we sample 100 stars 100 times and estimate the potential parameters with each resampling. Figure 2.5 shows the recovered parameters for each sample and demonstrates the power of this method: a moderately sized sample of RR Lyrae alone places strong constraints on the shape and mass of the Galaxy’s dark matter halo. From the covariance matrix derived from the distribution of points in Figure 2.5, we find the mean recovered parameters and one-sigma deviations to be $q_1 = 1.36 \pm 0.02$, $q_z = 1.36 \pm 0.03$, $\phi = 96.0 \pm 1.5$ degrees, and $v_{\text{halo}} = 123.2 \pm 1.6$ km/s.

2.4 Discussion, strengths, and limitations

The strengths of this method stem from its simplicity: it requires only a rough estimate of the satellite mass m_{sat} combined with backwards integration of orbits. **Rewinder** does not

noisy and expensive to compute. The stochasticity and easy parallelization of the algorithm outperforms other optimizers on this problem.

assume that stream stars follow a single orbit and instead *relies* on the fact that each star is on a different orbit. There are also no assumptions made about of the internal distribution of satellite stars. Thus, *Rewinder* is applicable to any debris that is known to come from a single object and not restricted to the coldest tidal streams. In principle, it could also be applied to the vast stellar debris *clouds* that have been discovered (e.g., the Triangulum-Andromeda and Hercules-Aquila clouds; Rocha-Pinto et al. 2004; Belokurov et al. 2006), or even stars that have only associations in orbital properties and do not form a coherent spatial structure (e.g., Helmi & White 1999). The method trivially extends to combining constraints from multiple debris systems at once by simply integrating all debris from several satellites simultaneously, with D_{ps} defined appropriately for each star.

It is also important to characterize the the limitations of this method. Firstly, the measurement errors for RR Lyraes associated with the very coldest streams (e.g., the globular clusters Pal5 and GD1; Odenkirchen et al. 2002; Koposov et al. 2010) will likely be too large to resolve the minute differences in orbital properties between the debris and satellite. Second, the present prescription neglects orbital evolution (e.g., dynamical friction) and scattering of stream stars due to the potential of the satellite. Preliminary simulations (to be fully explored in forthcoming work) suggest that these two points can be neglected for satellite masses between $\sim 10^7$ and $\sim 10^9 M_{\odot}$. Lastly, the current version of the algorithm relies on knowledge of the current position and velocity of the parent satellite, which may not be available (e.g., the Orphan Stream; Belokurov et al. 2007a).

2.5 Conclusions and motivation for future work

This *Chapter* presents an algorithm for measuring the Galactic potential that anticipates combined data from the *Spitzer* and *Gaia* satellite missions which promise precise, full phase-

space measurements of RR Lyrae stars in the halo of our Galaxy. When applied to a sample of 100 stars (with realistic observational errors) drawn from the Law & Majewski (2010) N-body simulation of the destruction of the Sgr dwarf satellite, *Rewinder* recovers the depth, shape, and orientation of the dark matter potential to within a few percent.

While the tests presented in this *Chapter* are very simple, the accuracy of potential recovery promised by such a small sample of stars provides strong motivation for further theoretical work to: 1) develop a robust generative model that utilizes the concepts demonstrated by *Rewinder*; 2) investigate the power of using multiple debris structures; and 3) examine how *Rewinder* might work with less accurate measurements or missing dimensions.

Our results also motivate an observational campaign with *Spitzer* to survey RR Lyrae stars in debris structures around the Milky Way to get precise distances to combine with near-future *Gaia* velocity data. If just 100 stars in a single stellar stream allow us to study the depth, shape, and orientation of the Milky Way potential, larger samples in multiple structures (e.g., the Orphan Stream; Sesar et al. 2013b) offer the prospect of assessing these quantities as a function of Galactocentric radius. Tracing the mass in a dark matter halo with this level of detail is impossible for any other galaxy in the Universe.

Acknowledgments

We thank Barry Madore for providing the inspiration for this work. Thanks to David Hogg for statistical advice. Thanks also to Steve Majewski, David Law, and David Nidever. We also thank the anonymous referee for useful suggestions.

APW is supported by a National Science Foundation Graduate Research Fellowship under Grant No. 11-44155. This work was supported in part by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. PHYS-1066293 and the hospitality of the Aspen Center for Physics.

Chapter 3

Inferring the gravitational potential of the Milky Way with a few precisely measured stars

3.1 Introduction

Dark-matter-only simulations produce strongly triaxial halos (Jing & Suto 2002) with significant density fluctuations and substructure with a mass spectrum that follows a power law (Zemp et al. 2009). Inclusion of baryons tends to soften the triaxiality and smooth out graininess in the inner galaxy through a combination of dissipative infall (Dubinski 1994) or cooling (Bryan et al. 2013). These processes combined with the gravitational influence of a disk can act to make the inner halo more oblate or spherical, however they do not seem to erase the clumpy, triaxial nature of the outer halo (e.g., Pontzen & Governato 2012; Zhu

This section contains text from an article published in *The Astrophysical Journal*, Volume 794, Issue 1, article id. 4, 15 pp. (2014). Portions of this paper's introduction now appear in the introduction to this dissertation.

et al. 2015). This should lead to radially-dependent axis ratios, orientation, and smoothness, and predicts that the true mass distributions around galaxies like the Milky Way are complex and—given the long dynamical times in the halo—unrelaxed. None of these predictions have been conclusively tested.

The bulk of the baryonic matter in galaxies spans roughly 5–10% of the spatial extent of the host dark matter halo. Hence, the brightest and most easily observable components of a galaxy are sensitive to the inner portion of the host halos mass distribution. For example, the rotation curves of disk galaxies trace the inner mass with exquisite sensitivity since matter in disks can be assumed to move on nearly circular orbits. Measurements of the dark matter distribution at large radii is complicated by the low density of visible tracers, observational difficulties of measuring kinematics of stars at large distances, and unknown orbits. Around external galaxies, the extended mass distribution has been studied using a variety of approaches (see Courteau et al. 2013, for a complete and detailed review). For example, the kinematics of tracer populations such as globular clusters or planetary nebulae can be used to derive mass estimates under the assumptions that these satellite systems are on random orbits and are well-mixed in orbital phase (early investigations include Méndez et al. 2001; Côté et al. 2003). Simple, parameterized fits to both the mass and orbit distribution have been simultaneously constrained using such data (e.g. Napolitano et al. 2011; Deason et al. 2012b). Alternatively, the statistical properties of gravitationally lensed background sources around a galaxy can be used to constrain the *projected* shape, orientation, and radial profile of mass (see, for example, the Lens Structure and Dynamics Survey described in Koopmans & Treu 2002). Of course, lensing reconstructions can only be performed for galaxies which closely intersect our line of sight to background sources, but the advent of large photometric catalogues has allowed automatic searches for such chance alignments and significant increases in the number of objects studied in this way (e.g. the Sloan Lens ACS

Survey, see Bolton et al. 2006).

Within the Milky Way our unique vantage point allows us a three-dimensional view of stars within our own dark matter halo. Our proximity allows us to use individual stars as kinematic tracers and hence build much larger samples that probe deeper into the halo than the globular cluster and planetary nebula studies of external galaxies. For example, Deason et al. (2012a) used halo BHB stars selected from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS; York et al. 2000) as a random tracer population to measure the mass and slope of a power-law fit to the potential. Such studies assume that the tracer orbits are randomly sampled from a smooth distribution function and are fully phase mixed. However, large photometric surveys such as the SDSS and 2MASS (Skrutskie et al. 2006) have discovered copious amounts of substructure—in streams and kinematic associations of stars—in the Milky Way halo (e.g., Belokurov et al. 2006; Rocha-Pinto et al. 2004), thus demonstrating that the stellar distribution is neither on random orbits nor fully phase-mixed. Substructure in the form of stellar streams and clouds is known to bias mass and velocity inferences from random tracer methods by several tens of percent (Yencho et al. 2006).

Another approach to using halo stars as potential measures is to exploit the non-random nature of halo. Tidal streams are dynamically cold systems—debris typically have small distributions of energy and angular momentum—and thus require orders of magnitude fewer tracers than a random sample to get constraints of comparable accuracy. For example, in the simplest case we might assume that debris stars are actually still on the same orbit as their progenitor system (a *wrong* assumption, see below). This information about the orbits combined with measurements of the full-space velocities \mathbf{v} at different points \mathbf{x} in the structure (e.g., along a stream) would give us a direct measure of differences in a potential, Φ .

Law & Majewski (2010, LM10) used N -body simulations of the disruption of the Sgr

dwarf galaxy to simultaneously fit a model to the available data on the debris stars and a triaxial, analytic Milky Way potential. By varying parameters of the Milky Way potential, they found “best-fit” parameters by comparing the properties of observed Sgr stars to their simulated debris. The computational costs of running N -body simulations limited their search to a grid of potential parameters and forced the authors to fix many other parameters (e.g., properties of the disk and bulge). Nevertheless, they were able to constrain the 3D shape that their assumed potential model must take in order to best represent the Milky Way out to ~ 70 kpc and found that the best-fitting halo has a nearly oblate (only mildly triaxial) shape flattened in a direction close to the Sun-Galactic center line. Though an unlikely orientation for the halo—Debattista et al. (2013) find that the disk of the Milky Way would not remain stable in such a configuration—LM10 showed that the data is at a state where such inference is possible.

The computational costs associated with N -body simulations has motivated the development of many methods that approximately model tidal streams. The simplest alternative is to fit a single orbit to observed debris (e.g., Koposov et al. 2010; Deg & Widrow 2013). Though this is known to be incorrect and leads to biases in inferred properties of the underlying potential (e.g., Eyre & Binney 2011; Lux et al. 2013; Sanders & Binney 2013a), Deg & Widrow (2014) and Lux et al. (2013) have used orbit fitting to demonstrate the power of combining multiple streams in dynamical inference. To account for the offset between the orbit of the progenitor and the orbits of the debris stars, methods have been proposed that add some dispersion or offset around a single orbit either in phase space (e.g., Eyre & Binney 2009; Varghese et al. 2011; Küpper et al. 2012) or action-angle coordinates (Eyre & Binney 2011; Sanders & Binney 2013b; Bovy 2014; Sanders 2014). Other statistical methods have been proposed (Johnston et al. 1999b; Peñarrubia et al. 2012; Sanderson et al. 2014) that may prove powerful when applied to, for example, data from the *Gaia* mission, where full

6D coordinates will be known for large samples of stars in the halo—and therefore many debris structures—but stream membership is not known for all stars.

Motivated by the strengths of previous work, we identify a minimum set of issues that any approximate stream model or potential recovery method should address (see Section 3.5 for a more detailed discussion of these points in the context of this work):

1. **Observational uncertainties:** The known debris structures are $\gtrsim 10$ kpc from the Sun where distance and proper motion measurement errors are significant. Thus it is critical for any method that uses tidal debris to incorporate observational uncertainties and missing dimensions in a consistent and justified way.
2. **Form of the potential:** There is large uncertainty in the radial profile, shape, orientation, and graininess of the outer halo and the constancy of these parameters over distance. Properly describing the potential may require non-parametric techniques or complex analytic functions so the method should not rely on the existence of or ability to compute conserved orbital properties such as actions.
3. **Multiple debris structures:** Near-future photometric surveys such as *Gaia* and the *LSST* will likely discover many new streams and kinematic associations of stars. Potential recovery methods should be able to simultaneously use multiple streams and incorporate other dynamical constraints.
4. **Comparing models to data:** Matching generated streams to observed stellar densities is difficult; models that rely on this must account for observational biases, internal properties of the progenitor, and background halo stars.
5. **Computational expense:** Full N -body simulations are expensive to run; incorporating an N -body simulation into a likelihood function evaluation and then performing a

parameter search would be computationally intensive and, presently, intractable.

In Price-Whelan & Johnston (2013) (and Chapter 2), we introduced a simple method based on the work of Johnston et al. (1999b) for using individual stars associated with tidal debris combined with knowledge about the mass and orbit of the progenitor to constrain properties of the host galaxy potential. The method exploits the relationship between the phase-space distribution of debris and (measurable) properties of the progenitor system (e.g., the tidal radius and escape velocity). Specifically, a better potential is one in which orbits of test particle stars (integrated backwards from their present position) came close (within the tidal radius in position, and escape velocity in velocity) to the orbit of the progenitor at some time in the past.

In this *Chapter*, we present a fully probabilistic model (**Rewinder**) for tidal streams that builds on these simple scalings, which depend only on the mass and orbit of the progenitor and parent potential. By “probabilistic model” we mean a justified, parametrized likelihood function with priors on the parameters. **Rewinder** relies on numerical orbit integration in ordinary phase-space and can thus incorporate arbitrarily complex forms for the parent potential (such as time dependence and significant substructure). Individual stars are constraints on the potential, thus **Rewinder** can handle very small samples of well-measured stars (e.g., 8). Incorporating multiple streams, debris structures, and other kinematic information is trivial but will be explored in future work.

In Section 3.2 we describe a suite of N -body simulations that span a range of progenitor masses on a characteristic, mildly eccentric orbit and then use them in Section 3.3 to motivate a new, flexible model for tidal streams that works entirely in phase-space. In Section 3.4 we demonstrate how **Rewinder** can be used to measure properties of a non-trivial Galactic potential by performing several experiments with simulated observations of data from N -body simulations. In Section 3.5, we discuss the results of these experiments and the extent

to which we address the above points 1-5. We conclude in Section 3.6.

3.2 Simulations

We first perform a set of N -body simulations with the Self-Consistent Field (SCF) basis function expansion code (Hernquist & Ostriker 1992) to build realistic models of streams for studying the phase-space distribution of debris as it is stripped from its progenitor. We later use one of these simulations to test *Rewinder*. In each simulation, a 10^5 particle NFW-profile satellite was inserted at the apogalacticon of its orbit in a static, multi-component galaxy with a triaxial host halo, described below. The satellite was evolved first in isolation, then the host potential was turned on slowly over 10 satellite internal dynamical times to reduce artificial gravitational shocking. The initial position and velocity was obtained by integrating the orbit of the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy from present-day coordinates $\mathbf{r} = (19.0, 2.7, -6.9)$ kpc, $\mathbf{v} = (230., -35., 195.)$ km s $^{-1}$ (Law & Majewski 2010) backwards for 6 Gyr. The N -body satellite was then reintegrated from that initial position for the same interaction time and number of time-steps. This orbit has its apogalacticon at approximately 59 kpc and perigalacticon near 12 kpc with an average orbital period of 930 Myr, although all of these quantities vary over the course of the simulation due to the halo’s triaxiality. Total energy is conserved to $\sim 2\%$ of the satellite internal potential energy.

To capture the character of streams across a range of merger mass ratios, four satellites with masses $m = 2.5 \times 10^6, 2.5 \times 10^7, 2.5 \times 10^8, 2.5 \times 10^9 M_\odot$ (where m is the mass enclosed within 35 NFW scale radii, the radius out to which particles were realized in the NFW distribution), were evolved in the setup described above. Their scale radii, r_0 , were adjusted to maintain a constant density across all simulations which results in identical fractional mass-loss rates: 74% of the initial mass is lost by the end of each simulation. The base

value is $r_0 = 0.01565$ kpc at $m = 2.5 \times 10^6 M_\odot$. The maximum particle radius (i.e. $35 \times r_0$) was chosen to encompass the full range of concentrations of dark matter sub-halos seen in cosmological simulations of structure formation (following Bullock & Johnston 2005).

We take care to record the time at which each particle is unbound from the satellite in the simulations: we locate the position of the remnant iteratively by first calculating the satellite potential with all particles, removing particles with kinetic energies sufficient to escape, then recalculate the potential without those particles until the system converges. There is no spatial restriction on where a particle may become unbound and all particles (both bound and unbound) contribute their gravity during normal time-steps, presuming that they are resolved by the basis functions.

In all simulations, the host potential is taken to be a three-component sum of a Miyamoto-Nagai disk (Miyamoto & Nagai 1975), Hernquist spheroid, and a triaxial, logarithmic halo (e.g., Law & Majewski 2010):

$$\Phi_{\text{disk}}(R, z) = -\frac{GM_{\text{disk}}}{\sqrt{R^2 + (a + \sqrt{z^2 + b^2})^2}} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\Phi_{\text{spher}}(r) = -\frac{GM_{\text{spher}}}{r + c} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\Phi_{\text{halo}}(x, y, z) = v_h^2 \ln(C_1 x^2 + C_2 y^2 + C_3 xy + (z/q_z)^2 + r_h^2) \quad (3.3)$$

where R is the cylindrical radius, r is the spherical radius, M_{disk} is the mass of the disk, M_{spher} is the mass of the bulge or spheroid, the ratio b/a sets the flattening of the disk potential, c is the scale-length of the spheroid potential, v_h is the total halo mass normalization, and C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 are combinations of the x and y axis ratios (q_1 , q_2) and orientation of the halo

Figure 3.1: Equipotential contours for the LM10 potential (Eq. 3.7) in Galactocentric, cartesian coordinates for various halo parameter choices. For all panels, $v_h = 121.858$ km/s, $r_h = 12$ kpc, and $q_2 = 1$. Left to right, each column represents a new choice of parameters. If not specified, other parameters are fixed to $q_1 = q_z = 1$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$ (far left panels). Panels on far right show the best-fit parameter values from LM10.

with respect to the baryonic disk (ϕ):

$$C_1 = \frac{\cos^2 \phi}{q_1^2} + \frac{\sin^2 \phi}{q_2^2} \quad (3.4)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{\sin^2 \phi}{q_1^2} + \frac{\cos^2 \phi}{q_2^2} \quad (3.5)$$

$$C_3 = 2 \sin \phi \cos \phi (q_1^{-2} - q_2^{-2}). \quad (3.6)$$

The total potential then is just

$$\Phi_{\text{tot}} = \Phi_{\text{disk}} + \Phi_{\text{spher}} + \Phi_{\text{halo}}. \quad (3.7)$$

Figure 3.2: Particle positions (grey dots) in Galactocentric cartesian coordinates from the final time-step of four N -body simulations (Section 3.2) with the same progenitor orbit initial conditions over a range of progenitor masses (columns). Black crosses indicate eight particles chosen from each mass simulation and used in the experiments described in Section 3.4.

We use this potential not because we think it is a realistic representation of the Galactic potential, but because successful inference with this potential demonstrates that it is possible to recover information about non-trivial potential forms. Figure 3.1 shows equipotential slices in the Galactic X-Z plane ($Y=0$) and Y-Z plane ($X=0$) for a few choices of q_1 , q_z , and ϕ while holding all other parameters fixed, as described in the figure caption. The potential parameters used for the simulations are shown in the “Truth” column of Table 3.1.

3.3 Method (Rewinder)

Rewinder integrates stars and the progenitor back from their present-day, observed positions to the time at which they become unbound from the satellite, where we evaluate the likelihood

for each star. Below we (1) motivate a simple model for the debris just as it disrupts and (2) present this idea within a probabilistic framework for incorporating observational uncertainties and missing data. For a satellite galaxy orbiting within a static host potential, mass loss is driven by a combination of tidal stripping by the steady tidal field of the parent system and tidal shocking by the rapidly changing tidal field as the progenitor system moves through pericenter (e.g., Choi et al. 2009). On a mildly eccentric orbit, the tidal shocking is subdominant to the steady disruption. The interplay between these two processes as a function of orbital properties is outside the scope of this *Chapter* and will be explored in future work; we focus here on the slow removal of stars by steady tidal forcing.

3.3.1 Motivation: tidal debris

Consider a point-mass satellite with mass m on a circular orbit with frequency Ω around a more massive “host” mass $M \gg m$ (the “restricted three-body problem”; e.g., §8.3 Binney & Tremaine 2008). In a frame rotating with the orbital frequency of the satellite, the satellite remains fixed and the static, effective potential around the satellite has (amongst others) two unstable optima located around galactocentric radii $\sim R \pm r_J$, where R is the orbital radius of the satellite and r_J is the Jacobi or tidal radius

$$r_J \sim R \left(\frac{m}{3M} \right)^{1/3}. \quad (3.8)$$

Particles that would be bound to the satellite in isolation may have enough (Jacobi) energy to overcome the effective potential barrier at these Lagrange points (Fig. 8.6 of BT) and thus will be preferentially stripped from the satellite at these points. For a spherical, extended parent mass distribution the tidal radius instead scales with the enclosed mass at the instantaneous orbital radius, $R(t)$, with additional terms that account for the local slope of the density

profile. In general the satellite mass also depends on time. The tidal radius of the debris then follows

$$r_{\text{tide}}(t) = R(t) \left(\frac{m(t)}{3M_{\text{enc}}(R)} \right)^{1/3} \quad (3.9)$$

where M_{enc} is the instantaneous enclosed mass of the parent system within orbital radius R . In general, the Lagrange points may not be symmetric about the center of the satellite and may deviate from the tidal radius by factors of order unity.

The bulk velocity of the satellite will be of order $V \sim \sqrt{GM_{\text{enc}}/R}$. If the velocity dispersion of the satellite is $\sigma_v \sim \sqrt{Gm/r_J}$, then it follows

$$\sigma_v(t) \sim V \left(\frac{m(t)}{M_{\text{enc}}(t)} \right)^{1/3}. \quad (3.10)$$

(as pointed out in Binney & Tremaine 2008) and hence we expect the debris-star velocities also to scale with $(m/M_{\text{enc}})^{1/3}$. These scalings assume that the satellite is spherical with isotropic velocities as is reasonable for a globular cluster or dwarf spheroidal galaxy, but non-random, internal satellite orbits (e.g., a disk) will break these assumptions.

In a triaxial potential, the orbital plane of the satellite is not fixed but we still expect there to be *effective* Lagrange points for a spherical satellite system along the line of centers connecting the origin of the parent potential to the satellite—that is, we expect the stars to be stripped at some characteristic distance from the satellite (near the tidal radius) along the instantaneous position vector of the satellite with some dispersion about these points. We proceed by defining a coordinate system relative to the position and velocity of the progenitor, $(\mathbf{r}_p, \mathbf{v}_p)$, rotated into the instantaneous orbital plane defined by $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{r}_p \times \mathbf{v}_p$.

Note that this is the instantaneous orbital radius, *not* the orbital radius at pericenter.

Figure 3.3: Orbits of 2000 randomly-drawn, disrupted particles projected into the instantaneous orbital plane coordinates (Eqs. 3.11-3.13), normalized by the tidal radius (Eq. 3.9), and only shown within half a satellite crossing time around $t = t_{\text{ub}}$ for each of the four progenitor masses. The orbits were integrated backwards from their present-day positions (final time step of the N -body simulations) as test particles without the potential of the progenitor. Horizontal black line shows $x_2 = 0$ (top panels) and $x_3 = 0$ (bottom panels), and the unit circle (black circle) illustrates the classical disruption radius in these coordinates.

The (time-dependent) basis vectors are given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_1 = \frac{\mathbf{r}_p}{\|\mathbf{r}_p\|} \quad (3.11)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_2 = \frac{\mathbf{L} \times \hat{\mathbf{x}}_1}{\|\mathbf{L} \times \hat{\mathbf{x}}_1\|} \quad (3.12)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_3 = \hat{\mathbf{L}} = \frac{\mathbf{L}}{\|\mathbf{L}\|} = \frac{\mathbf{r}_p \times \mathbf{v}_p}{\|\mathbf{r}_p \times \mathbf{v}_p\|}. \quad (3.13)$$

Figure 3.3 shows sections of particle orbits (for particles that are stripped) from the N -body simulations described above, projected into this coordinate system. The positions are normalized by the instantaneous tidal radius (Eq. 3.9) and velocities are normalized by

Figure 3.4: Same as Figure 3.3 but for particle velocities normalized by the velocity scale (Eq. 3.10).

the instantaneous velocity scale (Eq. 3.10). Sections of the orbits symmetric around their unbinding times, t_{ub} , are shown for each of the four progenitor masses. In these coordinates, the classical Lagrange points would be located at $x_1 \approx \pm r_{\text{tide}}, x_2 = 0, x_3 = 0$ (illustrated by the intersection of the black unit circles and horizontal lines in Figure 3.3). Though not exactly centered on the point-mass Lagrange points derived for a circular orbit, the location of and dispersion about the effective Lagrange points in these scaled coordinates remain remarkably consistent across the range of progenitor masses explored. Figure 3.4 shows the velocity orbits of each star also projected into these coordinates and normalized. The dispersion in velocity is well-normalized by the velocity scale of Eq. 3.10, though it is clear that the velocity dispersion along \hat{x}_1 , the radial vector to the satellite position, is larger than that in other dimensions, possibly because of mild tidal shocking.

We conclude that even on a non-circular orbit in a complex potential, the dispersion—in position and velocity—of tidally stripped debris as it comes unbound from the satellite scales

with the mass ratio $(m/M_{\text{enc}})^{1/3}$. This motivates a model for tidal debris in which each star was “released” at the instantaneous, effective Lagrange point at its unbinding time, t_{ub} , with a dispersion in position and velocity, all of which depend only on the mass and orbit of the progenitor and the parent potential. We present this model in detail below.

3.3.2 Probabilistic model

Suppose we observe the 6D position of a star, $\mathbf{D} = (l, b, d, \mu_l, \mu_b, v_r)$, in heliocentric coordinates—e.g., the measured position on the sky, (l, b) ; distance, d ; proper motions, (μ_l, μ_b) ; and line-of-sight velocity, v_r —and have determined through some other means that this star was once part of a progenitor system (e.g., satellite galaxy) with mass $m(t)$ that is disrupting and forming a cold debris structure in the potential, Φ , of the parent galaxy (e.g., the Milky Way). We assume that the mass of the parent system enclosed within the pericenter of the orbit of the satellite, $M_{\text{enc}}(R_{\text{peri}})$, is much larger than the initial mass of the satellite, $M_{\text{enc}}(R_{\text{peri}}) \gg m(t = 0)$. The present position of the progenitor is observed to be at heliocentric position \mathbf{D}_p (where any subscript p refers to the progenitor). In general, the data for the star and progenitor will have significant uncertainties or missing dimensions at distances typical to the Galactic halo, thus we define \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{W}_p as the true 6D, heliocentric positions of the star and progenitor and will include these in our model. Since we include these positions as parameters, this method will work even when the star has missing dimensions or the progenitor location is unknown (as in the Orphan stream, Belokurov et al. 2007a).

To model the true, 6D, present-day position of the star, \mathbf{W} , we first transform to cartesian, Galactocentric coordinates where $(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{v}_0)$ and $(\mathbf{r}_{p,0}, \mathbf{v}_{p,0})$ are the position and velocity of the star and progenitor today. The star is taken as having been sampled at $t = t_{\text{ub}}$ (the unbinding time) from an isotropic Gaussian centered on one of the effective Lagrange points in position, and an isotropic Gaussian centered on the origin in velocity. The present-day

phase-space position is the result of integrating this sample forward from t_{ub} in the parent potential, Φ , whose form is parametrized by the vector Θ_Φ . We assume that once the star becomes “unbound” from the satellite the potential of the satellite can be ignored, and thus we treat the star as a test particle.

The satellite mass enters this prescription through the tidal radius; a changing satellite mass will skew the positions of the effective Lagrange points and velocity scale. We allow for mass-loss by incorporating the initial satellite mass, m_0 , and a constant mass-loss term, \dot{m} into the model: $m(t) = m_0 - \dot{m}t$. We assume constant mass-loss as an example of a simple, monotonically decreasing function, but this an arbitrary choice. We don't expect this assumption to have a large effect on our conclusions as the mass only enters the model through the tidal radius as $m^{1/3}$: even if we ignored mass-loss entirely, the progenitor and orbit considered here has lost 75% of its mass by the end of the simulation corresponding to a factor of just ~ 1.6 difference in tidal radius. In principle, with more data, the mass-loss history could be inferred self-consistently by the model, but we leave this exercise for future work.

Finally, we add two additional parameters: a constant, global factor, α , that scales the position of the effective Lagrange points relative to the classical tidal radius, and a binary parameter β (one for each star), that is either -1 or $+1$ depending on whether the star is in the leading or trailing tail. To compress notation, we pack all progenitor parameters into the vector $\Theta_p = (\mathbf{W}_p, m_0, \dot{m}, \alpha)$. The likelihood for this model is:

$$p(\mathbf{W} \mid \Theta_p, \Theta_\Phi, \beta, t_{\text{ub}}) = p(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{v}_0, \mid \Theta_p, \Theta_\Phi, \beta, t_{\text{ub}}) |\mathbf{J}| \quad (3.14)$$

$$p(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{v}_0, \mid \Theta_p, \Theta_\Phi, \beta, t_{\text{ub}}) = [\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{r} \mid \Theta_p, \beta) \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{v} \mid \Theta_p)]_{t_{\text{ub}}} \quad (3.15)$$

This assumption breaks down for sufficiently large-mass progenitors with total mass somewhere between $\sim 10^8 - 10^9 M_\odot$.

where \mathcal{N} represents the normal distribution, r_{tide} is given by Eq. 3.9, and σ_v by Eq. 3.10 and the positions and velocities $(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{r}_p, \mathbf{v}_p)$ are evaluated at the unbinding time, t_{ub} , by integrating the orbits backwards from $(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{v}_0, \mathbf{r}_{p,0}, \mathbf{v}_{p,0})$. $|\mathbf{J}| = \left| \frac{\partial(x,y,z,v_x,v_y,v_z)}{\partial(l,b,d,\mu_l,\mu_b,v_r)} \right|$ is the absolute value of the determinant of the Jacobian that defines the transformation from heliocentric, spherical to Galactocentric, cartesian coordinates. We then marginalize the likelihood over all possible unbinding times, assuming a uniform prior of unbinding times over the entire interaction time:

$$p(\mathbf{W} | \Theta_p, \Theta_\Phi, \beta) = \int_0^{t_{\text{int}}} p(\mathbf{W} | \Theta_p, \Theta_\Phi, \beta, t_{\text{ub}}) p(t_{\text{ub}}) dt_{\text{ub}} \quad (3.16)$$

where the interaction time is taken to be $t_{\text{int}} = 6$ Gyr, the total duration of the simulations of Section 3.2.

The likelihood above is evaluated for each star at all time-steps of the simulation during the marginalization with a uniform prior over all possible unbinding times. We chose this approach because the phase-space position (and hence time) at which a star becomes unbound from a satellite can only be strictly defined for the case of a spherical satellite orbiting on a circular orbit in a spherical potential. Various authors have chosen to measure mass loss in simulations of satellite disruption on eccentric orbits in non-spherical potentials by either looking at the kinetic energy of the particles relative to the satellite’s potential energy (Johnston et al. 1995) or looking at the point at which a star crosses the instantaneous tidal radius (Küpper et al. 2012). Neither choice is strictly valid and both have been found useful for representing the mass-loss process. Hence we make the simplest choice of using Gaussians to characterize the phase-space distribution of debris as it makes the transition between being bound and unbound. We find that changing this distribution to a log-normal distribution does not affect our conclusions.

We assume that the observational uncertainties are Gaussian in heliocentric, spherical coordinates, such that

$$p(\mathbf{D} | \mathbf{W}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{D} | \mathbf{W}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}) \quad (3.17)$$

$$p(\mathbf{D}_p | \mathbf{W}_p) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{D}_p | \mathbf{W}_p, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_p) \quad (3.18)$$

where the covariance matrices $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_p$ specify the observational uncertainties on the observed 6D position of the star and progenitor, respectively.

For a single star, the evaluation of the likelihood works as follows: given observed, present-day coordinates for the star and progenitor $(\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{D}_p)$, potential parameter values $(\boldsymbol{\Theta}_\Phi)$, and nuisance parameter values (α, β) ,

1. transform star and progenitor positions in heliocentric coordinates to Galactocentric, cartesian coordinates;
2. integrate star and progenitor orbits backwards as test particles in the potential given by $\boldsymbol{\Theta}_\Phi$ for the total interaction time, t_{int} (in this case, ~ 6 Gyr);
3. transform the particle position to the relative, normalized coordinates defined in Section 3.3.1;
4. compute the likelihood given by Equation 3.14 at each time-step of the integration and marginalize over the unbinding time, t_{ub} .

Assuming each star is an independent tracer, the full likelihood for many stars is then just the product of the individual likelihoods:

$$p(\{\mathbf{D}^{(i)}\}, \mathbf{D}_p | \{\boldsymbol{\Theta}^{(i)}\}, \boldsymbol{\Theta}_p, \boldsymbol{\Theta}_\Phi) = p(\mathbf{D}_p | \mathbf{W}_p) \prod_i p(\mathbf{D}^{(i)} | \mathbf{W}^{(i)}) p(\mathbf{W}^{(i)} | \boldsymbol{\Theta}_p, \boldsymbol{\Theta}_\Phi, \beta^{(i)}) \quad (3.19)$$

where $\Theta^{(i)} = (\mathbf{W}^{(i)}, \beta^{(i)})$. All parameters are summarized in Table 3.1.

3.4 Experiments

In what follows, we use `Rewinder` to model “observations” of a small sample of stars from one of the N -body simulations described in Section 3.2. We consider this a strong test of the method because the data are generated with N -body simulations that do not resemble the likelihood function presented above. For all tests in this *Chapter*, we use the same functional form for the potential as used in the simulations (Equation 3.7). When recovering the potential, we hold fixed the disk and spheroid parameters (see Table 3.1), along with one of the halo parameters: the scale radius, r_h . The priors on the remaining halo parameters are taken to be uniform over a conservative domain of realistic values: for v_h , 100-200 km/s corresponds to a range in solar circular velocities from ~ 210 -250 km/s (holding other parameters fixed); the range in axis ratios allow for prolate, oblate, and generic triaxiality; and ϕ is restricted to $\pm 45^\circ$ around the true simulation value, $\phi = 97^\circ$.

For all experiments below, we use a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm to sample from the posterior probability distribution given by our model. Standard MCMC algorithms (e.g., Metropolis-Hastings) update a single chain while exploring parameter space. We instead use an affine-invariant “ensemble” sampler (Goodman & Weare 2010) that at each step in parameter space, updates the positions of many “walkers” (the ensemble). This algorithm is implemented in the `Python` programming language (Foreman-Mackey et al. 2013) and runs naturally in a parallelized environment such as the message passing interface (MPI). In each experiment we run the walkers for a large number of steps from starting positions described below, then throw away these samples and take the positions from the final step of this “burn-in” phase as a starting point for the samples used for inference. We

compute the autocorrelation time, t_{acor} , for each sampled parameter (using *ACOR*) and thin the chains by taking every $\max(t_{\text{acor}})$ sample to ensure the samples are close to independent. The autocorrelation time measures the number of steps required to produce independent samples from the posterior probability distribution: a shorter autocorrelation time means that fewer steps (and therefore fewer likelihood evaluations) are required to produce close to independent samples from the posterior.

3.4.1 Data with negligible uncertainties

We test *Rewinder* using only eight stars (particles)—four from the leading tail, and four from the trailing tail—randomly sampled from the $2.5 \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$ simulation (Section 3.2), assuming the observed 6D positions for both the stars and the progenitor have negligible uncertainties. The stars were required to have been stripped after the first pericentric passage and have a present-day distance within 40 kpc of the Sun. Figure 3.2 (second column from right) shows the randomly chosen stars (black crosses) in Galactic coordinates, over-plotted on all other simulated particles (grey points).

We leave the potential parameters (q_1, q_z, ϕ, v_h, r_h) free to vary, along with the Lagrange point offset, α , and initialize an ensemble of 64 MCMC walkers by sampling from the priors summarized in Table 3.1. We run the walkers for 5000 steps to burn-in, then restart the sampler starting from the final position of the burn-in phase and run for another 10000 inference steps. Figure 3.5 shows the walker positions over the 10000 inference steps for each of the parameters. The autocorrelation time for each parameter is displayed on its corresponding panel. Figure 3.6 shows projections of the posterior probability distribution for the parameters; with perfect data, the uncertainties on the potential parameters are all

<http://www.math.nyu.edu/faculty/goodman/software/acor/>
<https://github.com/dfm/acor>

$< 1\%$.

3.4.2 Data with near-future uncertainties

We next take the same eight stars used in the previous experiment and “observe” them with optimistic observational uncertainties. We require these stars to be RR Lyrae variables which are known to be excellent distance indicators via the mid-infrared period-luminosity relation (as shown in, e.g., Madore & Freedman 2012). Nearly 100 RR Lyrae associated with the Sgr stream and ~ 30 associated with the Orphan stream will be observed with *Spitzer* as part of the SMASH survey (Johnston et al. 2013) with expected fractional distance uncertainties around $\sim 2\%$. These stars will also be included in the *Gaia* proper motion catalog: at a distance of ~ 50 kpc, a typical RR Lyrae will have a tangential velocity error around ~ 20 km/s, though our sample of test stars are all within 40 kpc.

For this experiment, we (1) assume the stars are RR Lyrae stars (e.g., bright distance indicators) such that the fractional distance uncertainty is 2%; (2) neglect the uncertainty in angular position, l, b (for a typical RR Lyrae at 50 kpc this is $\sim 10^{-7}$ deg for *Gaia*); (3) assume we can measure radial velocities to these stars with 5 km/s uncertainty; and (4) compute the sky-averaged *Gaia* proper-motion uncertainty for each star assuming an F0V spectral type using the *PyGaia* code and use this uncertainty for both components of proper motion. We further assume that we know the tail assignment for each star, β . We observe the position of the progenitor with the same observational uncertainties though in reality some coordinates will have even better measurements.

This experiment samples over the five potential parameters, the Lagrange point offset, four phase-space coordinate parameters for each star (32 total), and four phase-space coordinate parameters for the progenitor—41 parameters in total. We use an ensemble of

<https://github.com/agabrown/PyGaia>

Figure 3.5: Positions of all 64 MCMC walkers (see Section 3.4) for each parameter at each step of the inference (black lines). The MCMC chains do not display any bulk movement or stray walkers, implying, by eye, that the chains have converged. We also compute the autocorrelation functions for each parameter and find that, for this experiment, the autocorrelation times are short (as shown on each panel in this figure). Projections of the binned samples (posterior densities) are shown in Figure 3.6.

256 walkers and draw initial conditions for the coordinate parameters by sampling from Gaussian’s centered on the “observed” value with variances specified by the observational uncertainties. Other parameters—potential parameters and α —are initialized by drawing from the priors summarized in Table 3.1. We burn in the walkers for 50000 steps and run for 100000 inference steps, but thin the chains by taking every $\max(t_{\text{acor}})$ sample, where $\max(t_{\text{acor}}) \approx 4000$ steps. Figures 3.7, 3.8, 3.9 show the marginalized posteriors for the potential parameters, satellite parameters, and parameters for a single particle. The uncertainties on the potential parameters are only 5-7% for the flattenings and circular velocity, but $\sim 15\%$ for the scale radius, r_h .

3.4.3 Precise distance measurements with missing proper motions

The Spitzer Merger History and Shape of the Galactic Halo survey (SMASH; Johnston et al. 2013) will be completed within a year (early 2015), long before the final *Gaia* data release. Thus, we will soon have precise distance measurements for stars in the Sgr and Orphan streams, but poor or no proper motion constraints. SMASH also targets several RR Lyrae in the Sgr core, which will enable a high-precision distance measurement of the progenitor. We now consider a case in which we have high-precision (2%) distances to stream stars and the progenitor, 10 km/s radial velocity uncertainty, and a proper motion uncertainty for the Sgr core of 0.2 mas yr^{-1} (Pryor et al. 2010), but missing proper motions for the stream stars.

As with Section 3.4.2, this experiment includes 41 model parameters in total. We again use an ensemble of 256 walkers. Potential parameters and α are again initialized by drawing from the priors summarized in Table 3.1. We burn in the walkers for 50000 steps and run for 500000 inference steps. We again thin the chains by taking every $\max(t_{\text{acor}})$ sample, but here the autocorrelation time is found to be very long, $\max(t_{\text{acor}}) \approx 15000$ steps. Figures 3.10, 3.11, 3.12 show the marginalized posteriors for the potential parameters, satellite parame-

ters, and parameters for a single particle. Even a small sample of stars with precise distance measurements provide an enormous amount of information about the triaxiality of the potential. The uncertainties on the potential parameters are only 7-10% for the flattening and circular velocity, but $\sim 40\%$ for the scale radius, r_h . The initially missing star proper-motions are recovered with $\sim 5-10\%$ uncertainties.

3.5 Discussion

1. Observational uncertainties: Any method that uses tidal debris as a potential measure must also model the (significant) uncertainties on the kinematic measurements; *Rewinder* handles observational uncertainties and missing data dimensions by including the true 6D positions of stars and the progenitor as model parameters. In this *Chapter* we have tested *Rewinder* using data of varied quality for a small sample of stars.

2. Form of the potential: No assumptions were made about the the form of the Galactic potential in deriving the likelihood for *Rewinder*. The simple experiments in this *Chapter* infer potential parameters from the same static, analytic potential used in the N -body simulations that generated the fake data. However, in principle the potential could be time-dependent, clumpy, or have properties that vary with radius. The orbits of the stars and progenitor are directly integrated and only require a function that evaluates the acceleration due to the potential at a given position (and time). We have shown that with the correct form for the Galactic potential, *precise* measurements of the potential parameters are attainable with near-future data, but we have not discussed the *accuracy* of such measurements due to incorrect assumptions. For example, (Bonaca et al. 2014) show that using a static potential model to fit the live potential of the *Via Lactea* halo with tidal streams can introduce significant biases to measurements of the halo mass, even with perfect knowledge of the 6D

coordinates of stars in the streams. In future work, we will (1) try fitting incorrect potential models to see if we can still recover global properties (e.g., flattening); (2) run simulations with smoothly changing potentials (e.g., Buist & Helmi 2014) and attempt to model the time dependence; and (3) explore using a generic, non-parametric potential form (e.g., a basis function expansion) as the recovery potential model.

3. Multiple debris structures: Each stream will provide constraints on different properties of the potential. For example, more eccentric streams may better constrain the radial profile (see Deg & Widrow 2014, who illustrate the power of using multiple streams to simultaneously constrain the potential using orbit fitting). In this *Chapter*, we only consider a stream on a Sgr-like orbit, which lies nearly in the Galactic x - z plane. We find that the stream puts better constraints on the z -axis flattening, q_z , than on the flattening in the x - y plane, q_1 , as one might expect. The best measurements of the detailed shape of the Galactic potential will come from combining constraints from multiple streams. We have defined above a proper likelihood function for observed stars in a given stream, thus incorporating multiple streams into the inference only requires multiplying the likelihoods computed for each stream and progenitor pair.

4. Comparing models to data: With *Rewinder*, each star adds constraints on the potential parameters and does not require matching a simulated density to the observed density of stars, thus this method works well even for small samples of well-measured stream stars. It might be that the most relevant stellar samples for inferring the Milky Way potential are small. For instance, stars that produce good distance estimates might be much more valuable than typical stars in the sample so that we may limit to only variable stars, e.g., RR Lyraes. These valuable stars are rare (and their abundances are age and metallicity dependent); there could be many cold structures in the Milky Way halo that are highly constraining on the potential in principle, but which contain only a few good distance-

indicating members. It is not yet known what the trade-offs are between having many stars at low precision and a few at high precision, nor is it known how valuable distance information really is, when a structure contains many precisely observed members.

5. Computational expense: One point of concern for `Rewinder` is that the number of parameters scales with eight times the number of stars: each star has six coordinate parameters (the true position), the unbinding time, and the tail assignment. Computational constraints limit the sample size, but even so, the inference is much faster than full N -body modeling because the stars and progenitor are treated as test particles. Each step in parameter space with `Rewinder` requires integrating the orbits of stars and the progenitor: we presently integrate with a fixed time-step using leapfrog integration. Computing the acceleration due to the given potential at each step is implemented in `Cython` (and approaches C-like speed), but the rest of the code is written in pure-Python. Though already significantly less computationally intensive than running a full N -body simulation for every parameter step, running each MCMC walker for $\gtrsim 100000$ steps requires parallelization a few hours of CPU time on a compute cluster. Further optimization of the integration method (e.g., using an adaptive method or implementing in `Cython`) could speed up the inference significantly.

3.6 Conclusions

We have presented a probabilistic model (`Rewinder`)—a likelihood function and with priors on the parameters—for using stars observed in tidal streams to constrain properties of any underlying gravitational potential. `Rewinder` relies on direct orbit integration and not on computing conserved quantities (e.g., actions) and can thus be used with arbitrarily complex (e.g., time-dependent or clumpy) forms of the potential. We have performed several experiments to show that `Rewinder` simultaneously constrains the potential and models a

tidal stream given simulated data with a range of realistic uncertainties. We find that with future high-quality data—that is, high precision distance measurements from RR Lyrae and proper motions from *Gaia*—a small sample of just eight stars in a tidal stream modeled with *Rewinder* provide measurements of potential parameters that rival present-day constraints from comparing full N -body simulations to large numbers of stellar tracers with poorly measured kinematics. For this high-quality data, we recover the input potential parameter values with uncertainties of order 5-7 percent. Without proper motion data the uncertainties range from 10-40 percent. We consider this work to be an encouraging first step towards the goal of recovering the (presumably) much more complex—time-dependent, clumpy, with axis ratios and orientations that vary with radius—Milky Way potential with larger data sets.

Acknowledgments

We thank Anthony Brown (Leiden) for insight on the *Gaia* data quality and for providing the open source *PyGaia* code for computing predicted uncertainties. We thank the organizers of the Gaia Challenge (2013) and the University of Surrey for hospitality during the workshop. We thank Ana Bonaca (Yale), Jo Bovy (IAS), Dan Foreman-Mackey (NYU), Marla Geha (Yale), Andreas Küpper (Columbia), and Hans-Walter Rix (MPIA) for useful discussions. KVJ thanks the Institute of Astronomy at the University of Cambridge for hospitality and Vasily Belokurov (IoA) and his group for discussion of his work while there. APW is supported by a National Science Foundation Graduate Research Fellowship under Grant No. 11-44155. This work was supported in part by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. PHYS-1066293 and AST-1312196. DWH was partially supported by the NSF (Grant IIS-1124794) and the Moore-Sloan Data Science Environment at NYU. This research made use of Astropy, a community-developed core Python package for Astronomy (Astropy Col-

laboration et al. 2013). This research has made use of NASA's Astrophysics Data System. This work additionally relied on Columbia University's *Hotfoot* and *Yeti* compute clusters, and we acknowledge the Columbia HPC support staff for assistance.

<i>Milky Way parameters</i> (Θ_{Φ})			
Component	Parameter	Truth	Prior
disk	M_{disk}	$1.0 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$	fixed
	a	6.5 kpc	fixed
	b	0.26 kpc	fixed
spheroid	M_{spher}	$3.4 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$	fixed
	c	0.7 kpc	fixed
halo	v_{h}	121.858	$\mathcal{U}(100, 200)$ km/s
	q_1	1.38	$\mathcal{U}(1, 2)$
	q_2	1.0	fixed
	q_z	1.36	$\mathcal{U}(1, 2)$
	ϕ	97	$\mathcal{U}(52, 142)$ deg
	r_{h}	12 kpc	$\mathcal{U}(8, 50)$ kpc
<i>Progenitor parameters</i> (Θ_{p})			
position	$\mathbf{r}_{\text{p},0}$	–	$\ \mathbf{r}_{\text{p},0}\ \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 200)$ kpc
velocity	$\mathbf{v}_{\text{p},0}$	–	$\ \mathbf{v}_{\text{p},0}\ \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 500)$ km/s
Lagrange pt. offset	α	–	$\mathcal{U}(0.5, 2.5)$
initial mass	m_0	$2.5 \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$	fixed
mass loss	\dot{m}	–	$3.2 \times 10^4 M_{\odot}/\text{Myr}$ (fixed)
<i>Star parameters</i> ($\Theta^{(i)}$)			
position	\mathbf{r}_0	–	$\ \mathbf{r}_0\ \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 200)$ kpc
velocity	\mathbf{v}_0	–	$\ \mathbf{v}_0\ \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 500)$ km/s
tail assignment	β	–	± 1 equally likely (fixed at truth)

Table 3.1: Parameter values used in the experiments of Section 3.4. \mathcal{N} is the normal (Gaussian) distribution, and \mathcal{U} the uniform distribution. There are 11 parameters for the Milky Way potential, but only the halo parameters are left free to vary; some parameters are fixed (denoted by “(fixed)”) at the true values used in the N -body simulations that generated the fake test data. The progenitor has nine parameters—the position, \mathbf{r}_{p} , and velocity, \mathbf{v}_{p} , vectors each contain three components—but only five are left free to vary. The sky coordinates (e.g., Galactic l , b) are assumed to be known with negligible uncertainty. Each star has eight associated parameters, five of which are allowed to vary. Sky coordinates are fixed, along with the tail assignment (whether the star belongs to the leading or trailing tail). For inference with eight stars, there are $4 + 5 + 8 \times 4 = 41$ free parameters.

Figure 3.6: Projections of the posterior probability distribution over the five potential parameters (q_1 , q_z , ϕ , v_h , r_h) and Lagrange point offset (α) assuming negligible uncertainties on the observed phase-space coordinates of eight stars and the progenitor, visualized as two-dimensional histograms of MCMC samples. Solid contours (black lines) show approximately 1σ and 2σ levels of the distribution. Vertical and horizontal lines (blue) show the true, input values for the potential parameters used in the N -body simulations. For the potential parameters, the axis ranges are chosen to be the same for this and the potential posterior plots to follow.

Figure 3.7: Projections of the marginal posterior over the triaxial potential parameters for observed stars and progenitor with near-future uncertainties (Section 3.4.2). Axis ranges show the lower and upper bounds on the uniform priors over these parameters.

Figure 3.8: Projections of the marginal posterior over the progenitor parameters for observed stars and progenitor with near-future uncertainties (Section 3.4.2).

Figure 3.9: Projections of the marginal posterior over parameters for one of the stars for observed stars and progenitor with near-future uncertainties (Section 3.4.2).

Figure 3.10: Same as Figure 3.7 but for data with no proper motion measurements.

Figure 3.11: Same as Figure 3.8 but for data with no proper motion measurements.

Figure 3.12: Same as Figure 3.9 but for data with no proper motion measurements.

Chapter 4

Chaotic dispersal of tidal debris

4.1 Introduction

The dark-matter haloes of galaxies are thought to be triaxial in shape with axis ratios and alignments that depend on radius. However, despite suggestive evidence from a range of complimentary observational methods, this fundamental prediction from Λ CDM cosmology has not been conclusively verified. Around other galaxies, it is generally hard to measure the 3D mass profile because informative tracers are rare and the haloes are seen in projection. From the Earth's position within the Milky Way, our view of our own halo and proximity gives us a unique chance to directly measure the 6D positions of stars and model the shape of the mass distribution at large radii. The Milky Way halo has a low density of visible tracers, but luckily many of the halo stars are likely associated with debris stripped from stellar systems and thus contain additional information encoded by the formation mechanism.

As a satellite galaxy or globular cluster orbits within some larger system, mass is eroded by tidal forces from the host-galaxy potential. Along regular, mildly eccentric orbits, mass

This section contains text from an article published in Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society, Volume 455, Issue 1, p.1079-1098 (2016).

stripped from the progenitor has a small spread in orbital properties (e.g., energy, angular momentum). Once the debris has evolved far enough from the progenitor system that the self-gravity of the progenitor can be ignored (usually a fast process relative to the orbital time), the stars evolve essentially as an ensemble of test particle orbits in the potential of the host system. The debris remains coherent as a tidal stream if the phase-mixing time-scale is long: a small ensemble of regular orbits reaches a fully phase-mixed state in a timescale $\approx \sigma_\Omega^{-1}$, where σ_Ω is the dispersion in fundamental frequencies of the ensemble (tidal debris from a globular cluster typically has frequency spreads $\approx 0.1\text{--}1\%$, so it can take hundreds to thousands of orbital periods to fully phase-mix). The ensemble spreads due to shearing from slight variations in their fundamental frequencies, which, for tidal streams, preferentially occurs along one dimension (Merritt & Valluri 1996; Helmi & White 1999).

The morphological (density) evolution of the tidal debris therefore depends on the spread of orbital properties (e.g., actions or frequencies) of the debris and the orbit of the progenitor system, both of which are also determined by the shape and radial profile of the gravitational potential of the host galaxy. By modeling the observed phase-space density of stream stars along with the host galaxy potential it is hoped that we may infer the 3D mass distribution of the host. Many tidal streams are observed around the Milky Way, M31, and other nearby galaxies; the known streams span a large range of distances—from ≈ 10 to 100 kpc—and progenitor masses—from $\approx 10^3$ to $\approx 10^8 M_\odot$ in stellar mass—(Ibata et al. 1994; Odenkirchen et al. 2001; Belokurov et al. 2006; Grillmair & Dionatos 2006; Grillmair 2006; Bonaca et al. 2012). There has been extensive work on developing methods to use data from these streams to measure properties of the Milky Way’s dark matter halo. These methods span a range of complexity from orbit-fitting, to *Streakline* (Küpper et al. 2012) or ‘particle-spray’ models (Gibbons et al. 2014), to action-space density modeling (e.g., Sanders 2014; Bovy 2014), to N -body simulations (e.g., Law & Majewski 2010). All methods have been tested in some

way on simulated observations of data and these tests typically demonstrate the recovery of parameters for analytic, static potential forms.

One example of stream modeling in a multi-component (static, analytic) potential was presented by Pearson et al. (2015), who aimed to reproduce observations of the stellar stream density from the globular cluster Palomar 5 in a single oblate and single triaxial potential using *Streakline* (Küpper et al. 2012) and N -body models. They used the observed number density of stream stars, a limited number of radial velocities for stream members, and the sky position, distance, radial velocity, and proper motion of the cluster itself to fit model streams to the data. In the oblate potential (a three-component bulge+disk+spherical halo potential), a thin model stream was easily found that reproduces the observed stellar density morphology of the stream. In the triaxial potential (the potential from Law & Majewski (2010): a three component bulge+disk+triaxial halo fit to Sagittarius stream data), the model streams generically formed large, two-dimensional ‘fans’ of debris near the ends, and no physically reasonable progenitor orbits could be found that reproduced the observed thinness and curvature of the stream given the observational constraints of the present-day position and velocity of the cluster. The result in Pearson et al. (2015) demonstrates that the morphology of a stream alone can be used to rule out a potential. With an understanding of the circumstances that lead to the differences in stream morphology, this could be a powerful tool for rejecting potentials from positional information alone.

The obvious difference between the two potentials considered by Pearson et al. (2015) is the extra symmetry of the oblate potential. It is well known that the number of degrees of freedom of a potential plays a critical role in determining the orbit structure of the potential; Hamiltonians with more than two degrees of freedom generically contain significant chaotic regions. Pearson et al. (2015) tested the stochasticity of the orbit of the progenitor that produced ‘fanned’ debris by computing the Lyapunov exponent along this orbit but found

that it is consistent with being regular over dynamically relevant timescales (many Hubble times). It has been shown previously that along some strongly chaotic orbits and in live cosmological haloes, tidal streams do form large, diffuse ‘fans’ of debris (e.g., Fardal et al. 2015; Ngan et al. 2015), however it is unknown how the resultant properties of the debris (e.g., density or length of the stream) depend on the degree of stochasticity. The result from Pearson et al. (2015) suggests that even weak chaos (as measured by the Lyapunov exponent) may affect the density evolution and therefore observability of tidal streams. Understanding why this occurs and developing a measure to quantify the importance of this enhanced density evolution is a promising new direction to be explored further.

In this *Chapter*, we study the effect of chaotic diffusion of the fundamental frequencies of individual orbits on the density evolution of tidal debris. We choose a simple, cosmologically motivated model for a triaxial potential, analyze the degree of chaos as computed from single-orbit diagnostics for grids of constant-energy orbits, and compare these results to measures of the density evolution of finite-volume ensembles of orbits (meant to mimic tidal debris). We find that even when the chaotic timescale is predicted to be long for a given orbit, chaos may manifest over much shorter times in small orbit ensembles through the chaotic diffusion of the constituent orbits. For a chaotic orbit, the frequency spectrum of the orbit evolves with time: for a small ensemble, the spread in frequencies is therefore time-dependent, which could enhance phase-mixing. This idea supports a reevaluation of the importance of chaos in galactic haloes and implies that the amount of chaos in a given potential may have significant consequences for the observability and survivability of thin, cold tidal streams.

This *Chapter* is organized as follows. We review relevant nonlinear dynamics in Section 4.2. In Section 4.3, we describe our choice of potential, method for numerical orbit integration, and introduce the chaos indicators used in this work. Our results are split into three subsections: in Section 4.4.1 we present iso-energy grids of orbits and discuss the or-

bit classes and chaotic timescales present in our potential; in Section 4.4.2 we study the density evolution of small ensembles of orbits around each orbit of the previous section; in Section 4.4.3 we describe the behavior of chaotic diffusion and use this to explain how chaos is relevant for tidal streams over short times. We discuss the implications of our results in Section 4.5, and conclude in Section 4.6.

4.2 Review of nonlinear dynamics

To explore the question of if and how chaos manifests in the density evolution of orbit ensembles over timescales much shorter than that predicted from generic chaos indicators, we must first understand the behavior of individual orbits in complex gravitational potentials and the orbital structures in the potential itself (i.e. the strength of resonances and chaos). An orbit in an N degree of freedom (dof) Hamiltonian, H , is a set of $2N$ quasi-periodic time series,

$$(w_1(t), \dots, w_{2N}(t)) = (q_1(t), \dots, q_N(t), p_1(t), \dots, p_N(t)) \quad (4.1)$$

where q_k and p_k are conjugate coordinates in the sense that

$$\dot{p}_k = -\frac{\partial H}{\partial q_k} \quad (4.2)$$

$$\dot{q}_k = \frac{\partial H}{\partial p_k} \quad (4.3)$$

for all t . If bounded, the motion in any component, $w_k(t)$, can be described as a Fourier sum,

$$w_k(t) = \sum_j^{\infty} a_{kj} e^{i\omega_j t} \quad (4.4)$$

where the a_{kj} are complex amplitudes.

A *regular orbit* is a set of such time series that can be transformed to a special set of canonical coordinates known as angle-action coordinates. In these coordinates, the position variables are angles, $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, that increase linearly with time with rates set by N constant, fundamental frequencies, $\boldsymbol{\Omega} = (\Omega_1, \dots, \Omega_N)$. The frequency of a Fourier component (the ω_k in Equation 4.4) for any individual component of motion are just linear, integer combinations of the fundamental frequencies, $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ —that is, for a regular orbit, any Fourier component frequency may be written

$$\omega_j = \mathbf{n}_j \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega} \quad (4.5)$$

where \mathbf{n}_k is a vector of N integers. The conjugate momentum coordinates—the actions, \mathbf{J} —are constants of motion. Even stronger, the actions are isolating integrals and any pair are in involution such that

$$[J_\alpha, J_\beta] = 0 \quad (4.6)$$

where $[\cdot, \cdot]$ is the Poisson bracket. This implies that for an N dof system, a regular orbit has N independent constants of motion and the motion is therefore restricted to an N -dimensional manifold embedded in the $2N$ dimensional phase space. The topology of angle-action space is toroidal and any regular orbit in an N dof Hamiltonian can be understood as motion on the surface of an N -torus. Each set of actions, (J_1, \dots, J_N) (or frequencies), labels a torus, and regular orbits are sometimes referred to in terms of their orbital tori (see, e.g., Section 50 in Arnold 1978, Section 10-5 in Goldstein 1980, Section 3.5 in Binney & Tremaine 2008).

4.2.1 Orbits in integrable potentials

A Hamiltonian or potential is said to be *globally integrable* when the number of isolating integrals of motion is equal to the number of degrees of freedom and a transformation to

angle-action coordinates may be done globally—for example, the transformation to angle-action coordinates may be written as a function of arbitrary phase-space coordinates and the functional form is independent of phase-space position (e.g., Goldstein 1980). The condition for global integrability is very restrictive and the likelihood that a Hamiltonian is globally integrable decreases as the number of degrees of freedom increase (e.g., Lichtenberg & Lieberman 1983) and as the potential becomes more complex (i.e. containing multiple components with different shapes). In a globally integrable potential, the Hamiltonian may be written solely in terms of the actions, $H = H(\mathbf{J})$. Galactic potentials are almost certainly not globally integrable but it is useful to understand the orbit structure in integrable systems before extending to more general potentials. For example, there are four general classes of orbits in the ‘Perfect Ellipsoid’ potential (an integrable triaxial potential and special case of the Stäckel potential; see, e.g., Kuzmin 1973; de Zeeuw 1985): box, inner long-axis tube, outer long-axis tube, and short-axis tube orbits. Regular orbits in non-integrable triaxial potentials can typically still be identified with these classes. Tube orbits have a non-zero time-averaged angular momentum about either the long or short axis and therefore never pass through the center of the potential (hence are centrophobic). Box orbits instead have a zero time-averaged angular momentum and therefore have finite probability of passing through the center of the potential. These orbits are generally centrophilic, though some resonant box orbits are also centrophobic (e.g., banana, pretzel, fish).

The frequencies of a generic orbit are typically incommensurable—that is, $\mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega} \neq 0$ for any integer vector, \mathbf{n} , with reasonable magnitude. These non-resonant orbits uniformly cover the surface of an orbital torus. If instead there exists a relation of the form $\mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega} = 0$ the orbit is referred to as a resonant orbit. Resonant orbits are confined to a surface with lower dimensionality than the surface of an orbital torus, depending on the number of resonance

A more precise condition is stated in terms of a diophantine condition, e.g., $|\mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega}| > \alpha |\mathbf{n}|^{-\gamma}$ where $\alpha, \gamma > 0$.

relations obeyed; in a triaxial potential, orbits may obey either zero, one, or two resonance relations. We refer to orbits that obey a single resonance relation as *uni-resonant* orbits, and if an additional resonance relation exists, *bi-resonant*. Uni-resonant orbits in a triaxial potential are confined to a 2D surface, and bi-resonant orbits are closed 1D curves. The resonant structure of a potential—the relative importance of particular resonance integer vectors—is difficult to compute, but determines the global behavior of orbits in the potential. In plots of frequency ratios, the resonances appear as lines; Figure 4.1 (left panel) shows a cartoon portrait of a portion of frequency-space for an integrable potential with example resonance lines, non-resonant, and resonant orbits marked. For an integrable potential, all orbits are regular.

Figure 4.1: An illustrative demonstration of the orbit structure for integrable (left), near-integrable (middle), and non-integrable (right) potentials in terms of the ratios of the fundamental frequencies. In an integrable potential, only resonant and non-resonant orbits exist, and all orbits are regular (resonances appear as lines in frequency-ratio-space). If the potential is perturbed mildly, resonance layers form around the resonances that host near-resonant orbits which behave like resonant orbits but have an additional frequency corresponding to libration about the resonance. Where resonances overlap or near separatrices, stochastic layers form and orbits will be chaotic. For more strongly perturbed potentials, many of the non-resonant orbits may become chaotic but resonance layers may grow and still remain regular.

4.2.2 Orbits in near- and non-integrable potentials

The orbit structure of near-integrable potentials can be understood by considering a Hamiltonian that is a small perturbation away from being globally integrable—that is, a Hamiltonian that may be written

$$H(\mathbf{J}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = H_0(\mathbf{J}) + \epsilon H_1(\mathbf{J}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad (4.7)$$

where $H_0(\mathbf{J})$ represents an integrable Hamiltonian, and ϵ is a small parameter that determines the perturbation strength (a description of perturbation theory applied to nonlinear Hamiltonians is given in Lichtenberg & Leiberman 1983). When $0 < |\epsilon| \ll 1$, resonant surfaces become ‘thick’ resonant layers, within which orbits are qualitatively similar to the parent resonant orbit (e.g., Merritt & Valluri 1999). These resonant layers are then generically surrounded by stochastic layers where chaotic motion occurs (in the vicinity of separatrices). Chaotic orbits are not bound to the surface of a torus and instead fill a $(2N-1)$ -dimensional volume where a continuous set of tori would exist in an unperturbed Hamiltonian, H_0 . While the frequency spectrum of sub-sections of a regular orbit are indistinguishable (i.e. measured over a finite interval of time), the frequency spectra of sub-sections of a chaotic orbit will evolve stochastically.

Figure 4.1 (middle panel) shows a cartoon of frequency space for a near-integrable potential (a small perturbation away from the potential in the left panel) assuming the resonances are stable. Much of the structure that was present in the integrable potential remains in the near-integrable case, but the differences are highlighted. Orbits in the resonant layers surrounding the resonances (grey) are near-resonant orbits that librate around the resonance and have finite thickness (e.g., Merritt & Valluri 1999). Chaotic orbits in the stochastic layer (red) behave erratically depending on the surrounding resonance structure. If the stochastic layer is small and the chaotic orbit is therefore confined, the orbit may behave nearly regular

for long periods of time. If the resonance in the unperturbed Hamiltonian is unstable, all orbits associated with the resonance will be chaotic; unstable resonances form linear gaps in frequency-space (this is not shown in the cartoon but are seen in Figure 4.B.1). Thus, only some resonances in the perturbed system will retain the signature of a resonance.

For small values of ϵ , many regular orbits survive and only small chaotic regions are introduced, especially in the vicinity of the intersection of two resonance lines (commonly referred to as ‘resonance overlap’; see Chirikov 1960). As the strength of the perturbation increases, eventually most tori associated with non-resonant motion will be destroyed. Figure 4.1 (right panel) qualitatively shows this phenomenon—the resonant and resonant-layer orbits may still be regular, but many or all of the non-resonant orbits will be chaotic. As the perturbation strength increases, eventually the uni- and bi-resonant tori are also destroyed—these are less susceptible to destruction from perturbations (for a more quantitative illustration of this transition from integrability to global chaos, see Figure 9 in Valluri & Merritt 1998).

When ϵ is large, there is no general prediction for the resulting behavior, however it seems that more complicated and physically motivated triaxial potential models for galaxies follow the intuition gained from the small-perturbation picture described above, at least for certain parameter choices (e.g., Valluri & Merritt 1998; Merritt & Valluri 1999). We therefore expect a large number of regular orbits will survive—the so-called KolmogorovArnoldMoser (KAM) tori—however the tori that survive will be separated by regions of chaotic motion. Any transformations to angle-action coordinates must be defined local to each resonance region due to the destruction of tori and chaotic motion which lead to discontinuous changes in orbital properties.

4.2.3 The behavior of chaotic orbits in non-integrable potentials

Chaotic orbits have no orbital actions and only conserve energy (if the potential is time-independent). The orbits therefore do not have a single set of fundamental frequencies, but rather the frequencies that describe the character of motion evolve with time. In near-integrable potentials, the frequencies of consecutive sub-sections of a chaotic orbit diffuse both around resonance layers. For weakly chaotic orbits, motion around a resonance layer can occur with a frequency close to the libration frequency of the nearby stable orbits in the resonance layer. Thus, if the resonance libration frequency is small, motion around a resonance can modulate the frequency spectrum of an orbit over an orbital time. However, the stochastic layers are often bounded in the direction orthogonal to the resonance by other stable, resonant regions so that the frequencies or actions can not change by large factors (unless there are other nearby resonances and overlapping stochastic layers, in which case the motion may be strongly chaotic).

The rate of diffusion along stochastic layers via Arnold diffusion depends on the local resonant structure and is hard to predict. This has been done analytically for simple potentials (e.g., Chirikov 1979). For systems with $N > 2$ dof, the stochastic layers connect and form an intricate network of stochasticity known as the Arnold web; an orbit that ergodically mixes over its energy hypersurface must traverse this web, though the timescales typical for this phenomenon are many thousands of orbital periods.

Arnold diffusion is not expected to be significant for most orbits over timescales relevant to galaxies (10s of orbits), however chaotic motion across resonances can occur over short times. If a stochastic trajectory is surrounded by regular orbits, it may be trapped around a

Note that during this diffusion, the frequencies never exactly hit those of a KAM torus but evolve stochastically around these discrete, stable tori (cf. Figure 2 in Laskar 1999). (a sort of stochastic libration) and along the stochastic layers that surround the resonances (Arnold diffusion).

regular parent orbit for long periods of time before escaping to another such semi-bounded region where it can become trapped around another parent orbit (a process by which it may eventually explore the whole Arnold web)—such orbits are commonly referred to as ‘sticky orbits.’ Additionally, if the volume of the surrounded region in frequency space is comparable to the characteristic spread of frequencies in the tidal debris, this small-scale evolution will be important for tidal debris.

4.2.4 Mixing of orbit ensembles

An ensemble of regular orbits (e.g., tidal debris) will phase-mix because of (small) differences in the fundamental frequencies of the orbits. The frequency distributions of thin streams are generally close to one-dimensional—that is, one eigenvalue of the distribution of frequencies for an orbit ensemble will be much larger than the others because of the local shape of the Hessian of the potential (Helmi & White 1999; Sanders & Binney 2013a; Bovy 2014). Phase-mixing generically leads to power-law decay of the mean density of the ensembles: initially, the density decreases linearly in time because of the large, nearly one-dimensional spread in frequencies, then may proceed as t^{-2} to t^{-3} depending on relative sizes of the other eigenvalues of the frequency-space distribution (e.g., Helmi & White 1999; Vogelsberger et al. 2008).

Generically, a small ensemble of chaotic orbits will lose coherence much faster than for regular orbits (see, e.g., Kandrup & Mahon 1994; Merritt & Valluri 1996; Kandrup & Siopis 2003), however this depends on the details of the resonant structure around the ensemble and the chaotic evolution of the individual orbits and is thus difficult to predict. For example, ensembles of orbits ‘stuck’ between resonances may quickly spread to fill the allowed volume, but then the orbits must escape this confinement and diffuse through the Arnold web to reach a fully mixed state (Merritt & Valluri 1996). That is, while the orbit is stuck, the small-scale

variations effectively cause an increase in the variance of the frequency distribution, which would enhance mixing of the debris in configuration-space. In this work, we investigate the consequences of short-time but small-scale frequency evolution and hypothesize that this may explain the enhanced density evolution of tidal debris around weakly chaotic regions where chaotic timescales are predicted to be long (e.g., Pearson et al. 2015). We then discuss how this would affect our understanding of the coherence and density evolution of tidal streams.

4.3 Numerical methods

Our goal is to map the orbit structure of arbitrary (galactic) potentials, with an emphasis on identifying the chaotic orbits and understanding the evolution of these ensembles of orbits over short times. In particular, we aim to understand how this chaos-enhanced density evolution can affect tidal stream morphology. In this section, we describe the methods we will use to detect and quantify the strength of chaos for large grids of orbits.

4.3.1 Potential choice

The density distributions within dark-matter haloes formed in cosmological N -body simulations are generically triaxial (e.g., Jing & Suto 2002; Bett et al. 2007; Zemp et al. 2009; Vera-Ciro et al. 2011). With the inclusion of baryonic physics and sub-grid prescriptions for energy input due to supernovae and other feedback mechanisms, the inner potential ($\lesssim 0.1R_{\text{vir}}$ for a $\approx 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ halo mass) typically becomes more spherical, though the magnitude of this reshaping depends on the particular merger history and star formation efficiency within a given halo and the mass and shape of the baryonic component (e.g., Dubinski 1994; Kazantzidis et al. 2004; Debattista et al. 2008; Bryan et al. 2013; Butsky et al. 2015, though in Milky Way-like galaxies, baryonic disks will add non-sphericity to the total potential). It

is less clear what happens to the outer halo (e.g., Zemp et al. 2011; Valluri et al. 2013).

Jing & Suto (2002, hereafter JS02) found that a triaxial generalization of the NFW density profile (Navarro et al. 1996) generates excellent fits to the density distributions within haloes in their high-resolution (dark-matter-only) N -body simulations, and they provide probability distributions for the axis ratios of a large sample of these haloes. JS02 find median axis ratios of $c/a \approx 0.55$ and $b/a \approx 0.77$ where a is the major axis, b the intermediate, and c the minor axis. These are largely consistent with findings from more recent simulations (e.g., Bett et al. 2007; Vera-Ciro et al. 2011; Butsky et al. 2015; Zhu et al. 2015) and consistent with constraints from weak lensing that place a lower limit on minor-to-major axis ratios of $c/a \gtrsim 0.5$ (van Uitert et al. 2012). JS02 find significant scatter in the distributions of concentration parameter, c_e , or scale radius (depending on choice of parametrization).

All of these parameters are specified in terms of the *density*; for orbit analysis, we need to determine the form of the potential in terms of these parameters, which, in general, requires numerical integration of the density at each position of interest. For computational efficiency, many authors instead express the triaxiality in the form of the potential, but this can lead to unphysical situations where the density becomes negative. Lee & Suto (2003) derive a perturbative expansion of the potential integral for a triaxial NFW density and show that the expansion is accurate even for modest axis ratios (e.g., the median values shown above).

In this work, we use the triaxial potential expression from Lee & Suto (2003), parametrized in a slightly different manner. In terms of spherical coordinates with the radius normalized

Note that JS02 use the opposite notation so that c is the major and a is the minor axis.
(r, ϕ, θ) = (radius, azimuth, colatitude)

Figure 4.2: Equipotential contours (left) and isodensity contours (right) for the triaxial NFW potential considered in this work. For the potential plot there are eight contour levels evenly spaced and linear in the value of the potential. For the density plot there are eight contour levels logarithmically spaced from $10^4 \text{ M}_\odot \text{ kpc}^{-3}$ to $10^7 \text{ M}_\odot \text{ kpc}^{-3}$.

by the scale radius, $u = r/r_s$

$$\Phi(u, \phi, \theta) \approx \frac{v_c^2}{A} \left[F_1(u) + \frac{1}{2}(e_b^2 + e_c^2)F_2(u) + \frac{1}{2}[(e_b \sin \theta \sin \phi)^2 + (e_c \cos \theta)^2]F_3(u) \right] \quad (4.8)$$

$$A = \left(\ln 2 - \frac{1}{2} \right) + \left(\ln 2 - \frac{3}{4} \right) (e_b^2 + e_c^2) \quad (4.9)$$

where $e_b = \sqrt{1 - (b/a)^2}$, $e_c = \sqrt{1 - (c/a)^2}$, and v_c is the circular velocity at the scale radius, r_s , for the spherical case. The functions $F_i(u)$ are given in the appendix of Lee & Suto (2003).

We chose $r_s = 20 \text{ kpc}$ and $v_c = 175 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ by taking the mean halo concentration for a $M_{vir} \approx 10^{12} \text{ M}_\odot$ halo, $c_e \approx 5$, from Jing & Suto (2002) and by assuming $R_{vir} \approx 200 \text{ kpc}$.

Figure 4.2 shows equipotential contours of this potential, and Table 4.1 summarizes the potential parameters.

This potential is a simple (and unrealistic) model for the total potential of a Milky-Way-

Parameter	Value
v_c	175 km s ⁻¹
r_s	20 kpc
a	1
b	0.77
c	0.55
T_{abc}	0.58

Table 4.1: Summary of parameters for the triaxial NFW potential (Equation 4.8) used in this work. Triaxiality is introduced in the density (rather than the potential) to ensure that the density is physical at all radii. Velocity scale, scale radius, and axis ratios are chosen to match the median halo parameters for a $M_{\text{vir}} \approx 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ halo from (Jing & Suto 2002). The triaxiality parameter, $T_{abc} = \frac{a^2 - b^2}{a^2 - c^2}$, is also given.

like galaxy, however it represents a conservative choice for exploring the structure of orbits in the haloes of such galaxies. Realistic galactic potentials will have a significant component due to the disk and bulge, radially changing axis ratios or orientations (e.g., Romanowsky & Kochanek 1998; Kazantzidis et al. 2004; Debattista et al. 2008; Vera-Ciro et al. 2011; Butsky et al. 2015), significant substructure (Moore et al. 1998; Zemp et al. 2009), or time dependence (either from bulk rotation, mass growth, mergers, etc.; see, e.g., Bailin et al. 2005). We expect inclusion of any of these effects to increase the complexity of the resonant structure and influence of chaos (see Section 4.5).

4.3.2 Orbit integration

We use the Dormand-Prince 8th-order Runge-Kutta scheme (Prince & Dormand 1981) to integrate orbits in the above potential. Specifically, we use a `Python` wrapper over the `C` implementation by Hairer et al. (1993). For all orbits we ensure that energy is conserved to $|\Delta E/E_0| \leq 10^{-8}$ by the end of integration, however most orbits conserve energy to a part in $\approx 10^{-13}$. Unless otherwise specified the integration timesteps are chosen so that there are

512 steps per strongest orbital period component, but the integrator uses adaptive stepping between each main step in order to satisfy a specified tolerance (we set the absolute tolerance to ≈ 100 times machine precision, `atol` = 10^{-13}).

4.3.3 Lyapunov exponents

The most well-known method for assessing chaotic motion is to analyze the Lyapunov spectrum or maximum Lyapunov exponent (MLE) of an orbit (Lyapunov 1992). The MLE measures the mean rate of divergence of two infinitesimally separated orbits and is only strictly defined in terms of a limit that goes to infinite time. Thus, we can never truly compute the MLE and it can take integration for many thousands of orbital periods to compute a converged numerical approximation of the MLE for a moderately chaotic orbit. In this work, we use the algorithm introduced by Wolf et al. (1985) for computing the MLE (for more a more detailed description of this algorithm, see Appendix 4.A).

The MLE, λ_{\max} , is interpreted as a rate that quantifies the exponential divergence of infinitesimally close chaotic orbits. It is therefore useful to consider the corresponding e -folding time by inverting the rate,

$$t_\lambda = \frac{1}{\lambda_{\max}}. \quad (4.10)$$

We will use this as the prediction from the Lyapunov exponent for the timescale over which chaos should be dynamically important for a given orbit.

4.3.4 Frequency diffusion rate

Bounded, regular orbits in a triaxial potential have three fundamental frequencies, $\mathbf{\Omega}$, that determine the periodic behavior of motion. The motion in any canonical coordinate can therefore be decomposed as a Fourier sum (Equation 4.4) where the Fourier frequencies are

linear, integer combinations of the fundamental frequencies (Equation 4.5). Laskar (1993) introduced a method for recovering the fundamental frequencies of an orbit that effectively uses fast-Fourier transforms (FFTs) of complex combinations of the motion (e.g., $x(t) + iv_x(t)$) to identify the frequencies. This method is referred to as ‘Numerical Approximation of Fundamental Frequencies’ (NAFF) and has been used extensively in planetary dynamics (e.g., Laskar & Robutel 1993; Laskar 1996) and galaxy dynamics (Papaphilippou & Laskar 1998; Valluri & Merritt 1998), especially in the study of orbits in triaxial systems. We have implemented and tested a version of this procedure in the *Python* programming language. Our implementation differs slightly from the original definition and from that used in Valluri & Merritt (1998); we refer to this slight modification of the algorithm as **SuperFreq** (Price-Whelan 2015) and the code is open-source and publicly available on *GitHub*. For more details about the algorithm and differences with previous work, see Laskar (1988, 1993); Papaphilippou & Laskar (1996) and Appendix 4.B.

If an orbit is chaotic, the motion can no longer be expanded in terms of a single set of fundamental frequencies. For a weakly chaotic orbit, the orbit may appear consistently periodic over long windows of time. **SuperFreq** will pick out a set of frequencies for chaotic orbits that correspond to the largest peaks in the power spectrum of the orbits, however these peaks will change location and amplitude with time. For more strongly chaotic orbits, the power spectrum will be quite noisy and the peak frequencies may change erratically when comparing two consecutive sections of orbit. The frequencies picked out by **SuperFreq** for such orbits will therefore represent the average periodic nature of the orbit over a given integration window. Following previous work, we define the fractional frequency diffusion

<https://github.com/adrn/SuperFreq>

rate, \mathcal{R} , in the k th fundamental frequency as

$$\mathcal{R}_k = \frac{\Omega_k^{(2)} - \Omega_k^{(1)}}{\Omega_k^{(1)} \Delta t} \quad (4.11)$$

where the upper index refers to the two consecutive sections of orbit and Δt is the length of each integration window (Laskar 1993; Valluri & Merritt 1998; Valluri et al. 2012). By inverting this rate, we can compute the timescale over which we expect order-unity changes to the fundamental frequencies: the *frequency diffusion time* is defined as

$$t_\Omega = (\max_{a_k} \mathcal{R}_k)^{-1} \quad (4.12)$$

where the maximum is taken with respect to the corresponding amplitudes, a_k , of the fundamental frequency components (see Valluri et al. 2012).

For a small ensemble of orbits (e.g., tidal debris), a more relevant timescale is the time over which the change in frequencies for a single orbit is comparable to the spread of frequencies in the ensemble. We can estimate this timescale by multiplying the frequency diffusion time by a factor equal to the fractional spread in frequencies of the debris. For example, a globular cluster typically has $\approx 0.1\%$ spreads in fundamental frequencies, so by multiplying the frequency diffusion time by $f = 10^{-3}$, we can estimate the time (in number of orbital periods) over which we expect the frequencies to evolve by this amount.

4.4 Results

In Section 4.4.1, we generate grids of orbits in the potential described above to map the orbital structure of the potential. We classify each orbit in terms of the strength of chaos along the orbit as computed using the Lyapunov and frequency diffusion times of Section 4.3.

With this initial classification, in Section 4.4.2 we follow the evolution of ensembles of trajectories generated around each orbit in the initial grid. We find that the configuration-space density of ensembles around weakly chaotic orbits evolve faster (e.g., in mean density) than expected given the timescales over which chaos is computed to be relevant for the parent orbits. In Section 4.4.3, we explain this phenomenon in the context of how chaotic diffusion occurs (e.g., Section 4.2.3).

4.4.1 Part I: Lyapunov and frequency diffusion times

We generate an isoenergy grid of initial conditions along the xz ($y = 0$) plane with energy (per unit mass), E , chosen to span a range of distances comparable to the scale radius of the potential ($E = -(397.2 \text{ km s}^{-1})^2$ in physical units; see Table 4.1). We fix $v_x = v_z = 0$, and compute v_y from the energy. This grid generates all of the major orbit classes (short-axis tubes, inner long-axis tubes, outer long-axis tubes, stochastic intermediate-axis, and box orbits). The most numerous orbits in this grid are the short-axis and long-axis tubes that circulate about either the minor or major axis. Thin tidal streams may preferentially form along tube orbits rather than box orbits because of the faster disruption and debris diffusion expected for stellar systems on radially plunging orbits. Figure 4.3 shows the grid of initial conditions in the xz plane—each pixel in this grid represents an orbit, and the pixels are colored by the median pericentric distance (left) and median apocentric distance (right) over an integration time of 64 orbital periods. From here onwards, all lengths are given in units of scale radii, r_s , velocities in units of circular velocity, v_c , (see Table 4.1) and times in units of orbital periods, T .

We integrate all orbits in the grid for 10000 orbital periods and use the method described in Section 4.3.3 to compute the MLEs. Figure 4.4 again shows the grid of initial conditions,

x is the major and z the minor axis.

Figure 4.3: A grid of isoenergy orbits initialized on the xz plane. All distances are normalized by the potential scale radius. Each pixel in these panels represents a single orbit, and the shading of each pixel corresponds to the median pericentric distance (left) or median apocentric distance (right) computed over 64 orbital periods. The central black band in the left panel and white band in the right panel are tube orbits with apocenter-to-pericenter ratios close to one. The four arrows are explained in Section 4.4.2 and the caption of Figure 4.4.

but now the color corresponds to the logarithm of the inverse of the MLE (the Lyapunov time). The darker pixels have shorter Lyapunov times and are more chaotic. Because of the fixed the integration time, the MLE cannot detect weak chaos and the majority of orbits appear to be regular because they have exceedingly long Lyapunov times (all white points have $(t_\lambda/T) \gtrsim 1000$).

For each orbit, we also separately integrate for 256 orbital periods and use **SuperFreq** to compute the fundamental frequencies for the two consecutive sections of 128 orbital periods. We have chosen this window size so that we recover the frequencies for regular orbits with fractional error $\approx 10^{-8}$ (we estimate the error in frequency recovery using the method de-

Figure 4.4: The same grid of orbits as shown in Figure 4.3, but now each pixel is colored by the logarithm of the Lyapunov time (in units of orbital periods). Orbits are integrated for a total of 10000 orbital periods. Chaotic orbits with $t_\lambda/T \gtrsim 700$ appear regular because the integration time for each orbit is insufficient to resolve weak chaos. Four orbits are pointed out with arrows—from top to bottom, these are the strongly chaotic (D), near-resonant (A), weakly chaotic (C), and non-resonant (B) orbits of Table 4.2 (see Section 4.4.2).

scribed in Laskar 1993). With this integration window we are able to successfully recover frequencies for >99.9% of the orbits **SuperFreq**. Figure 4.5 shows the same grid of initial conditions as in Figure 4.4, but now the greyscale intensity is set by the logarithm of the frequency diffusion time. The darker pixels have shorter frequency diffusion times and are more chaotic. This map reveals the intersection of this particular energy hypersurface with the rich structure of resonant surfaces present in this potential and highlights the accuracy of **SuperFreq**—weak chaos (grey) is detectable over much shorter integration periods using frequency analysis, compared to the many tens of thousands of orbits it would take to detect such features with the maximum Lyapunov exponent. The tube orbits in this potential are mostly regular or only mildly chaotic—the largest regular regions are associated with the short-axis and long-axis tube orbits—however islands of stronger chaos do appear, especially at the intersections of resonances where resonance overlap occurs.

The strongest chaotic regions (black) appear in both of the above grids (Figure 4.4 and Figure 4.5). Some of the weakly chaotic unstable resonances do appear in the Lyapunov time map—for example, near $(x_0, z_0)/r_s \approx (1.5, 0.6)$ and $(x_0, z_0)/r_s \approx (0.6, 0.4)$ where there is a slight hint of weak chaos (grey) in Figure 4.4. The details of the resonant structure is revealed in the frequency diffusion map from integrations of just 256 orbital periods. While there is rich structure and a significant number of weakly chaotic orbits, the majority of the orbits have estimated chaotic timescales corresponding to thousands of orbital periods and are thus not expected to be relevant for tidal stream evolution. In the next section, we analyze the density evolution of finite-volume ensembles of orbits around each orbit in the above grids in order to compare the effect of ordinary phase-mixing of tidal debris with potentially enhanced mixing due to chaos. We then compare the density evolution of the ensembles to the single-orbit chaos indicators computed in this section.

Figure 4.5: The same grid of orbits as shown in Figure 4.3, but now each pixel is colored by the logarithm of the frequency diffusion time (again in units of orbital periods). The frequencies are computed in two consecutive windows, each of which has length equal to 40 orbital periods. The frequencies are measured precisely so that small changes in the frequencies can be detected over just ≈ 10 s of orbits. Four orbits are pointed out with arrows—from top to bottom, these are the strongly chaotic (D), near-resonant (A), weakly chaotic (C), and non-resonant (B) orbits of Table 4.2 (see Section 4.4.2).

4.4.2 Part II: Ensemble properties and mixing

The Lyapunov and frequency diffusion times measure the timescales over which chaos is relevant for a given orbit—that is, these quantities are measures of how infinitesimal deviations will diverge on average from some parent orbit, or of how long it takes for the frequencies of a single orbit to change by some amount. Tidal debris is disrupted from progenitor systems with finite spreads in orbital properties (e.g., energy). For a disrupting, globular-cluster-scale progenitor, the typical energy or frequency-space dispersion of the debris is 0.1–1% of the progenitor orbital energy (assuming masses of 10^4 – $10^6 M_\odot$; Johnston 1998), but for a dwarf-galaxy-scale progenitor, the dispersion can be $\sim 10\%$. In this section, we ask whether the Lyapunov or frequency diffusion time predict the timescale over which a finite phase-space volume (e.g., tidal debris) stays coherent.

It is computationally intractable to run full N -body simulations for the large grid of orbital initial conditions of the previous section and we therefore take a simplified approach for studying how finite-volume debris spreads along each of these orbits. We instead consider small ensembles of particles meant to represent debris disrupted from a single tidal disruption event. For a given set of orbital initial conditions—the ‘parent’ orbit—we integrate for 128 orbital periods, find the phase-space position of the minimum pericenter over this time, initialize a small ensemble of test particle orbits around this position, and integrate the orbits of all test particles for some integration time. We are interested in the degree to which chaos enhances the mixing rate of orbit ensembles and we therefore want to isolate out the effect of ordinary phase-mixing along regular orbits. We set the physical scale of the ensemble by the tidal radius in position and the velocity scale in velocity; the initial spread in fundamental frequencies will scale as $(m/M)^{1/3}$ like the tidal radius and velocity scale (e.g., Johnston 1998; Price-Whelan et al. 2014). If $(\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{v}_0)$ are a set of initial conditions at

pericenter for a parent orbit, then $\delta x_{k,i}$ and $\delta v_{k,i}$ are the k th components ($k = 1, 2, 3$) of the position and velocity deviation vectors for the i th particle and the magnitude of the offsets are assumed to be Normally distributed away from the parent orbit:

$$\delta x_{k,i} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, r_{\text{tide}}/\sqrt{3}) \quad (4.13)$$

$$\delta v_{k,i} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_v/\sqrt{3}) \quad (4.14)$$

$$r_{\text{tide}} = \|\mathbf{x}_0\| \left(\frac{m}{M(< \|\mathbf{x}_0\|)} \right)^{1/3} \quad (4.15)$$

$$\sigma_v = \|\mathbf{v}_0\| \left(\frac{m}{M(< \|\mathbf{x}_0\|)} \right)^{1/3} \quad (4.16)$$

where $M(< r)$ is the mass enclosed of the host potential within radius r , m is the mass scale of the ‘progenitor,’ and $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm. We take $m = 10^4 M_\odot$ to represent globular-cluster-like progenitors, and use the spherically-averaged enclosed mass of the host potential to estimate the above debris scales.

We start by considering four particular orbits chosen from the orbit grid of Section 4.4.1: a regular, near-resonant orbit (A), a regular, non-resonant orbit (B), a weakly chaotic orbit (C), and a more strongly chaotic orbit (D). The orbits were chosen to be close on the orbit grid so that their orbital properties (e.g., apocenter, pericenter) are similar, but have different frequency diffusion times; all four orbits are long-axis tube orbits. Figure 4.6 shows the orbits in projection over an integration period of 1024 orbital periods. The initial conditions and chaos diagnostics for each orbit are listed in Table 4.2. Figure 4.7 shows final positions of test-particle ensembles initialized around the four orbits described above and integrated for 64 orbital periods. A thin stream forms on the near-resonant orbit (left column), a thin—but more two-dimensional—stream forms on the non-resonant orbit (middle-left), a more diffuse stream forms on the weakly chaotic orbit with a slightly ‘fanned’ morphology (middle-right),

and a two-dimensional, ‘fanned’ stream on the more strongly chaotic orbit (right). Given the long Lyapunov and frequency diffusion times of the weakly chaotic orbit ($t_\lambda/T > 900$, $t_\Omega/T \approx 2 \times 10^5$), it is surprising that the density evolution of the ensemble on this orbit appears to be more diffuse than the regular orbit stream.

Figure 4.6: Four representative orbits chosen from the orbit grid (e.g., Figure 4.3): a regular, near-resonant orbit (A), a regular, non-resonant orbit (B), a weakly chaotic orbit (C), and a more strongly chaotic orbit (D). All orbits are long-axis tubes with similar pericenters and apocenters. Orbits in this Figure were integrated for 1024 orbital periods and are shown in projection.

We verify that these orbit ensembles capture the nature of more realistic stream formation by running N -body simulations of globular-cluster-mass progenitor systems on these same four orbits. We use the Self-Consistent Field (SCF) basis function expansion code (Hernquist & Ostriker 1992) to run the simulations, which we set up to run from apocenter-to-apocenter (rather than pericenter-to-apocenter as in the ensembles), but finish with the progenitor in the same location as the parent orbit in the ensemble evolution described above. Figure 4.8

Orbit ensembles

Figure 4.7: Final particle positions after integrating unbound, globular-cluster-sized ensembles of orbits generated around each of the three N -body orbits (Figure 4.8). The ensembles each contain 1024 particles and are initialized at pericenter. The particle positions qualitatively match the morphology of the ‘oldest’ debris from the corresponding N -body simulations (Figure 4.8).

shows the final particle distributions rotated so that the angular momentum of the progenitor orbit is aligned with the z -axis. From a comparison of Figures 4.7 and 4.8, it is clear that the morphology of the ensembles is visually similar to the ‘oldest’ (first stripped) debris in the N -body simulations.

Visual inspection of Figures 4.7 and 4.8 suggests that chaotic mixing of small orbit ensembles affects the configuration-space evolution of an ensemble over short times, even when the predicted chaotic timescales (from the Lyapunov and frequency diffusion times) are long: The mean, single-orbit chaos indicators are not well-suited for determining the importance of chaotic diffusion on tidal stream evolution. As a quantitative measure of

N -body simulations

Figure 4.8: We use the Self-Consistent Field (SCF) basis function expansion code (Hernquist & Ostriker 1992) to run N -body simulations of globular-cluster-mass progenitor systems on the three orbits of Figure 4.7. The progenitor in each simulation is initialized as a 10^4 particle Plummer sphere and the background triaxial NFW potential is turned on slowly over 250 Myr to reduce artificial gravitational shocking. We start the progenitor systems at apocenter and integrate for ≈ 64 orbital periods so that each simulation finishes again at subsequent apocenter. The mass of the progenitor is set to $10^4 M_\odot$, and the length-scale of the Plummer sphere is set to 5 pc to get ≈ 50 – 75% mass loss over the integration time. Panels show particle positions from the final snapshots of the simulations—for visualization the positions have been rotated so that the angular momentum of the progenitor at the final snapshot are aligned with the z -axis. These simulations confirm that the test-particle orbit ensembles (Figure 4.7) do (qualitatively) capture the nature of the early-stripped tidal debris.

ID	x/r_s	y/r_s	z/r_s	v_x/v_c	v_y/v_c	v_z/v_c	t_λ/T	t_Ω/T
A	0.85	0	1.303	0	0.721	0	> 700	$> 10^7$
B	0.85	0	1.152	0	0.849	0	> 700	$> 10^7$
C	0.85	0	1.27	0	0.752	0	> 700	$\approx 3 \times 10^5$
D	0.85	0	1.434	0	0.597	0	8.14	$\approx 2.5 \times 10^4$

Table 4.2: Orbital initial conditions from the xz grid for orbits with a range of chaotic timescales—A is a regular, near-resonant orbit, B a regular, non-resonant orbit, C a weakly chaotic orbit, and D a strongly chaotic orbit. Positions (x, y, z) are given in units of scale radii, r_s , and velocities (v_x, v_y, v_z) in units of scale velocity, v_c . Chaotic timescales are expressed (t_λ, t_Ω) in number of orbital periods. Recall that the frequency diffusion time, t_Ω , is the time over which we expect order-unity changes in the fundamental frequencies, hence why the timescales appear quite long.

this enhanced density evolution, we compute the evolution of the mean configuration-space density for orbit ensembles evolved around the four parent orbits (A,B,C,D) described above. At each time step, we use kernel density estimation (KDE) with the ensemble of particle positions to estimate the configuration-space density field. We use an Epanechnikov kernel with an adaptive bandwidth: at each evaluation of the density, we use 10-fold cross-validation to find the optimal kernel bandwidth. We evaluate the density at the positions of each particle, ρ_i , and compare to the mean initial density, $\langle \rho_0 \rangle$.

Figure 4.9 shows the mean density of the ensemble particles computed at 256 evenly-spaced intervals from the initial ensemble distribution to the distribution after 64 orbital periods. Over-laid on each panel are qualitative power-laws (i.e. not fit to the density evolution) that demonstrate the expected trends: After initial t^{-1} decay, the mean density of the near-resonant orbit (A) should follow t^{-2} , whereas the non-resonant orbit (B) will transition from t^{-2} to t^{-3} after long times (and thus currently display an intermediate power-law index). Given the extremely long chaotic timescale for the weakly chaotic orbit (C), we

We use an implementation from the Python package `scikit-learn` (Pedregosa et al. 2011).

would expect the mean density to follow a simple power-law over long times, however at ≈ 16 orbital periods the density clearly diverges and begins to follow a decaying exponential. The mean density along the strongly chaotic orbit (D) evolves stochastically but generally follows a decaying exponential.

Motivated by the noticeable discrepancy between the final mean density between the two regular (A,B) and the weakly chaotic (C) orbit ensembles—even though the chaotic timescale of the weakly chaotic ensemble parent orbit is several times the integration period used above—we compute the final mean density for orbit ensembles generated around each orbit in the grid described in Section 4.4.1. For all ensembles, we integrate the orbits for 64 (parent) orbital periods and compute the initial and final values of the mean, configuration-space density. Figure 4.10 again shows the grid of initial conditions (Section 4.4.1, but now the greyscale indicates the ratio of the final mean density to the initial density. Interestingly, much of the structure that is visible in the upper-half of the frequency diffusion time map (Figure 4.5) is again visible in this map of the density evolution of orbit ensembles. Many features appear as lighter, curved features in the upper portion of this grid where the density remains systematically higher—these are the stable resonances of the potential. Darker regions have systematically lower densities and correspond to regions of resonance overlap where weakly chaotic orbits are found.

However, it is surprising that these features are present: The chaotic timescales predicted from both the Lyapunov and frequency diffusion times were typically 100 to 1000s of orbital periods for many of the unstable features around resonances. The timescales in the lower portion of the grid (where the orbits are primarily stable, short-axis tube orbits) are simply too long to detect density differences over 64 orbital periods even from weak chaos in this particular choice of potential.

It is worth noting that the frequency diffusion time map predicts that the resonances are

Figure 4.9: Evolution of the mean density (normalized by the initial density) of orbit ensembles around the four orbits (Figure 4.6) over 64 orbital periods. Over-plotted are various power-laws that qualitatively show the decay of the mean density for the ensembles: the mean density of the near-resonant orbit (A) follows nearly t^{-2} ; the non-resonant orbit (B) is slowly transitioning from t^{-2} to t^{-3} ; the weakly chaotic orbit (C) initially follows t^{-2} but then exponential decay takes over; the strongly chaotic orbit (D) is roughly exponential with fairly erratic density evolution.

surrounded by thick stochastic layers, while in the density map the resonance layers appear to be stable (and thus lead to higher mean densities). This comes from a failure of frequency determination: Near resonances it can take extremely long integration periods to ensure accurate recovery of the frequencies due to aliasing (Laskar 2003). However, at the edges of the resonance layers—where we expect to find stochastic layers and do see weakly chaotic motion—the frequency diffusion time is a robust indicator of chaos.

We conclude from these experiments that the degree of chaos is an indicator that ensembles of orbits may mix faster than predicted from regular phase-mixing, however the Lyapunov time and frequency diffusion time are not good predictors for the timescale over which this mixing will occur. To understand this discrepancy, we next explore why this occurs (Section 4.4.3, in the context of Section 4.2.4).

Figure 4.10: The same grid of orbits as shown in Figure 4.3, but now the greyscale intensity is set by the mean density of a of small ensembles of orbits after integration for 64 orbital periods. The orbit ensembles are generated around each parent orbit in the grid (Section 4.4.2) and the mean density is a kernel density estimation (KDE) with an adaptive Epanechnikov kernel. Given the extremely long chaotic timescales of the weakly chaotic orbits in the upper half of the grid, it is surprising that any of the high-order resonant structure is visible in this map. Four orbits are pointed out with arrows—from top to bottom, these are the strongly chaotic (D), near-resonant (A), weakly chaotic (C), and non-resonant (B) orbits of Table 4.2 (see Section 4.4.2).

4.4.3 Part III: Short-time frequency evolution

Why does chaos manifest itself after just 64 orbital periods around orbits with predicted chaotic timescales larger than thousands of orbital periods? Both the Lyapunov exponent and the frequency diffusion rate measure mean, long-term rates of chaotic diffusion. If a weakly chaotic orbit is confined (by other nearby, non-overlapping resonances or stable regions), the mean drift of an orbit in frequency space may be small if computed over timescales long compared to the orbital time but short compared to the Arnold diffusion time, however small-scale variation of the frequencies may occur over much shorter timescales.

As a demonstration of the small-scale frequency modulation, we consider again the four orbits of Section 4.4.2 (initial conditions are listed in Table 4.2). To resolve the short-time behavior of the frequency diffusion (corresponding to motion across or around resonance layers) we compute the frequencies in a series of rolling windows along each orbit. We use a window with a width equal to 64 orbital periods and shift the window by an orbital period between each calculation of the most significant frequencies. Figure 4.11 shows plots of the frequencies of each orbit computed in each window of time—plotted in projection are the percent deviations of the frequency from the initial value. The difference between the first window (blue +) and the last window (red x) is 128 orbital periods. For the two regular orbits, (A) and (B), the frequencies vary only from numerical issues when recovering the frequencies ($\ll 1\%$) and thus the initial and final value markers overlap. The frequencies of the weakly chaotic orbit (C) evolve quickly but are bounded to a small volume with fractional size $\approx 1\%$ (presumably by nearby resonant surfaces); this is larger than the frequency spread in globular cluster tidal debris (0.1–0.5%). The frequencies of the strongly chaotic orbit (D) also evolve quickly but fill a larger volume.

We see now where the discrepancy between chaotic timescales and the observable effects

of chaos arise in tidal debris: even if the large-scale diffusion of frequencies is slow, an orbit may explore a region of frequency space over much shorter times. The frequency diffusion time (Equation 4.12) is an estimate of the time over which the mean value of the frequencies evolves, however the *variance* of the frequencies over short times is dynamically relevant for small ensembles. This small-scale variability is insignificant for the evolution of global structure in, for example, an elliptical galaxy or in erasing substructure in the Solar neighborhood (e.g., Maffione et al. 2015), but is significant for the morphological evolution of tidal debris with small spreads in frequencies.

We therefore expect a small ensemble of orbits in frequency space to expand over short times around even weakly chaotic parent orbits and the debris should therefore appear dynamically hotter in real-space. The effect is especially significant if the chaotic evolution of the frequencies occurs orthogonal to the largest eigenvector of the distribution of frequencies or the local Hessian of the Hamiltonian. We illustrate this phenomenon by computing the frequencies for each orbit in small ensembles of orbits around each of the four orbits (A,B,C,D).

We generate orbit ensembles with 128 orbits around the four orbits and integrate for two consecutive windows of 128 orbital periods. Figures 4.12 and 4.13 show the distribution of frequencies for all orbits in the ensembles for the four orbits in each of the two consecutive windows. Around the near-resonant orbit (A), the frequency distribution is nearly one-dimensional, which explains the thin, one-dimensional morphology of the ensemble in the left column of Figure 4.7. The non-resonant orbit ensemble (B) is ‘thicker’—the ratio of the two largest eigenvalues of this distribution is larger—and therefore in real space, the ensemble begins to spread over two dimensions, as is also evident in the final ensemble debris morphology in the middle-left panel of Figure 4.7. Non-resonant orbits in axisymmetric or triaxial potentials will generically have frequency distributions that have more comparable

spreads in each direction and the configuration-space density of typical tidal debris will therefore decrease faster in such potentials (Helmi & White 1999). The weakly chaotic orbit ensemble (C) is clearly more diffuse than the two regular ensembles: As is evident in Figure 4.11, the small-scale chaotic evolution of the frequencies—though bounded—increases the variance of the frequency distribution. By comparing Figure 4.12 and 4.13, it appears that the frequency distribution gets more diffuse until it uniformly fills the allowed volume. The strongly chaotic orbit ensemble (D) already has a large spread in Figure 4.12, and in Figure 4.13 many of the frequencies have fractional frequency differences relative to the parent orbit $\approx 5\text{--}10\%$ (off of the plot).

4.5 Discussion: limitations and future work

We have shown that the Lyapunov and frequency diffusion times are indicators of chaos and that the frequency diffusion time resolves the detailed resonant structure of gravitational potentials, but the timescales predicted do not capture the importance of chaos for the density evolution of ensembles of orbits meant to mimic tidal debris. We have shown that small-scale but fast chaotic diffusion of frequencies can explain this enhanced mixing. In the sub-sections below, we discuss a few important limitations that remain for exploration in future work.

4.5.1 The progenitor mass scale

We have only considered low-mass progenitor systems such as globular clusters because the intrinsic spreads in fundamental frequencies are small (0.1–0.5%). Small changes to the frequencies of the orbits of tidal debris stripped from these progenitors due to chaotic processes will therefore cause observable changes to the real-space morphology of the debris.

Figure 4.11: Evolution of the fundamental frequencies computed over a total of 256 orbital periods for the four orbits, A, B, C, D. Plotted are the per cent deviations of the frequencies computed in window relative to the value in the initial window—that is, if j is the index of a given time window, $\delta\Omega_{1,j} = (\Omega_{1,j} - \Omega_{1,0})/\Omega_{1,0}$. The initial value is shown as a blue plus sign and the final value is shown as a red x. The frequencies are computed with a window width of ≈ 128 orbital periods, and the window is shifted by one orbital period between each computation (each grey point represents the fundamental frequencies computed in a single window). For the regular orbits (A,B), the fractional variation is around 10^{-6} and thus all points overlap on this scale. The weakly chaotic orbit (C) displays frequency variations comparable to the spread in frequencies in globular-cluster-like tidal debris. The frequency variations of the strongly chaotic orbit (D) have a larger characteristic spread.

Figure 4.12: Distributions of the fundamental frequencies for all orbits in 128-orbit ensembles generated around the four orbits, A, B, C, D. Plotted are the per cent deviations of the frequencies of each ensemble orbit relative to the frequencies of the parent orbit—that is, if i is the index of a given orbit and $i = 0$ is the parent orbit, $\delta\Omega_{1,i} = (\Omega_{1,i} - \Omega_{1,0})/\Omega_{1,0}$. All orbits are integrated for 128 orbital periods to compute the frequencies. The near-resonant ensemble frequency distribution (A) is nearly 1D, and thus the ensemble appears one-dimensional in configuration-space (Figure 4.7). The two largest eigenvalues of the non-resonant ensemble frequency distribution (B) are closer, and thus the ensemble spreads quicker, leading to a two-dimensional spread of debris in configuration-space. Around both the weakly chaotic orbit (C) and strongly chaotic orbit (D), chaotic diffusion increases the spread of the debris significantly, leading to faster 3D spreading in configuration-space.

Figure 4.13: Same as Figure 4.12 but after integrating the same orbits for another 128 orbital periods. The ensemble frequency distributions around the regular orbits (A,B) appear nearly identical, whereas both the weakly and strongly chaotic ensemble frequency distributions spread significantly.

For more massive progenitor systems, the typical size and velocity dispersion of the debris will be larger and thus the debris morphology will be less sensitive to small changes in orbital properties. The mass-scale of the debris that will display enhanced density evolution depends on the magnitude of weak chaos, which depends on the orbit structure of a given potential. In potentials with more significant chaos, debris disrupted from more massive progenitor systems may also display ‘stream-fanning.’ However, since the scale of the debris is larger it is more likely that some orbits will exist in chaotic regions.

4.5.2 Potential choice

The potential considered in this work is ‘unrealistic’ for the total potential of a Milky-Way-like galaxy in that it is static, smooth, and does not contain baryonic components. Simulations of forming galactic disks in cosmological dark-matter haloes have shown that baryonic feedback and relaxation can significantly change the inner distribution of dark matter and either make the potential more spherical or oblate (Dubinski 1994; Kazantzidis et al. 2004; Bryan et al. 2013; Butsky et al. 2015). However, the significance of baryonic relaxation or of time-dependence, triaxiality, and substructure on shaping the matter distribution within the Milky Way is largely unknown. Here we briefly summarize future directions for potential models:

- *Baryonic components:* (Debattista et al. 2008, D08) and (Valluri et al. 2010, V10) studied the orbit evolution induced by growing a baryonic disk in dark-matter haloes with various shapes and orientations (e.g., prolate, triaxial). In general, the authors find that the growth of a disk slowly deforms the orbits of mass tracers (e.g., dark matter particles) and preferentially populates tube or other ‘round’ orbits (i.e. even the chaotic and box orbits fill a fairly spherical or oblate volume). Consequently, the inner shape of the potential becomes more oblate or spherical. If the inner haloes of

galaxies are indeed close to spherical or oblate, the majority of orbits will be regular and chaos will be less important, however this is far from conclusive. We have found from simple experiments in superposing potential components that transition regions between potential shapes can significantly enhance the amount of chaos. Though superposing potentials is not realistic, it at least suggests that a more careful exploration of potential configurations is required to understand how complex, radius-dependent potential forms affect the amount and significance of chaos in galactic haloes.

- *Time dependence:* Galaxies are certainly not static systems. To first order, galaxies grow in mass—for example, the spherically averaged mass profile of dark-matter haloes evolves fairly predictably in cosmological simulations (Wechsler et al. 2002; Buist & Helmi 2014) after some initial period of stochastic mass growth. The Milky Way has probably had a fairly calm accretion history over the last 6 Gyr and therefore the mass growth may be similar to that seen in simulations. This steady growth most likely does not alter the global structure or shape of the potential. However, we also know from simulations that figure rotation, baryonic feedback, and the accretion and phase-mixing of subhaloes do perturb the global state of simulated haloes. Deibel et al. (2011) showed that by adopting pattern speeds comparable to those found in cosmological simulations, figure rotation generally acts to destabilize orbits (rather than stabilize chaotic orbits in the equivalent static potential) and the resulting orbit structure is that most regular orbits are associated with resonances. The presence of and response to the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds may also introduce significant (time-dependent) perturbations to the global potential of the Milky Way (e.g., Besla et al. 2010; Gómez et al. 2015). In future work we will explore the effect of these time-dependent processes on the chaotic dispersal of tidal streams using live potentials from cosmological N -body simulations.

- *Substructure*: Cosmological simulations predict that dark-matter haloes are filled with substructure in the form of dark matter subhaloes. If they exist, these subhaloes may account for up to $\approx 1\text{-}10\%$ of the mass of the dark matter (e.g., Diemand et al. 2007) and therefore may contribute significantly to and orbit in the large-scale potential of any galaxy. Gravitational scattering due to subhalo interactions has been studied, however in the haloes of galaxies where dynamical times are long, the scattering cross-section for *strong* encounters is small. Instead, the collective effect of the subhaloes may instead act as a noise term in the Hamiltonian of any halo orbit. This subhalo-induced heating—which depends on the mass spectrum and distribution of subhaloes—may also act to simply increase the magnitude of chaos along orbits, and destabilize sufficiently non-resonant orbits (see, e.g., Kandrup et al. 2000; Siegal-Gaskins & Valluri 2008).

4.5.3 Stream modeling

Tidal stream modeling is one of the most promising ways to constrain the 3D mass distribution around the Milky Way at distances of 10s to 100s of kpc. Methods that use tidal streams to infer properties of the Galactic potential typically operate by constructing models of the debris distribution using either the present-day phase-space density (e.g., Varghese et al. 2011; Küpper et al. 2012, 2015; Gibbons et al. 2014), time-of-disruption phase-space density (Price-Whelan & Johnston 2013; Price-Whelan et al. 2014), or the density in angle-action coordinates (Sanders 2014; Bovy 2014). All of these methods may fail or produce uninterpretable results if modeling globular-cluster streams on mildly chaotic orbits. For each of these methods, it is important to understand the failures and biases introduced by ignoring chaotic orbit evolution.

4.5.4 Ophiuchus stream

The Ophiuchus stream (Bernard et al. 2014; Sesar et al. 2015) appears to be a thin, short tidal stream (deprojected length $\approx 1.5\text{--}2$ kpc) near the Galactic bulge with no apparent progenitor. At Galactocentric $R \approx 1$ kpc, $z \approx 5$ kpc, the orbits of the stream stars likely pass through the MW disk, feel the triaxiality of the Galactic bar (e.g., Wegg & Gerhard 2013; Wegg et al. 2015), and have short orbital periods (relative to streams in the halo). It is possible that the observed debris is the last remnants of the recently disrupted progenitor system (Sesar et al. 2015), however if a significant number of stars were stripped on previous pericentric passages, this older debris may be ‘fanned’ and still near the observed portion of the stream. The fanned debris would have significantly lower surface brightness and thus would be more difficult to detect. The detection of this low-surface-brightness component would open up the possibility that enhanced density evolution due to chaos is a dynamically relevant process for thin streams in real galaxies, though Carlberg (2015) has shown that it is also possible to get short, high density segments of streams from debris formed on eccentric orbits.

4.6 Summary and Conclusions

We have considered here a simple triaxial gravitational potential chosen to mimic the median properties of dark-matter haloes formed in dark-matter-only simulations (or the large-scale properties of haloes formed in simulations with baryonic effects). We have numerically computed the magnitude of chaos for a large grid of iso-energy orbits in this potential using two independent methods that have been used extensively to classify and characterize chaotic orbits: 1) the Lyapunov exponent and 2) the frequency diffusion rate. From each of these indicators, we compute a timescale over which chaos is likely to be important and find that

the majority of orbits have chaotic timescales greater than 100s of orbital periods, however with the frequency diffusion rate we are still able to resolve weak chaos. We then study the density evolution of small ensembles of orbits generated around each orbit in the grid used for the previous experiment and find that along some orbits classified as weakly chaotic—with chaotic timescales of 100s of orbital periods—the orbit ensembles display enhanced density evolution and reach a lower overall density faster than orbit ensembles around nearby regular orbits (which mix due to phase-mixing alone). We explain this discrepancy between the predicted chaotic timescale and the observed effects of chaos on tidal debris by considering the nature of chaotic diffusion: the classical chaos indicators are most sensitive to the slow, Arnold diffusion process that can cause large changes to orbital properties, but small-scale frequency evolution occurs over much shorter times as chaotic orbits stochastically diffuse across the stochastic layers that surround many resonances. The fundamental frequencies of a weakly chaotic orbit therefore vary over a small region (bounded by nearby stable resonances), and when this amplitude is comparable to or larger than the typical spread in frequencies of tidal debris from the progenitor, the phase-space density of the debris will evolve faster to a state of lower density relative to nearby regular orbits.

Our main results and conclusions are summarized as follows:

1. “stream-fanning” of tidal streams on weakly chaotic orbits (as seen in simulations by Pearson et al. 2015) occurs due to small-scale chaotic evolution of the fundamental frequencies of the debris star orbits;
2. the Lyapunov time and frequency diffusion time are powerful indicators of chaos, but do not capture the importance of small-scale chaotic diffusion for the density evolution of small ensembles of orbits (tidal debris);
3. tidal debris becomes diffuse and thus harder to observe on weakly chaotic orbits when

the small-scale chaotic diffusion of the fundamental frequencies has a scale comparable to the internal spread in frequencies of the debris;

4. the details of the enhanced mixing along weakly chaotic orbits depends on the resonant structure of the potential;
5. the covariance of the fundamental frequencies of an orbit over a given time window may be a better predictor of the importance of small-scale chaotic frequency diffusion on the resulting morphology of tidal debris.

Our results provide a clear explanation of how and why the morphology of tidal streams alone can be used to constrain the potential of the host galaxy. The longest thin streams are most valuable for this effort because they have clearly evolved for a long time, but the debris remains compact. For shorter thin streams it will be hard to decouple the unknown evolution time from enhanced density evolution from chaos. The mere existence of thin tidal streams in the halo of the Milky Way either (1) provides useful information about the potential on these scales by, e.g., implying a large degree of regularity, or (2) indicates that the thin, long streams (e.g., GD-1) are on regular orbits. These are not mutually exclusive—in fact, if the streams are on regular orbits, this would be a powerful way to check or rule out possible potential models by requiring that the progenitor orbits remain regular.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank Robyn Sanderson, Dan D’Orazio, David Merritt, and the *Stream Team* for useful comments and discussion. The authors additionally thank the referee, Walter Dehnen, for insightful comments that greatly improved this *Chapter*.

APW is supported by a National Science Foundation Graduate Research Fellowship un-

der Grant No. DGE 11-44155. KVJ and APW were partially supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. AST-1312196 and NASA grant NNX15AK78G. MV is supported in part by the University of Michigan’s Elizabeth Crosby Fund and the Office of the VP for Research and NASA ATP grant NNX15AK79G. AHWK would like to acknowledge support from NASA through Hubble Fellowship grant HST-HF-51323.01-A awarded by the Space Telescope Science Institute, which is operated by the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc., for NASA, under contract NAS 5-26555.

This research made use of *Astropy*, a community-developed core *Python* package for Astronomy (Astropy Collaboration et al. 2013). This work additionally relied on Columbia University’s *Hotfoot* and *Yeti* compute clusters, and we acknowledge the Columbia HPC support staff for assistance. This work used the Extreme Science and Engineering Discovery Environment (XSEDE), which is supported by National Science Foundation grant number ACI-1053575 (Towns et al. 2014).

4.A Lyapunov exponents

If one is only interested in characterizing the degree of chaos, computing the full Lyapunov spectrum for an orbit is often not necessary. It is usually sufficient to compute an estimate of the maximum Lyapunov exponent by estimating the finite-time maximum Lyapunov exponent (FTMLE). Using the definition of \mathbf{w} from Equation 4.1, consider an orbit that is a small deviation away from the parent orbit, $\mathbf{w}' = \mathbf{w} + \delta\mathbf{w}$. If the parent orbit is chaotic, the norm of the infinitesimal deviation should grow exponentially with time with some characteristic rate, λ ,

$$\|\delta\mathbf{w}(t)\| = e^{\lambda t} \|\delta\mathbf{w}_0\| \tag{4.17}$$

(see, e.g., Lichtenberg & Lieberman 1983; Tabor 1989). From this expression, we see that

$$\lambda(t) = \frac{1}{t} \ln \frac{\|\delta\mathbf{w}(t)\|}{\|\delta\mathbf{w}_0\|} \quad (4.18)$$

where the maximum Lyapunov exponent is the limit as $t \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\lambda_{\max} = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \lambda(t). \quad (4.19)$$

Numerically computing this quantity is not trivial because (1) obviously the limit to infinity is not possible and (2) the norm of the deviation vector $\|\delta\mathbf{w}(t)\|$ is expected to increase exponentially for chaotic orbits, leading to nonlinear evolution of the deviation and numerical problems. To circumvent these issues, it is sufficient to instead start a nearby orbit with some small initial deviation with norm δ_0 , integrate for a sufficiently small amount of time, τ , then renormalize the deviation back to the initial norm (Benettin et al. 1976). There is no general way to determine τ except to perform convergence tests. The FTMLE after a given number of timesteps, N , is then estimated as

$$\lambda_N = \frac{1}{t_N} \sum_i^N \ln \frac{\|\delta\mathbf{w}(t_i)\|}{\|\delta\mathbf{w}_0\|} \quad (4.20)$$

where the t_i are the times at which the renormalization occurs and the MLE is estimated after a very long time to approximate the limit of Equation 4.19.

For most regular orbits, deviations will grow linearly or as a power-law of time. As we have seen in Section 4.2, if the orbit is regular, there exists a local transformation to action-angle variables where the angle variables increase linearly with time, $\theta_i \propto \Omega_i t$. We can look

at small variations around the angle-space orbit,

$$\frac{d(\delta\theta_i)}{dt} = \frac{\partial\Omega_i}{\partial J_k} \delta J_k \quad (4.21)$$

These equations are easily integrated:

$$\delta\theta_i(t) = \delta\theta_i(0) + \left(\frac{\partial\Omega_i}{\partial J_k} \delta J_k \right) t \quad (4.22)$$

It's clear then that the norm of the deviation vector grows linearly with time:

$$\|\delta\mathbf{w}(t)\| = \left[\sum_i (\delta\theta_i(t))^2 + \sum_i (\delta J_i)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (4.23)$$

$$= \left[\sum_i \left(\delta\theta_i(0) + \frac{\partial\Omega_i}{\partial J_k} \delta J_k t \right)^2 + \sum_i (\delta J_i)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (4.24)$$

$$\propto t. \quad (4.25)$$

From Equations 4.18 and 4.19 it is evident that any deviation vector that grows as a power law with time, t^k , will asymptote to 0 from the limit

$$\lambda_{\max} \propto \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} k \frac{\ln t}{t} = 0. \quad (4.26)$$

At long times, the numerically computed MLE for a regular orbit should approach 0 as t^{-1} . For chaotic orbits, the divergence is exponential, and the limit should converge to the rate of the exponential: the Lyapunov exponent. In practice, the MLE is often estimated as the mean of λ_N after the summation diverges from power-law behavior. For weakly chaotic orbits, reliable computation of the MLE may take integration of thousands of orbital periods.

4.B SuperFreq

The NAFF algorithm operates on numerically integrated orbital time-series (i.e. positions and velocities at a set of equally spaced times). Complex combinations of the phase-space coordinates of the orbit are Fourier-transformed using a standard FFT and the resultant spectrum is then searched for the strongest frequency component; this serves as an initial guess for the frequency of a particular Fourier component. Solving for the frequency that maximizes the Fourier integral of the FFT with a particular window function allows for a more accurate determination of the frequency. It has been shown that this accuracy converges much faster than the typical t_{int}^{-1} expected for a standard FFT by using a window function of the form

$$W(\tau = t/t_{\text{int}}) = \frac{2^p (p!)^2}{(2p)!} (1 + \cos \pi\tau)^p \quad (4.27)$$

where t_{int} is the integration time (Laskar 1999). Once the strongest frequency component is found, it is subtracted from the spectrum and the process is repeated iteratively. This procedure generates a table of frequencies for each component of motion which must then be searched for the three fundamental frequencies. The original implementations of NAFF have used $p = 1$ (e.g., Laskar 1993; Valluri & Merritt 1998), but we have chosen to use $p = 4$. With a higher order window function, the central peak is broadened, but the amplitudes of the side lobes decrease faster (see Hunter 2002); we have found that this additional damping of the side lobes allows for more reliable determination of frequencies from strongly chaotic orbits.

SuperFreq recovers the fundamental frequencies for an orbit faster (with a fewer number of terms) when the coordinates used are ‘close’ to the angle variables (PL96; Papaphilippou & Laskar 1996). PL96 show that a good choice of coordinates for tube orbits are the Poincaré

Figure 4.B.1: A reproduction of Figure 3.45 from (Binney & Tremaine 2008) as a validation of our frequency analysis code: Frequency ratios for 100000 isoenergy orbits integrated in a triaxial logarithmic potential. Linear features are resonances—stable resonances appear as dark lines, unstable resonances appear as linear gaps.

symplectic polar coordinates, a set of canonical coordinates similar to cylindrical coordinates. When computing the frequencies for tube orbits, we first align the circulation about the z -axis through rotation, transform to Poincaré polar coordinates, then use `SuperFreq` to measure the fundamental frequencies. We could equivalently use the Cartesian time series, but the convergence of terms is slower (the amplitudes of successive terms decrease slower for Cartesian coordinates). We have tested that our implementation of `SuperFreq` returns the same fundamental frequencies in either case for a set of tube orbits. For box orbits, the motion is close to separable in each Cartesian component and we therefore use Cartesian coordinates for estimating the frequencies for these orbits.

Figure 4.B.1 shows a validation of our frequency analysis code in which we reproduce the frequency map at a fixed energy of an axisymmetric, logarithmic potential (Binney & Tremaine 2008, pg. 260, Figure 3.45). Plotted are the (Cartesian) frequency ratios recovered for a grid of iso-energy, box orbits integrated in the potential

$$\Phi(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{2} \ln (x^2 + (y/0.9)^2 + (z/0.7)^2 + 0.1). \quad (4.28)$$

Following Binney & Tremaine (2008), we generate a grid of orbits on the equipotential surface $\Phi(x, y, z) = 0.5$ (we use a grid with 100000 orbits compared to their 10000 orbits). Each orbit is integrated for ≈ 40 orbital periods. In this figure, stable resonances appear as linear over-densities and unstable resonances appear as linear under-densities or gaps. The regularity of the points in this map reflects the input grid of initial conditions. Points that appear to be erratically scattered are chaotic orbits where the frequencies change with time.

Chapter 5

Chaotic fanning of the Ophiuchus stream

5.1 Introduction

The Ophiuchus stream (Bernard et al. 2014; Sesar et al. 2015) is a recently discovered stellar tidal stream that sits above the Galactic bulge at a Galactocentric radius and height $(R, z) \approx (1.5, 4.3)$ kpc. All observational evidence suggests that the stream is a completely disrupted globular cluster: The stream stars have (1) a small positional dispersion orthogonal to the extended direction of the stream (width ≈ 10 pc, length ≈ 1.5 kpc); (2) no detectable over-density along the stream that could be the progenitor system; (3) a small velocity dispersion ≈ 0.4 km s⁻¹; and (4) an old stellar population (≈ 12 Gyr) estimated from isochrone fitting (Sesar et al. 2015, hereafter S15).

There are a number of peculiarities about the observed kinematics of the Ophiuchus stream. For example, the de-projected length of the visible part of the stream is short given the age of its stellar population (≈ 1.5 kpc). S15 fit an orbit to the kinematics of the stream

stars in a static, axisymmetric model for the gravitational field of the inner Galaxy and ran N -body simulations of globular clusters on this orbit. S15 find that—on this orbit—the portion of the stream visible as an over-density in main-sequence stars must have been formed in the last $\lesssim 400$ Myr for the stream to remain as short as it is observed. This dynamical age is at odds with the old (≈ 10 – 12 Gyr) stellar population: The abrupt end of the stream suggests that the cluster apparently fully disrupted at once in the last 400 Myrs. Another puzzle is the existence of blue horizontal branch (BHB) stars close to the stream (within a few degrees) with similar radial velocities, but with a large dispersion in both sky position and velocity (Sesar et al. 2016, hereafter S16). The stream has a very distinct and large line-of-sight velocity (≈ 290 km s $^{-1}$) and is therefore easily detected above the background halo population. Four BHB stars have been detected with line-of-sight velocities > 230 km s $^{-1}$ that lie close to an extrapolation of the stream on the sky. This makes them likely members of the stream, as their velocities are in stark contrast to the background halo population (see Section 4, S16). Yet, they have a velocity dispersion ≈ 75 times larger than the measured internal velocity dispersion of the stream stars. These stars hint at the existence of associated low-density, high-dispersion features that were not modeled in S15 and are not predicted by the N -body simulations from this prior work, which assume a sudden, total disruption of the stream progenitor.

The orbit fit and N -body simulations in S15 used a static, axisymmetric potential to represent the Milky Way potential, but it is well-known that the Galactic bulge contains a triaxial, rotating, bar-like structure several kpc in size (e.g., Blitz & Spergel 1991; Weinberg 1992; Dwek et al. 1995; Wegg & Gerhard 2013). Given the proximity of the stream to the center of the Galaxy, the time-dependent, triaxial potential of the Galactic bar must be taken into account when modeling the orbit of the Ophiuchus stream. The presence of a bar-like perturbation to the potential will change the orbit of the stream progenitor and the orbit

Figure 1: *Left column:* Circular velocity curves along the Sun-Galactic center line for a representative barred MW potential model (top left) and for the static MW potential model (bottom left). Solid black line shows total (sum of all components), lines below show a decomposition by potential components. Vertical grey bar shows approximate position of the Sun, horizontal grey bar shows roughly the range in measured circular velocity of the Sun. *Right column:* Contours of constant surface density for a barred MW potential (top right) and the static MW potential model (bottom right). Four contours are drawn per decade in surface density between 10^7 and $10^{12} M_\odot \text{ kpc}^{-3}$. Note the perturbation from the bar potential within Galactocentric radius $r \lesssim 4$ kpc. The Sun's position is indicated by the ' \odot ' symbol.

structure in the inner galaxy (Zotos 2012; Portail et al. 2015a; Gajda et al. 2015). Bar-like features can also introduce a significant number of chaotic orbits in their vicinity (Weinberg 2015) and generate resonances that may also affect stream formation (Hattori et al. 2015).

Recent work has shown that dynamical chaos can dramatically alter the density evolution of tidal streams (e.g., Fardal et al. 2015; Price-Whelan et al. 2016). Along certain chaotic orbits, the stream stars will spread much faster in 3D position than from ordinary phase-mixing and, depending on the orbital phase at which the stream is observed, may develop large, low-density “fans” of stars at the ends of a stream (Pearson et al. 2015; Price-Whelan et al. 2016). As a first application of this theoretical understanding, we study whether stream-fanning—chaotic or simply from density evolution in a triaxial, time-dependent potential—could plausibly explain the observed properties of the Ophiuchus stream. In particular, we consider whether such models can reproduce:

1. the apparent shortness and fast density truncation of the stream;
2. the increased positional dispersion of the four new candidate members from S16;
3. the large velocity dispersion of the S16 stars.

We do not aim to perfectly represent the observed data, but rather to explore the plausibility of explaining the peculiarities of the stream using chaotic stream fanning. Note that an alternate model was recently proposed that instead places the stream progenitor on an orbit in resonance with the bar (Hattori et al. 2015). We discuss the differences between these two models in Section 5.5.

In Section 5.2 we describe the methods used in this work: in Section 5.2.1 we describe the models we use for the gravitational potential of the Galaxy, in Section 5.2.2 we outline the probabilistic procedure we use to fit orbits to the stream data (explained in detail in Appendix 5.B), and in Section 5.2.3 we explain the simple method we use to generate mock

streams. In Section 5.3 we discuss the results from fitting orbits to the data in a static, axisymmetric potential model and several potential models with a time-dependent bar. In Section 5.4 we generate mock streams along these orbits to argue that chaotic stream-fanning is a plausible explanation for the observational peculiarities of the Ophiuchus stream. We discuss the implications of this work and possibilities for future work in Section 5.5 and we conclude in Section 5.6.

5.2 Methods

Our goal is to (1) assess whether the Galactic bar can produce chaotic orbits in the vicinity of the Ophiuchus stream and (2) determine if chaotic density evolution of tidal debris stripped from the progenitor of this stream can explain the apparent shortness of the stream and low-density, high-dispersion stars beyond the extent of main sequence stars observed in PS1. In this section, we describe the potential models we use to represent the galaxy and outline the methods we use to detect and quantify the strength of chaos for individual orbits. We then describe the likelihood function we use for fitting orbits to the stream stars. Finally, we describe how we generate mock stellar streams for a progenitor on a given orbit.

Throughout we assume the Sun is at Galactocentric position $(x, y, z) = (-8.3, 0, 0)$ kpc (e.g., Schönrich 2012) with velocity $(v_x, v_y, v_z) = (-11.1, 250, 7.25)$ km s⁻¹ (e.g., Schönrich et al. 2010; Schönrich 2012).

5.2.1 Potential models

To integrate orbits and to compute chaos indicators we must choose a gravitational potential model to represent the potential of the Milky Way. The key feature of the potential that we would like to capture is the time-dependence and triaxiality of the Galactic bar. Recent

work has used stellar number counts of Red Clump giant stars in the Galactic bulge to constrain dynamical models of the bar (Portail et al. 2015b). Measurements of the total mass of the bar feature from this study are largely consistent with past work (e.g., Wang et al. 2012), however the measured pattern speed and present bar angle are significantly discrepant and this difference is not fully understood. We construct a parametrized potential model consisting of a triaxial, time-dependent (rotating) bulge component added to simple models for the disk and halo of the Milky Way. We describe below how we fix the parameters of the disk, halo, and bar or bulge component, but explore different choices for the time-dependence and orientation of the bar. We also define a static potential with a spherical bulge for comparison.

These potential models are meant to be representative rather than definitive. The uncertainty in the Milky Way potential within Galactocentric radii of $r \lesssim 4$ kpc and outside of $r \gtrsim 15$ kpc are large enough that trying to match the exact density distribution of the Ophiuchus stream is not a useful exercise. Instead, we consider qualitatively different potentials that allow us to isolate and study the affect of chaotic stream-fanning of tidal debris in the vicinity of the stream.

5.2.1.1 Barred potential

We use a spherical Navarro-Frenk-White potential to represent the dark matter halo (Navarro et al. 1996) parametrized as

$$\Phi(r) = -v_h^2 \frac{\ln(1 + r/r_s)}{r/r_s} \quad (5.1)$$

and a Miyamoto-Nagai potential for the disk (Miyamoto & Nagai 1975). For the bar component, we use a basis function expansion (BFE) of the potential and density of the bar

with expansion coefficients derived for a triaxial, exponential bar density (Wang et al. 2012, hereafter W12). We use the pre-computed expansion coefficients used in W12, which were computed from a low-order expansion of the triaxial bar density used in Dwek et al. (1995). We have implemented the BFE computation of the potential, density, and gradient of the potential in `C` and `Python` and the code is publicly available on *GitHub*.

The BFE representation fixes the axis ratios of the bar—that is, the exponential scale lengths along the three axes of the bar were adopted from Dwek et al. (1995) when the expansion coefficients were calculated in W12; all other potential parameter values are given in Table 5.1. The mass of the halo is fixed and the mass of the disk and bar are varied in order to qualitatively reproduce the flatness and amplitude of the circular velocity curve of the Milky Way (Bovy et al. 2012c). Figure 1, top left shows the circular velocity along the line connecting the Sun to the Galactic center in this model (the Galactic x axis). Figure 1, top right shows contours of constant surface density for a face-on (left) and edge-on (right) view of this potential model with the bar angle set to 20° (compare to, e.g., Figure 3 in Portail et al. 2015b). We consider a grid of nine parameter combinations of bar angle and pattern speed. Model names and parameter values are given in Table 5.2.

5.2.1.2 Static potential

For comparison, we also define a time-independent potential model with a purely spherical bulge. In this model, we set the bar mass to 0 and instead add a spheroidal component represented with a Hernquist potential (Hernquist 1990). Parameters for this potential model are given in Table 5.3. Figure 1, bottom left shows the circular velocity along the line connecting the Sun to the Galactic center in this model (the Galactic x axis). Figure 1,

The coefficients presented in W12 are for just the cosine terms (the A_{lm} in Hernquist & Ostriker (1992) or the S_{nlm} in Lowing et al. (2011)) because all sine terms have zero coefficients for a triaxial density function.
<https://github.com/adrn/biff>

Component	Parameter	Value
Disk	M_{disk}	$4 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$
	a	3 kpc
	b	0.28 kpc
Spheroid	M_{sph}	$5 \times 10^9 M_{\odot}$
	c	0.2
Halo	v_c	185.8 km s $^{-1}$
	r_s	30 kpc
Bar	M_{bar}	$1.8 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$

Table 5.1: The disk potential scale lengths (a , b) were adopted following (Bovy 2015) to match the exponential scale length of the disk (Bovy & Rix 2013) and local dark-matter density (e.g., Bovy & Tremaine 2012). The halo mass scale is set by specifying the circular velocity at the scale radius, v_c , and the scale velocity in Equation 5.1 is given by $v_h^2 = v_c^2 / (\ln 2 - 1/2)$. The bar mass is taken from recent 3D density modeling of red clump stars in the Galactic bulge (Portail et al. 2015b). The other bar parameters are listed in Table 5.2 next to the corresponding model name.

bottom right shows contours of constant surface density for a face-on (left) and edge-on (right) view of this potential model.

5.2.2 Fitting orbits to the Ophiuchus stream

In each of the potentials described above, we fit orbits to the measured kinematics of BHB stars that are high-likelihood members of the Ophiuchus stream (Sesar et al. 2015, 2016). The details of this procedure and a definition of the likelihood function we use are presented in Appendix 5.B. We use an ensemble Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm (Goodman & Weare 2010) implemented in Python (`emcee`) to generate samples from the posterior distribution over the parameters in our orbit-fitting model (Foreman-Mackey et al. 2013). The algorithm uses an ensemble of individual “walkers” to adapt to the geometry of the parameter-space being explored. In all cases, we use 80 walkers (8 times the number of

Name	α [deg]	Ω_p [km s ⁻¹ kpc ⁻¹]
bar1	20	40
bar2	20	50
bar3	20	60
bar4	25	40
bar5	25	50
bar6	25	60
bar7	30	40
bar8	30	50
bar9	30	60

Table 5.2: Present-day bar angle (α) and pattern speed (Ω_p) for the nine parameter pairs considered in this work. These values span the range of recent measurements from a variety of techniques (Dwek et al. 1995; Wang et al. 2012, 2013; Wegg & Gerhard 2013).

parameters).

To initialize these walkers, we first run an optimization routine to maximize the likelihood: We use the Powell algorithm implemented in `Scipy` (Powell 1964; Jones et al. 2001–) to minimize the negative, log-likelihood. To generate initial conditions for the walkers, we sample from Gaussian distributions centered on the maximum likelihood values. For the coordinates, we set the dispersions of these Gaussians to 1/1000 of the median uncertainties of the stars. For the nuisance parameters, we set the dispersions to 1/1000 of their maximum likelihood values.

For each potential, we run the MCMC walkers for a burn-in period of 512 steps and then re-initialize the walkers from their positions at the end of this run. This erases any relics of the initialization procedure outlined above. After burn-in, we run the walkers for an additional 512 steps. For each parameter, we compute the autocorrelation times, τ , of the Markov chains and thin the chains by taking every 2τ sample. This reduces the number of samples, but ensures that our posterior samples are effectively independent.

Component	Parameter	Value
Disk	M_{disk}	$6 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$
	a	3 kpc
	b	0.28 kpc
Halo	v_c	185.8 km s ⁻¹
	r_s	30 kpc
Spheroid	M_{sph}	$1.2 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$
	c	0.3

Table 5.3: Same as Table 5.1, except: the disk mass is increased to account for removing the bar component, a spheroidal bulge component is added.

5.2.3 Generating mock streams

To generate mock stellar streams, we use the method presented in Fardal et al. (2015): Star particles are ‘released’ from a progenitor system near the Lagrange points with a dispersion in position and velocity that is set by the mass and orbit of the progenitor. We draw samples from the posterior probability distributions over orbital parameters from fitting orbits to the stream star members and use these as the progenitor orbital parameters (Section 5.B). For a given progenitor orbit—the 6D position of the orbit today—we integrate the orbit backwards in time for a given integration period. From the endpoint of the backwards-integration (e.g., the past position), we begin integrating the orbit forward in time, but now at each time-step a star particle is released near each of the Lagrange points of the progenitor. The position of the Lagrange points and the scale of the dispersion in position and velocity are set by the progenitor mass, m . The star particles are drawn from Gaussians centered on the Lagrange points (in position) and the progenitor (in velocity) and the full parametrization of the release distribution is given in Fardal et al. (2015). This method has been shown to reproduce the morphologies of N -body simulations of stellar streams, but requires far less

Figure 2: Results from fitting orbits to BHB stars associated with the Ophiuchus stream in the static and barred potential models. Data used for computing the likelihood are shown as black points with grey error bars. The four “fanned” BHB stars from S16 excluded from the likelihood computation are shown as grey squares. Error bars may sometimes be smaller than the point size. Lines (blue) show sections of orbits integrated forward and backwards from initial conditions drawn from the posterior samples generated by MCMC (See Section 5.B). Note that the four higher dispersion stars (the four stars with highest longitude) were not used when computing the likelihood and are only shown for completeness. Though these four stars are significant outliers relative to the extrapolated orbit, they are (1) at the correct distance and sky position relative to the stream and (2) have velocities $\approx 2.5\sigma$ discrepant with the halo velocity distribution in this region.

computing time because it relies only on integrating test-particle orbits.

We make one modification to this method based on the idea that the Ophiuchus stream progenitor has been fully-disrupted. We add an additional parameter to the stream generation routine to specify the time of disruption, τ_d . At this time, we set the offset of the Lagrange point to 0: In terms of the parametrization in (Fardal et al. 2015), we set $k_r = 0$ and $k_{vt} = 0$ but preserve the dispersion in the release radius and velocity. Any star released after τ_d is released with a small dispersion around the progenitor orbit but no offset. This mass-loss history is intended to mimic the expected gradual evaporation of a globular cluster over a tidally-limited boundary (i.e. driven by two-body relaxation and gravitational shocks over many Gigayears) with final disruption likely to occur once the tidal boundary is less than the core radius of the cluster. The physics of this disruption is not followed exactly but rather the disruption rate and final disruption time are set by the hypothesis that the most recent combined pericenter and disk shock fully disrupted the cluster, but, critically, that the cluster has been losing debris over its entire orbital history.

5.3 Results 1: Orbit fits and chaos

Figure 2 summarizes our results from fitting orbits to the BHB stream stars. Shown in each panel are the high-probability Ophiuchus stream stars (black points, to which orbits are fit) and orbits integrated from samples from the posterior probability over orbital parameters (blue lines). The four “fanned” BHB stars from S16 are shown as grey squares and are not included in the orbit fitting procedure. We only show one of the barred potentials: The end-to-end integration time of the orbit over the observed extent of the stream is only ≈ 6 Myr, so the derived orbits are extremely similar in all potentials (the time-dependence of the bar potential is not significant over such short timescales). The orbital periods are typically ≈ 170 – 200 Myr with pericenters $r_p \approx 4$ kpc and apocenters $r_a \approx 12$ – 15 kpc. Though the

coordinate and velocity parameter values in observed coordinates are very similar between each potential model, the resulting orbits are quite different. For the posterior samples in each potential, we take the mean values of the coordinate and velocity parameters and convert to Galactocentric coordinates (e.g., Table 5.4). Figure 3 shows projections of these “mean” orbits in each potential model.

For the posterior samples in each potential, we also compute the maximum Lyapunov exponent (MLE, λ_{\max}) and corresponding Lyapunov *time* ($t_\lambda = 1/\lambda_{\max}$) to assess whether each orbit is chaotic. For strongly chaotic orbits, the Lyapunov time is still an appropriate indicator of chaos and of the timescale over which chaos is important for tidal debris (Price-Whelan et al. 2016). Figure 4 shows distributions of Lyapunov times for orbits drawn from the posterior distributions from orbit fitting in each potential model. All orbits in the static potential have Lyapunov times $t_\lambda > 20$ Gyr and we consider them to be regular (no panel is shown for these orbits). All orbits sampled from each barred potential are strongly chaotic with Lyapunov times that range from $t_\lambda \approx 400\text{--}1100$ Myr. It is clear from these panels that the orbits around Ophiuchus are generally more strongly chaotic (have lower Lyapunov times) for larger pattern speeds.

The orbits sampled from the orbit-fit posteriors in the barred potentials are all strongly chaotic. We have tried computing the frequency diffusion rate for these orbits as an independent check of their chaotic timescale but have found that, over consecutive integration windows, the frequency recovery fails or is unreliable because the frequency spectrum changes dramatically over timescales of $\approx 10\text{--}20$ orbital periods.

Figure 3: Projections of orbits integrated from the mean orbital parameters estimated from the orbit fitting posterior distributions in each potential model. Orbits are integrated for 6 Gyr and shown in Galactocentric, Cartesian coordinates. Even though the mean orbital parameters have nearly identical values (e.g., the initial conditions are nearly identical in heliocentric coordinates), the orbits in each potential model are different in appearance.

5.4 Results 2: Stream models for the Ophiuchus stream

Here we study whether the observed abrupt drop in density and possible fanned debris stars can be explained without assuming a sudden change in the mass-loss history of the cluster. In particular, we are interested in whether the mock streams formed around the strongly chaotic progenitor orbits in the barred potentials can explain these features while having been steadily disrupted over many Gigayears.

For each potential model, we randomly sample 256 orbits from the orbital parameter posterior distributions and generate mock streams along each orbit. We use the method

Figure 4: Histograms of estimated Lyapunov time, $t_\lambda = 1/\lambda_{\max}$, for posterior samples from the orbit fitting procedure (Section 5.B). More chaotic orbits, i.e. those with shorter Lyapunov times, typically occur in barred potentials with higher pattern speeds. There is little dependence on bar angle. All orbits in these barred potential models are strongly chaotic with $t_\lambda \ll t_{\text{Hubble}}$ and $t_\lambda \sim t_{\text{orbit}}$, where the typical orbital period for Ophiuchus stream stars is a few hundred Megayears.

outlined above (Section 5.2.3) to generate the streams and set the free parameters as follows: (1) we evolve the progenitors for 6 Gyr along each orbit prior to the current position to explore stream models where the shortness of the stream is *not* due to an instantaneous disruption 400 Myrs ago, (2) we release star particles every 0.5 Myr (uniformly in time) to densely sample the final density distribution, (3) we set the progenitor mass to $m = 10^4 M_\odot$ (as was estimated by S15), and (4) we set the disruption time of the progenitor equal to the last time at which a pericenter and disk crossing coincide (in each case, this is at $t \approx -200$ Myr). After the disruption time, we continue releasing the star particles uniformly in time (every 0.5 Myr) rather than releasing a “burst” of particles at once. We therefore expect that the density of the most recently disrupted debris will be systematically higher for the model streams as compared to the observed stream.

name	ϕ_2 [deg]	d [kpc]	μ_l [mas yr $^{-1}$]	μ_b [mas yr $^{-1}$]	v_r [km s $^{-1}$]
static	-0.03 ± 0.05	8.3 ± 0.05	-7.4 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	288.9 ± 0.9
bar1-9	-0.03 ± 0.05	8.35 ± 0.05	-7.4 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	289.0 ± 1.0
	s_{ϕ_2} [deg]	s_d [kpc]	s_{v_r} [km s $^{-1}$]		
	0.20 ± 0.04	0.31 ± 0.10	2.9 ± 0.8		
	0.21 ± 0.05	0.31 ± 0.14	3.2 ± 0.9		

Table 5.4: Estimated mean and standard deviation of samples from the marginal posterior distributions over each parameter in our orbit fit model (the posterior distributions are very close to Gaussian). For the barred potentials, all mean values are the same because the time-dependence of the bar doesn’t impact the orbit fit over the short length of the stream. We have made samples from the full posterior distribution available with this *Chapter* and provide code to transform to and from stream coordinates (see <http://adrian.pw/ophiuchus> for more information).

For each generated mock stream, we compute the likelihood of the data (now including all BHB stars from S15 and S16, e.g., all points in Figure 2) given the star particles by estimating the phase-space model density using a kernel density estimate with a Gaussian kernel (see, e.g., Bonaca et al. 2014). For each i data point \mathbf{x}_i and each k model point

with coordinates \mathbf{y}_k , we compute the likelihood by converting the model point position and velocity into heliocentric coordinates and evaluate

$$p(\mathbf{x}_i | \mathbf{y}_k, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i, \mathbf{h}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_i | \mathbf{y}_k, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i^2 + \mathbf{h}^2) \quad (5.2)$$

where $\mathcal{N}(x | \mu, \sigma^2)$ is the normal distribution with mean μ and variance σ^2 and \mathbf{h} represents the diagonal of the bandwidth matrix, \mathbf{H} , used for the density estimate, $\mathbf{h} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{H})$. We fix the bandwidth parameters as follows

$$\mathbf{h} = \begin{pmatrix} 0.2 \text{ deg} \\ 0.2 \text{ deg} \\ 0.2 \text{ kpc} \\ 0.2 \text{ km s}^{-1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.3)$$

for sky position in Galactic coordinates (l, b) , distance, and radial velocity. The full likelihood for all N data points given K model points is

$$\mathcal{L} = \prod_i^N \frac{1}{K} \sum_k^K p(\mathbf{x}_i | \mathbf{y}_k, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i, \mathbf{h}). \quad (5.4)$$

Figures 5–6 show the final particle positions and line-of-sight velocities in heliocentric coordinates for the maximum likelihood mock streams (grey points) in each potential. Vertical, dashed lines show the approximate extent of the part of the stream visible in main-sequence stars (excluding the BHB stars from S16). There are a few interesting features to note from these panels:

1. Even in the static potential (Figure 5, leftmost column), there is a slight decrease in the density for the model stream towards higher Galactic longitudes, l . This is a projection

effect: The portion of the stream at larger l is closer and points almost directly towards the Sun so that the debris covers a larger area on the sky.

2. The density of the mock stream in the static potential decreases slowly rather than abruptly as is observed. This is shown in the top panels of each column where each contour level represents a factor of 10 difference in projected surface density. In the static potential model the length of dense debris extends much farther than the observed extent of the stream (vertical dashed lines), whereas in some of the barred potential models the stars released earlier have “fanned” and are associated with much lower density debris (e.g., bar8).
3. The four high-dispersion BHB stars beyond the end of the stream (from S16) don’t match in position and velocity with the particle distribution from even the maximum likelihood stream model in the static potential. In some barred potentials the chaotic evolution of the stream stars can lead to over-densities of stars with an increased positional dispersion and significantly discrepant velocities (e.g., bar8).
4. None of the stream models—static or barred—produce an appreciable density of stars with line-of-sight velocities near the S16 BHB star with the largest velocity ($\approx 320 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). This star is either an interesting Ophiuchus member star or is associated with some other kinematic substructure.
5. For the barred potentials, the stream morphology is very sensitive to the properties of the bar (especially the pattern speed) and to the initial conditions of the orbit. We have found that the morphology can vary significantly between nearby orbits in the same potential model (because these are strongly chaotic orbits), but the overall characteristics remain similar: along more strongly chaotic orbits, the debris “fans” more and the apparent dense part of the model streams is shorter.

The density truncation of the mock streams in each potential model is more clearly seen in terms of the density contrast between stream stars and background stars, visualized in Figure 7: This figure shows mock sky-density maps of stars generated by superimposing the maximum likelihood model streams over a noisy background of stars. The number of mock stream star particles used to generate the map has been normalized such that the total number of stars within the observed extent of the stream (between $5.85 > l > 3.81$ deg) is equal to the number of stars attributed to the Ophiuchus stream in the PS1 data ($N \approx 500$ Bernard et al. 2014).

The viewing angle and stream geometry is more clearly demonstrated in Figure 8, which shows x - z projections of the star particles in Galactocentric Cartesian coordinates (grey) along with the position of the Sun (symbol at $(x, z) = (-8.3, 0)$ kpc) and the “window” of the heliocentric, sky-position plots of Figures 5–6 (shown as blue lines).

5.5 Discussion

The model streams presented here do not reproduce all observed features of the Ophiuchus stream (the details of the potential and the orbit predict vastly different phase-space morphologies for the fanned part). Instead, these results illustrate that chaotic evolution of tidal debris can plausibly explain the peculiar features of the stream. If the cluster progenitor was on a regular orbit, it would have to have disrupted entirely within the last ≈ 300 – 600 Myr in order to explain the shortness and density profile. In addition, the four most recently identified BHB stars with similar distances and line-of-sight velocities would have to be (highly unlikely) chance alignments of halo stars. If instead the progenitor were on a chaotic orbit (because of the influence of the Galactic bar): (1) stars stripped early will have “fanned” out and would thus be harder to observe and (2) the nearby, high-velocity-dispersion BHB stars

can be naturally explained by this chaotic stream-fanning. We consider the second scenario to be more plausible: our understanding of the formation and evolution of the Ophiuchus stream is that the progenitor object has been orbiting and steadily losing stars over the last several Gigayears, but only the stars stripped from the most recent few pericentric passages remain coherent enough to be detected as a stream-like over-density in the PS1 data.

It is still too early to say for sure that chaotic stream-fanning is occurring for the Ophiuchus stream. Deeper follow-up imaging and spectroscopy over a larger area region around the stream will be needed to test the predictions of this work and compare with other possible scenarios. For example, recent work has shown that if the Ophiuchus stream progenitor orbit is in resonance with the bar, the debris can remain short for at least 1 Gyr (Hattori et al. 2015). In their model, there would be no nearby, high-dispersion debris, and the pattern speed of the bar would be related to the orbital frequencies of the progenitor orbit. However, it has not been demonstrated whether this proposed scheme can explain the shortness of the stream over timescales closer to the age of the stellar population (≈ 10 Gyr). With more information about the density distribution of stars in the stream and better proper motion measurements we would be able to (1) help distinguish models for the Milky Way bar independent from current methods and (2) begin to model the survivability of globular clusters orbiting in the central Milky Way (e.g., Gnedin & Ostriker 1997).

5.5.1 Future work: Modeling the Galactic bar

The current kinematic data for the Ophiuchus BHB stars suggests that the stream is sensitive to the gravitational potential of the Milky Way bar—with better measurements of the velocities and a larger sample of member stars we will constrain parameters for the bar model. Current measurements of the pattern speed, angle, and structure of the Milky Way’s bulge and bar are largely discrepant (e.g., Wang et al. 2012, 2013; Wegg & Gerhard 2013;

Antoja et al. 2014). Most of the methods that infer these quantities rely on modeling the density or kinematics of stars at low Galactic latitudes and must therefore handle challenges with completeness and dust extinction. The Ophiuchus stream offers a unique opportunity to independently measure these quantities by modeling the density and kinematics of stars associated with the stream.

5.5.2 Future work: The orbits and survivability of inner Milky Way globular clusters

If the Ophiuchus stream formed from a globular cluster on a chaotic orbit and we happen to be witnessing its final demise, what does this imply about the population of clusters that have already been fully disrupted? The existence of strongly chaotic orbits in this region would limit the expected number of cold stellar streams in the inner Galaxy and enhance the rate of mixing of the debris. The fraction of strongly chaotic orbits that would lead to chaotic fanning or fast dispersal of tidal debris should therefore be related to the amount of kinematic substructure in the inner Galaxy. Indeed, first suggestions of kinematic substructure in the bulge have been found, but further modeling is needed to understand whether these hints could be signature of a widely dispersed globular cluster population. If so, a stronger theoretical understanding of the prevalence of these features could be combined with future kinematic surveys (from, e.g., *Gaia*) to place constraints on long-standing puzzles about the primordial globular cluster population (e.g., Murali & Weinberg 1997; Gnedin & Ostriker 1997).

5.6 Conclusions

We have shown that, with a qualitative but observationally-motivated potential model for the Galactic bar, the orbits of the Ophiuchus stream stars are likely sensitive to the time-dependence and shape of the bar potential. For modeling the stream density itself, it is therefore crucial to include this component of the Galactic potential. By fitting orbits to kinematic data for members of the stream in Milky Way-like potential models, we have found that orbits in the vicinity of the Ophiuchus stream are strongly chaotic for a range of bar parameters (pattern speeds and present-day angles). Using mock stellar stream models generated assuming a globular cluster-mass progenitor object, we have shown that the apparent shortness of the stream and the existence of nearby stars with very high velocity dispersion are plausibly explained by chaotic density evolution of the stars stripped from the progenitor object.

This is the first time chaos has been used to explain the morphology of a stellar stream and the first observational evidence for the importance of chaos in the Galactic halo. It also highlights the importance of including the Galactic bar in dynamical modeling of the Milky Way's inner halo and has important implications for future modeling of streams near in this region. With more Ophiuchus stream members, density and velocity information over a larger region near the stream, and better models for the internal structure of the Galactic bar, careful modeling of this stream could lead to tight constraints on the structure and evolution of the bar.

Acknowledgements

APW is supported by a National Science Foundation Graduate Research Fellowship under Grant No. 11-44155. KVJ and APW acknowledge support from NSF grant AST-1312196. This material is based on work supported by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration under Grant No. NNX15AK78G issued through the Astrophysics Theory Program. APW acknowledges the staff at the MPIA for their support and assistance. The authors wish to acknowledge Victor Debattista, Melissa Ness, and Sarah Pearson for useful discussions. APW acknowledges David Bowie (1947–2016) for his continuous inspiration and artistic vision. This research made use of Astropy, a community-developed core Python package for Astronomy (Astropy Collaboration et al. 2013). This work additionally relied on Columbia University’s *Yeti* compute cluster, and we acknowledge the Columbia HPC support staff for assistance.

5.A Transformation from Galactic to Ophiuchus stream coordinates

The transformation matrix is approximately represented as

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix}_{\text{Oph}} \approx \begin{pmatrix} 0.84922096554 & 0.07001279040 & 0.52337554476 \\ -0.27043653641 & -0.79364259852 & 0.54497294023 \\ 0.45352820359 & -0.60434231606 & -0.65504391727 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix}_{\text{Gal}}$$

Figure 5: Sky position, distance, and line-of-sight velocity in heliocentric, Galactic coordinates for star particles (contours or grey points) from the maximum-likelihood mock streams in each potential. Top panels show surface density of mock stream star particles in each potential. Contours are spaced logarithmically from 10^{-2} to 10 particles per sq. deg—that is, each color represents a factor of 10 difference in surface density. In the static potential (top left), the density remains high along the center of the stream, but for some of the barred potentials the density drops sharply because of chaotic stream-fanning. Vertical, dashed lines show the approximate extent of the densest part of the stream visible in main-sequence stars (the segment originally detected in Bernard et al. 2014).

Figure 6: Same as Figure 5 for the other five barred potentials.

Figure 7: Simulated maps of the 2D density of star particles from the maximum-likelihood mock streams in each potential with a noisy background of stars binned into $10'$ by $10'$ pixels. The background star density is assumed to be Poisson with $\lambda = 42$ (see Figure 3 in Bernard et al. 2014, where the typical background density is $\approx \frac{60}{(0.2 \text{ deg})^2}$). The mock stream particles are down-sampled so that the total number of particles in the region of sky that the stream is seen as an over-density matches the observed number of stars ($N \approx 500$ Bernard et al. 2014). Color-scale is stretched so that white to black is 2nd to 98th percentile.

Figure 8: Star particles (grey points) from mock streams generated on the mean orbits in each potential model shown in projections of Galatocentric, Cartesian coordinates. The position of the Sun is shown as the symbol at $(x, z) = (-8, 0)$ kpc. The volume of the sky position and distance plots of Figures 5–6 are shown transformed to these coordinates as the blue wedge near $(x, z) = (-2, 4)$ kpc. This demonstrates that the stream is nearly aligned our viewing angle.

but the precise transformation and coordinate frame is implemented in `Python` using the `Astropy` coordinates package. This code is hosted on *GitHub*.

5.B Fitting orbits to stellar streams

Our goal is to infer the posterior probability distributions over orbital initial conditions, $\mathbf{w}_0 = (l, b, \text{DM}, \mu_l, \mu_b, v_r)_0$, given a potential, Φ , and kinematic data for each i stream star, $\mathbf{x}_i = (l, b, \text{DM}, \mu_l, \mu_b, v_r)_i$. In this notation, (l, b) are Galactic coordinates, DM is the distance modulus, (μ_l, μ_b) are proper motions in the Galactic frame, and v_r is the radial velocity. We assume that the sky coordinates for each star are known perfectly well (have zero uncertainty) and transform the data to a rotated, heliocentric coordinate system that is aligned with the stream and centered on the median sky position of the BHB stars in the densest part of the stream (all BHB stars except the ‘fanned’ stars: cand15, cand26, cand49, cand54 from Sesar et al. 2016). We represent the longitude and latitude in these coordinates as (ϕ_1, ϕ_2) and the rotation matrix to transform from Galactic to these coordinates is given in Appendix 5.A. We treat the stream longitude, ϕ_1 , as the perfectly-known, independent variable so that all other coordinates can be expressed as functions of this longitude (e.g., $\phi_2(\phi_1)$, $\text{DM}(\phi_1)$, etc.). This methodology is similar to that used in Koposov et al. (2010) and Sesar et al. (2015).

5.B.1 Likelihood

We include three nuisance parameters in our likelihood to account for the internal dispersion of the stream: in observed coordinates, these are the on-sky positional dispersion, s_{ϕ_2} , a distance (modulus) dispersion, s_{DM} , and a radial velocity dispersion, s_{v_r} (the proper motion uncertainties are sufficiently large that we can’t resolve the velocity dispersion in these

See <http://adrian.pw/ophiuchus> for more information
<https://github.com/adrn/ophiuchus>

coordinates). We add two additional nuisance parameters for controlling the amount of time to integrate forwards, t_f , and backwards, t_b , from the given initial conditions, which ultimately controls the length of the section of orbit that is compared to the stream star data. For brevity in the equations below, we define $\mathbf{s} = (s_{\phi_2}, s_{\text{DM}}, s_{v_r})$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\mathbf{w}_0, \Phi, t_b, t_f)$.

For a given set of initial conditions (\mathbf{w}_0), we compute a model orbit as follows: (1) transform the initial conditions to Galactocentric coordinates, (2) integrate the orbit forward and backward by t_f and t_b , respectively, in the potential Φ , (3) transform all orbit points (time-steps) back to observed coordinates, and (4) define interpolating functions for each coordinate as a function of stream longitude, ϕ_1 , using cubic splines—e.g., functions $\tilde{\phi}_2(\phi_1)$, $\widetilde{\text{DM}}(\phi_1)$, $\tilde{\mu}_l(\phi_1)$, $\tilde{\mu}_b(\phi_1)$, $\tilde{v}_r(\phi_1)$. These functions let us compute the predicted values of each of these coordinates at the longitudes of each observed star, $\phi_{1,i}$.

We assume that each observed kinematic component is independent so that the likelihood of the data for a given star, \mathbf{x}_i , with uncertainties, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i$, is given by the product over the likelihoods for each dimension of the data:

$$p(\mathbf{x}_i | \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i, \mathbf{s}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = p(\phi_{2,i} | \phi_{1,i}, s_{\phi_2}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) p(\text{DM}_i | \phi_{1,i}, \sigma_{\text{DM},i}, s_{\text{DM}}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \\ \times p(\mu_{l,i} | \phi_{1,i}, \sigma_{\mu_l,i}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) p(\mu_{b,i} | \phi_{1,i}, \sigma_{\mu_b,i}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) p(v_{r,i} | \phi_{1,i}, \sigma_{v_r,i}, s_{v_r}, \boldsymbol{\theta}). \quad (5.5)$$

The uncertainties in these observed coordinate components are assumed to be normally distributed away from the model values: using the notation

$$\mathcal{N}(x | \mu, \sigma^2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (5.6)$$

We assume that the dispersion in these coordinates is constant over the observed (short) section of the stream. This may be a bad assumption.

the likelihoods are

$$p(\phi_{2,i} | \phi_{1,i}, s_{\phi_2}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathcal{N}(\phi_{2,i} | \tilde{\phi}_2(\phi_{1,i}), s_{\phi_2}^2) \quad (5.7)$$

$$p(\text{DM}_i | \phi_{1,i}, \sigma_{\text{DM},i}, s_{\text{DM}}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathcal{N}(\text{DM}_i | \widetilde{\text{DM}}(\phi_{1,i}), s_{\text{DM}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{DM},i}^2) \quad (5.8)$$

$$p(\mu_{l,i} | \phi_{1,i}, \sigma_{\mu_{l,i}}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathcal{N}(\mu_{l,i} | \tilde{\mu}_l(\phi_{1,i}), \sigma_{\mu_{l,i}}^2) \quad (5.9)$$

$$p(\mu_{b,i} | \phi_{1,i}, \sigma_{\mu_{b,i}}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathcal{N}(\mu_{b,i} | \tilde{\mu}_b(\phi_{1,i}), \sigma_{\mu_{b,i}}^2) \quad (5.10)$$

$$p(v_{r,i} | \phi_{1,i}, \sigma_{v_{r,i}}, s_{v_r}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathcal{N}(v_{r,i} | \tilde{v}_r(\phi_{1,i}), s_{v_r}^2 + \sigma_{v_{r,i}}^2). \quad (5.11)$$

We assume the data from each star is independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) so that the full likelihood is the product over the likelihoods for all N stars:

$$p(\{\mathbf{x}_i\} | \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i\}, \mathbf{s}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \prod_i^N p(\mathbf{x}_i | \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i, \mathbf{s}, \boldsymbol{\theta}). \quad (5.12)$$

5.B.2 Priors

For the intrinsic dispersion parameters, we use logarithmic (scale-invariant) priors such that $p(s) \propto s^{-1}$. For the integration time parameters, we use uniform priors, $\mathcal{U}(a, b)$ (over the range a - b),

$$p(t_f) = \mathcal{U}(1, 100) \text{ Myr} \quad (5.13)$$

$$p(t_b) = \mathcal{U}(-100, -1) \text{ Myr}. \quad (5.14)$$

Note that present-day is $t = 0$. For computational efficiency, we place strong priors on the minimum and maximum longitudes of the model points, $(\phi_{1,\min}, \phi_{1,\max})$ so that the model

orbit does not integrate for longer than necessary. In particular, we set

$$p(\phi_{1,\min} | \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathcal{N}(\phi_{1,\min} | \min(\phi_{1,i}), s_{\phi_2}^2) \quad (5.15)$$

$$p(\phi_{1,\max} | \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathcal{N}(\phi_{1,\max} | \max(\phi_{1,i}), s_{\phi_2}^2). \quad (5.16)$$

For the orbital initial condition components, we use uniform priors in each cartesian position component over the range $(-200, 200)$ kpc. For velocity, we use a Gaussian prior on the magnitude of the total velocity, v , with a dispersion of 150 km s^{-1} ,

$$\mathcal{N}(v | 0, (150 \text{ km s}^{-1})^2) \quad (5.17)$$

We keep the potential, Φ , fixed. In total, this model has 10 parameters (5 phase-space coordinates, 5 nuisance parameters).

The full expression for the posterior probability, $p(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{w}_0, t_b, t_f | \{\mathbf{x}_i\}, \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i\}, \Phi)$, is the joint likelihood (Equation 5.12) multiplied by all priors described above (Equations 5.13–5.17).

Chapter 6

Conclusion

Stellar streams are a unique tool for measuring the structure of mass around galaxies where the density of visible tracers is low. The work presented in this *Chapter* has shown that it will soon be possible to infer the 3D shape and distribution of dark matter around the Milky Way by modeling the many streams observed in the Galactic halo. This goal will be made possible by near-future catalogs of 6D kinematic measurements for individual stars in these streams from surveys like the *Gaia* mission. We have also shown that dynamical chaos can dramatically alter the morphological evolution of streams. Since the amount and significance of chaos depends strongly on the Galactic gravitational potential, this supports developing a new method for constraining the potential based purely on the morphologies of the many long, thin streams presently seen around the Milky Way. In this section, we summarize and discuss the key results presented in this *Chapter* and discuss future directions for this work.

6.1 Summary of Results

In Chapter 2, we developed a new algorithm for using precise kinematic measurements of stars in stellar streams to measure the parameters of the underlying host galaxy's gravitational

potential. This work was motivated by the prospect of combining extremely precise distance measurements for RR Lyrae stars with proper motion measurements from the *Gaia* mission and ground-based radial velocities to obtain full-space kinematics for samples of stars in stellar streams in the Galactic halo. The algorithm operates with the simple assumption that stars observed in a stellar stream were once part of the same progenitor system; by integrating the orbits of the progenitor system and stream stars backwards in time, in more correct host galaxy potential models the stars should come closer (in 6D phase-space) to the progenitor. We demonstrated that by modeling observations of a simulation of the Sagittarius stream with realistic but optimistic uncertainties, the true potential parameters can be inferred with small uncertainties and negligible biases. While this is encouraging and demonstrates the power of using dynamically cold structures for dynamical inference, it does not a proper likelihood function and therefore cannot be used when there are missing or poorly measured data dimensions.

In Chapter 3, we used the ideas presented in Chapter 2 to develop a probabilistic model for stellar streams. The key enhancement of this new approach is that it is written as a likelihood function with priors on the parameters so that missing or poorly-measured data can be incorporated into the inference of the potential parameters. **Rewinder** is distinct from many other stream-modeling methods because it (1) makes no assumption about the underlying form or integrability of the host galaxy potential, (2) non-parametrically infers the mass-loss history of the progenitor system, and (3) models the distribution function of stars *at the time of stripping* rather than at present-day and can therefore analytically evaluate the likelihood without numerically reconstructing the density field. We tested **Rewinder** with a simulation observed with different assumptions about the tracer population (different data qualities) and showed that in all cases, all input potential parameters are successfully recovered: mass and length scaling but also the shape parameters of the input triaxial halo.

In Chapter 4, we showed that even when chaos is not important for restructuring the global orbit structure of a galaxy, chaos can greatly enhance the density evolution of stellar streams over just a few orbital times. This suggests that the morphology of tidal streams *alone* can constrain the significance of chaos along the orbits of the progenitor systems, thereby placing constraints on the global properties of the gravitational potential. For example, different dark matter particle candidates (WIMPs vs. axions) predict vastly different amounts of substructure, which can dramatically change the number of chaotic orbits in a given potential; the amount of chaos is therefore sensitive to the physical nature of dark matter. This result motivates developing a quantitative framework to use the observed density structure of streams and shells to map the orbit structure of the host potentials. Critically, this would be applicable to imaging data where only the configuration-space morphology of the structures are observable, but can be tested and calibrated with the existing thin streams around the Milky Way.

In Chapter 5, we present dynamical models for the newly-discovered and peculiarly-short Ophiuchus stream that suggest that the stream has formed in a strongly chaotic region of phase-space. We found that the stream’s proximity to the Galactic center suggests that the bar must have a significant influence on its dynamical history: the triaxiality and time-dependence of the bar generates many chaotic orbits in the vicinity of the stream. We model the formation of the stream in a Milky Way potential model that includes a rotating bar and found that in all choices for the rotation parameters of the bar, orbits fit to the stream are strongly chaotic. Mock streams generated along these orbits qualitatively match the observed properties of the stream: because of chaos, stars stripped early generally form low-density, high-dispersion “fans” leaving only the most recently disrupted material detectable as a strong over-density. Our models predict that there should be more low-surface-brightness tidal debris than detected so far, likely with a complex phase-space morphology. This is the

first time that chaos has been used to explain the properties of a stellar stream and is the first demonstration of the dynamical importance of chaos in the Galactic halo.

6.2 Future Work

6.2.1 Rewinder

Rewinder and other stream-modeling methods have demonstrated that they can *precisely* infer potential parameters from simulated data where the analytic form of the gravitational potential is known but the parameter values are not known. This is, of course, a far reach from the real universe where the form of the potential is likely very complex. In our view, two critical enhancements must be made before Rewinder or any other stream-modeling methods can be meaningfully applied to observational data. First, they must use flexible or non-parametric forms for the potential, for example, using basis function expansions of the potential. This will make the potential inferences less precise but will be less biased. Second, these methods must simultaneously incorporate data from multiple streams.

6.2.2 Chaotic stream dispersal as a potential constraint

Does the existence of thin streams around the Milky Way constrain the triaxiality or shape of the Galactic potential? It is possible to rule out certain potentials that cause the observed thin streams to spread too quickly with their configuration-space morphology alone (e.g. Pearson et al. 2015), but, of course, modeling the streams directly will provide more precise constraints on the potential. Instead, it is worth considering whether this could be used to measure the properties of a sample of external galaxy halos where it is not possible to obtain velocity measurements for individual tracers but streams can be observed with low-

surface-brightness imaging. For example, the high-latitude survey of the WFIRST mission will cover 2200 deg^2 with an unprecedented limiting J -band magnitude of $J = 26.7$ (Spergel et al. 2015). With the expected surface brightness limits ($32 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$), WFIRST is expected to measure 5–10 distinct debris structures around each of over 100 of these nearby galaxies (Johnston et al. 2008). The surface-brightness limits of the upcoming LSST ($29 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$) are less sensitive, but the survey will contain a much larger sample of galaxies ($\approx 10^6$). In order to use these data, we must first develop a way to model the expected number and distribution of morphologies of tidal debris structures given dark matter halo shape and profiles. For example, we could study the tidal debris mixing rates as a function of frequency diffusion rate for a sample of halo shapes and profiles and use this to understand how many thin structures are expected to survive as a function of halo geometries. Though it is unclear whether this is possible in practice, it is an entirely new direction for research and would be the first proposed method for (statistically) measuring the 3D dark matter halo shapes for large samples of galaxies.

Bibliography

Akerib, D. S., Bai, X., Bedikian, S., et al. 2012, Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A, 668, 1

Antoja, T., Helmi, A., Dehnen, W., et al. 2014, A&A, 563, A60

Arnold, V. I. 1978, Mathematical methods of classical mechanics

Astropy Collaboration, Robitaille, T. P., Tollerud, E. J., et al. 2013, A&A, 558, A33

Bailin, J., Kawata, D., Gibson, B. K., et al. 2005, ApJ, 627, L17

Battaglia, G., Helmi, A., Morrison, H., et al. 2005, MNRAS, 364, 433

Bechtol, K., Drlica-Wagner, A., Balbinot, E., et al. 2015, ApJ, 807, 50

Bekki, K. 2012, MNRAS, 422, 1957

Bell, E. F., Xue, X. X., Rix, H.-W., Ruhland, C., & Hogg, D. W. 2010, AJ, 140, 1850

Bell, E. F., Zucker, D. B., Belokurov, V., et al. 2008, ApJ, 680, 295

Belokurov, V., Zucker, D. B., Evans, N. W., et al. 2006, ApJ, 642, L137

Belokurov, V., Evans, N. W., Irwin, M. J., et al. 2007a, ApJ, 658, 337

Belokurov, V., Zucker, D. B., Evans, N. W., et al. 2007b, ApJ, 654, 897

Belokurov, V., Evans, N. W., Bell, E. F., et al. 2007c, *ApJ*, 657, L89

Belokurov, V., Koposov, S. E., Evans, N. W., et al. 2013, ArXiv e-prints, arXiv:1301.7069

Benedict, G. F., McArthur, B. E., Feast, M. W., et al. 2011, *AJ*, 142, 187

Benettin, G., Galgani, L., & Strelcyn, J.-M. 1976, *Phys. Rev. A*, 14, 2338

Bernard, E. J., Ferguson, A. M. N., Schlafly, E. F., et al. 2014, *MNRAS*, 443, L84

Besla, G., Kallivayalil, N., Hernquist, L., et al. 2010, *ApJ*, 721, L97

Bett, P., Eke, V., Frenk, C. S., et al. 2007, *MNRAS*, 376, 215

Binney, J. 2008, *MNRAS*, 386, L47

Binney, J., Gerhard, O., & Spergel, D. 1997, *MNRAS*, 288, 365

Binney, J., Gerhard, O. E., Stark, A. A., Bally, J., & Uchida, K. I. 1991, *MNRAS*, 252, 210

Binney, J., & Tremaine, S. 2008, *Galactic Dynamics: Second Edition* (Princeton University Press)

Blitz, L., & Spergel, D. N. 1991, *ApJ*, 379, 631

Bochanski, J. J., Willman, B., Caldwell, N., et al. 2014, *ApJ*, 790, L5

Bolton, A. S., Burles, S., Koopmans, L. V. E., Treu, T., & Moustakas, L. A. 2006, *ApJ*, 638, 703

Bonaca, A., Geha, M., & Kallivayalil, N. 2012, *ApJ*, 760, L6

Bonaca, A., Geha, M., Küpper, A. H. W., et al. 2014, *ApJ*, 795, 94

Bovy, J. 2014, *ApJ*, 795, 95

- . 2015, *ApJS*, 216, 29
- Bovy, J., Hogg, D. W., & Roweis, S. T. 2009, *ApJ*, 700, 1794
- Bovy, J., & Rix, H.-W. 2013, *ApJ*, 779, 115
- Bovy, J., Rix, H.-W., & Hogg, D. W. 2012a, *ApJ*, 751, 131
- Bovy, J., Rix, H.-W., Liu, C., et al. 2012b, *ApJ*, 753, 148
- Bovy, J., & Tremaine, S. 2012, *ApJ*, 756, 89
- Bovy, J., Allende Prieto, C., Beers, T. C., et al. 2012c, *ApJ*, 759, 131
- Bovy, J., Nidever, D. L., Rix, H.-W., et al. 2014, *ApJ*, 790, 127
- Brooks, A. M., Kuhlen, M., Zolotov, A., & Hooper, D. 2013, *ApJ*, 765, 22
- Brown, W. R., Geller, M. J., Kenyon, S. J., & Diaferio, A. 2010, *AJ*, 139, 59
- Bryan, S. E., Kay, S. T., Duffy, A. R., et al. 2013, *MNRAS*, 429, 3316
- Buist, H. J. T., & Helmi, A. 2014, *A&A*, 563, A110
- Bullock, J. S., & Johnston, K. V. 2005, *ApJ*, 635, 931
- Butsky, I., Macciò, A. V., Dutton, A. A., et al. 2015, *ArXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1503.04814
- Cao, L., Mao, S., Nataf, D., Rattenbury, N. J., & Gould, A. 2013, *MNRAS*, 434, 595
- Carlberg, R. G. 2015, *ApJ*, 808, 15
- Chirikov, B. V. 1960, *Journal of Nuclear Energy*, 1, 253
- . 1979, *Phys. Rep.*, 52, 263

Choi, J.-H., Weinberg, M. D., & Katz, N. 2009, MNRAS, 400, 1247

Clementini, G., Gratton, R., Bragaglia, A., et al. 2003, AJ, 125, 1309

Coleman, M. G., de Jong, J. T. A., Martin, N. F., et al. 2007, ApJ, 668, L43

Côté, P., McLaughlin, D. E., Cohen, J. G., & Blakeslee, J. P. 2003, ApJ, 591, 850

Courteau, S., Cappellari, M., de Jong, R. S., et al. 2013, ArXiv e-prints, arXiv:1309.3276

Dalton, G., Trager, S. C., Abrams, D. C., et al. 2012, in Proc. SPIE, Vol. 8446, Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IV, 84460P

de Jong, R. S., Bellido-Tirado, O., Chiappini, C., et al. 2012, in Proc. SPIE, Vol. 8446, Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IV, 84460T

De Silva, G. M., Freeman, K. C., Bland-Hawthorn, J., et al. 2015, MNRAS, 449, 2604

de Zeeuw, T. 1985, MNRAS, 216, 273

Deason, A. J., Belokurov, V., & Evans, N. W. 2011, MNRAS, 416, 2903

Deason, A. J., Belokurov, V., Evans, N. W., & An, J. 2012a, MNRAS, 424, L44

Deason, A. J., Belokurov, V., Evans, N. W., & McCarthy, I. G. 2012b, ApJ, 748, 2

Deason, A. J., Van der Marel, R. P., Guhathakurta, P., Sohn, S. T., & Brown, T. M. 2013, ApJ, 766, 24

Deason, A. J., Belokurov, V., Evans, N. W., et al. 2012c, MNRAS, 425, 2840

Debattista, V. P., Gerhard, O., & Sevenster, M. N. 2002, MNRAS, 334, 355

Debattista, V. P., Moore, B., Quinn, T., et al. 2008, ApJ, 681, 1076

- Debattista, V. P., Roškar, R., Valluri, M., et al. 2013, MNRAS, 434, 2971
- Deg, N., & Widrow, L. 2013, MNRAS, 428, 912
- . 2014, ArXiv e-prints, arXiv:1401.4070
- Dehnen, W., & Binney, J. J. 1998, MNRAS, 298, 387
- Deibel, A. T., Valluri, M., & Merritt, D. 2011, ApJ, 728, 128
- Dékány, I., Minniti, D., Majaess, D., et al. 2015, ApJ, 812, L29
- Diemand, J., Kuhlen, M., & Madau, P. 2007, ApJ, 657, 262
- Drake, A. J., Catelan, M., Djorgovski, S. G., et al. 2013, ApJ, 763, 32
- Dubinski, J. 1994, ApJ, 431, 617
- Dubinski, J., & Carlberg, R. G. 1991, ApJ, 378, 496
- Dwek, E., Arendt, R. G., Hauser, M. G., et al. 1995, ApJ, 445, 716
- Eisenstein, D. J., Zehavi, I., Hogg, D. W., et al. 2005, ApJ, 633, 560
- Eyre, A., & Binney, J. 2009, MNRAS, 399, L160
- . 2011, MNRAS, 413, 1852
- Fardal, M. A., Huang, S., & Weinberg, M. D. 2015, MNRAS, 452, 301
- Fellhauer, M., Belokurov, V., Evans, N. W., et al. 2006, ApJ, 651, 167
- Flaugher, B. L., Abbott, T. M. C., Angstadt, R., et al. 2012, in Proc. SPIE, Vol. 8446, Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IV, 844611

- Foreman-Mackey, D., Hogg, D. W., Lang, D., & Goodman, J. 2013, *PASP*, 125, 306
- Gajda, G., Lokas, E. L., & Athanassoula, E. 2015, *ArXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1511.04253
- Gibbons, S. L. J., Belokurov, V., & Evans, N. W. 2014, *MNRAS*, 445, 3788
- Gilmore, G., & Reid, N. 1983, *MNRAS*, 202, 1025
- Gnedin, O. Y., & Ostriker, J. P. 1997, *ApJ*, 474, 223
- Goldstein, H. 1980, *Classical Mechanics*, Addison-Wesley series in physics (Addison-Wesley Publishing Company)
- Gómez, F. A., Besla, G., Carpintero, D. D., et al. 2015, *ApJ*, 802, 128
- Goodman, J., & Weare, J. 2010, *Comm. App. Math. Comp. Sci.*, 5, 65
- Grillmair, C. J. 2006, *ApJ*, 645, L37
- Grillmair, C. J. 2008, in *American Institute of Physics Conference Series*, Vol. 1082, American Institute of Physics Conference Series, ed. C. A. L. Bailer-Jones, 226–232
- Grillmair, C. J., & Carlin, J. L. 2016, in *Astrophysics and Space Science Library*, Vol. 420, *Astrophysics and Space Science Library*, ed. H. J. Newberg & J. L. Carlin, 87
- Grillmair, C. J., & Dionatos, O. 2006, *ApJ*, 643, L17
- Grillmair, C. J., Freeman, K. C., Irwin, M., & Quinn, P. J. 1995, *AJ*, 109, 2553
- Hairer, E., Nørsett, S. P., & Wanner, G. 1993, *Springer Series in Computational Mathematics*, Vol. 8, *Solving Ordinary Differential Equations. I. Nonstiff Problems*, 2nd edn. (Berlin: Springer-Verlag), xvi+528, a reprinting with corrections appeared in 2000.
- Harris, W. E. 2010, *ArXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1012.3224

- Hattori, K., Erkal, D., & Sanders, J. L. 2015, ArXiv e-prints, arXiv:1512.04536
- Helmi, A., & White, S. D. M. 1999, MNRAS, 307, 495
- Henderson, A. P., Jackson, P. D., & Kerr, F. J. 1982, ApJ, 263, 116
- Hernquist, L. 1990, ApJ, 356, 359
- Hernquist, L., & Ostriker, J. P. 1992, ApJ, 386, 375
- Hunter, C. 2002, Space Sci. Rev., 102, 83
- Ibata, R. A., Gilmore, G., & Irwin, M. J. 1994, Nature, 370, 194
- Ivezić, Ž., Sesar, B., Jurić, M., et al. 2008, ApJ, 684, 287
- Jing, Y. P., & Suto, Y. 2002, ApJ, 574, 538
- Johnston, K., Scowcroft, V., Madore, B., et al. 2013, Spitzer Proposal, 10015
- Johnston, K. V. 1998, ApJ, 495, 297
- Johnston, K. V., Bullock, J. S., Sharma, S., et al. 2008, ApJ, 689, 936
- Johnston, K. V., Majewski, S. R., Siegel, M. H., Reid, I. N., & Kunkel, W. E. 1999a, AJ, 118, 1719
- Johnston, K. V., Spergel, D. N., & Hernquist, L. 1995, ApJ, 451, 598
- Johnston, K. V., Zhao, H., Spergel, D. N., & Hernquist, L. 1999b, ApJ, 512, L109
- Jones, B. F., Klemola, A. R., & Lin, D. N. C. 1994, AJ, 107, 1333
- Jones, E., Oliphant, T., Peterson, P., et al. 2001–, SciPy: Open source scientific tools for Python, [Online; accessed 2015-02-11]

- Jurić, M., Ivezić, Ž., Brooks, A., et al. 2008, *ApJ*, 673, 864
- Kaffe, P. R., Sharma, S., Lewis, G. F., & Bland-Hawthorn, J. 2012, *ApJ*, 761, 98
- . 2014, *ApJ*, 794, 59
- Kalberla, P. M. W., & Dedes, L. 2008, *A&A*, 487, 951
- Kalberla, P. M. W., Dedes, L., Kerp, J., & Haud, U. 2007, *A&A*, 469, 511
- Kalberla, P. M. W., & Kerp, J. 2009, *ARA&A*, 47, 27
- Kandrup, H. E., & Mahon, M. E. 1994, *A&A*, 290, 762
- Kandrup, H. E., Pogorelov, I. V., & Sideris, I. V. 2000, *MNRAS*, 311, 719
- Kandrup, H. E., & Siopis, C. 2003, *MNRAS*, 345, 727
- Kazantzidis, S., Kravtsov, A. V., Zentner, A. R., et al. 2004, *ApJ*, 611, L73
- Klein, C. R., & Bloom, J. S. 2014, *ArXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1404.4870
- Koopmans, L. V. E., & Treu, T. 2002, *ApJ*, 568, L5
- Koposov, S. E., Rix, H.-W., & Hogg, D. W. 2010, *ApJ*, 712, 260
- Kuhlen, M., Diemand, J., & Madau, P. 2007, *ApJ*, 671, 1135
- Küpper, A. H. W., Balbinot, E., Bonaca, A., et al. 2015, *ApJ*, 803, 80
- Küpper, A. H. W., Lane, R. R., & Heggie, D. C. 2012, *MNRAS*, 420, 2700
- Kuzmin, G. G. 1973, in *Dynamics of Galaxies and Star Clusters*, ed. T. B. Omarov, 71–75
- Laskar, J. 1988, *A&A*, 198, 341

- . 1993, *Celestial Mechanics and Dynamical Astronomy*, 56, 191
- . 1996, *Celestial Mechanics and Dynamical Astronomy*, 64, 115
- Laskar, J. 1999, in *NATO ASI Series, Vol. 533, Hamiltonian Systems with Three or More Degrees of Freedom* (Springer Netherlands), 134–150
- Laskar, J. 2003, *ArXiv Mathematics e-prints*, math/0305364
- Laskar, J., & Robutel, P. 1993, *Nature*, 361, 608
- Law, D. R., & Majewski, S. R. 2010, *ApJ*, 714, 229
- Lee, J., & Suto, Y. 2003, *ApJ*, 585, 151
- Lee, Y. S., Beers, T. C., Sivarani, T., et al. 2008, *AJ*, 136, 2022
- Leon, S., Meylan, G., & Combes, F. 2000, *A&A*, 359, 907
- Levi, M., Bebek, C., Beers, T., et al. 2013, *ArXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1308.0847
- Levine, E. S., Blitz, L., & Heiles, C. 2006, *Science*, 312, 1773
- Lichtenberg, A. J., & Lieberman, M. A. 1983, *Regular and stochastic motion*
- Longmore, A. J., Fernley, J. A., & Jameson, R. F. 1986, *MNRAS*, 220, 279
- Lowing, B., Jenkins, A., Eke, V., & Frenk, C. 2011, *MNRAS*, 416, 2697
- LSST Science Collaboration, Abell, P. A., Allison, J., et al. 2009, *ArXiv e-prints*, arXiv:0912.0201
- Lux, H., Read, J. I., Lake, G., & Johnston, K. V. 2013, *MNRAS*, 436, 2386
- Lyapunov, A. M. 1992, *International Journal of Control*, 55, 531

Madore, B. F., & Freedman, W. L. 2012, *ApJ*, 744, 132

Maffione, N. P., Gómez, F. A., Cincotta, P. M., et al. 2015, *MNRAS*, 453, 2830

Majewski, S. R., Skrutskie, M. F., Weinberg, M. D., & Ostheimer, J. C. 2003, *ApJ*, 599, 1082

Majewski, S. R., Schiavon, R. P., Frinchaboy, P. M., et al. 2015, *ArXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1509.05420

Martin, D. C., Matuszewski, M., Morrissey, P., et al. 2015, *Nature*, 524, 192

McMillan, P. J. 2011, *MNRAS*, 414, 2446

Méndez, R. H., Riffeser, A., Kudritzki, R.-P., et al. 2001, *ApJ*, 563, 135

Merrifield, M. R. 1992, *AJ*, 103, 1552

Merritt, D., & Valluri, M. 1996, *ApJ*, 471, 82

—. 1999, *AJ*, 118, 1177

Miller, M. J., & Bregman, J. N. 2013, *ApJ*, 770, 118

Minchev, I., Boily, C., Siebert, A., & Bienayme, O. 2010, *MNRAS*, 407, 2122

Miyamoto, M., & Nagai, R. 1975, *PASJ*, 27, 533

Moore, B., Governato, F., Quinn, T., Stadel, J., & Lake, G. 1998, *ApJ*, 499, L5

Murali, C., & Weinberg, M. D. 1997, *MNRAS*, 291, 717

Napolitano, N. R., Romanowsky, A. J., Capaccioli, M., et al. 2011, *MNRAS*, 411, 2035

Navarro, J. F., Frenk, C. S., & White, S. D. M. 1996, *ApJ*, 462, 563

- Ness, M., Freeman, K., Athanassoula, E., et al. 2013a, MNRAS, 430, 836
- . 2013b, MNRAS, 432, 2092
- Newberg, H. J., Yanny, B., Rockosi, C., et al. 2002, ApJ, 569, 245
- Ngan, W., Bozek, B., Carlberg, R. G., et al. 2015, ApJ, 803, 75
- Niederste-Ostholt, M., Belokurov, V., Evans, N. W., & Peñarrubia, J. 2010, ApJ, 712, 516
- Nordström, B., Mayor, M., Andersen, J., et al. 2004, A&A, 418, 989
- Odenkirchen, M., Grebel, E. K., Dehnen, W., Rix, H.-W., & Cudworth, K. M. 2002, AJ, 124, 1497
- Odenkirchen, M., Grebel, E. K., Rockosi, C. M., et al. 2001, ApJ, 548, L165
- Ojha, D. K. 2001, MNRAS, 322, 426
- Papaphilippou, Y., & Laskar, J. 1996, A&A, 307, 427
- . 1998, A&A, 329, 451
- Peñarrubia, J., Koposov, S. E., & Walker, M. G. 2012, ApJ, 760, 2
- Pearson, S., Küpper, A. H. W., Johnston, K. V., & Price-Whelan, A. M. 2015, ApJ, 799, 28
- Pedregosa, F., Varoquaux, G., Gramfort, A., et al. 2011, Journal of Machine Learning Research
- Percival, S. M., & Salaris, M. 2011, MNRAS, 412, 2445
- Perlmutter, S., Aldering, G., Goldhaber, G., et al. 1999, ApJ, 517, 565
- Perryman, M. A. C., Lindegren, L., Kovalevsky, J., et al. 1997, A&A, 323

- Perryman, M. A. C., de Boer, K. S., Gilmore, G., et al. 2001, *A&A*, 369, 339
- Planck Collaboration, Aghanim, N., Arnaud, M., et al. 2015, *ArXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1507.02704
- Pontzen, A., & Governato, F. 2012, *MNRAS*, 421, 3464
- Portail, M., Wegg, C., & Gerhard, O. 2015a, *MNRAS*, 450, L66
- Portail, M., Wegg, C., Gerhard, O., & Martinez-Valpuesta, I. 2015b, *MNRAS*, 448, 713
- Powell, M. J. D. 1964, *The Computer Journal*, 7, 155
- Price-Whelan, A. M. 2015, *SuperFreq*, doi:10.5281/zenodo.18787
- Price-Whelan, A. M., Hogg, D. W., Johnston, K. V., & Hendel, D. 2014, *ApJ*, 794, 4
- Price-Whelan, A. M., & Johnston, K. V. 2013, *ApJ*, 778, L12
- Price-Whelan, A. M., Johnston, K. V., Sheffield, A. A., Laporte, C. F. P., & Sesar, B. 2015, *MNRAS*, 452, 676
- Price-Whelan, A. M., Johnston, K. V., Valluri, M., et al. 2016, *MNRAS*, 455, 1079
- Prince, P., & Dormand, J. 1981, *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*, 7, 67
- Pryor, C., Piatek, S., & Olszewski, E. W. 2010, *AJ*, 139, 839
- Putman, M. E., Staveley-Smith, L., Freeman, K. C., Gibson, B. K., & Barnes, D. G. 2003, *ApJ*, 586, 170
- Reid, M. J., Menten, K. M., Brunthaler, A., et al. 2014, *ApJ*, 783, 130
- Riess, A. G., Filippenko, A. V., Challis, P., et al. 1998, *AJ*, 116, 1009

- Rix, H.-W., & Bovy, J. 2013, *A&A Rev.*, 21, 61
- Robin, A. C., Creze, M., & Mohan, V. 1992, *A&A*, 265, 32
- Rocha-Pinto, H. J., Majewski, S. R., Skrutskie, M. F., Crane, J. D., & Patterson, R. J. 2004, *ApJ*, 615, 732
- Romanowsky, A. J., & Kochanek, C. S. 1998, *ApJ*, 493, 641
- Rubin, V. C., & Ford, Jr., W. K. 1970, *ApJ*, 159, 379
- Salem, M., Besla, G., Bryan, G., et al. 2015, *ApJ*, 815, 77
- Sánchez, A. G., Scóccola, C. G., Ross, A. J., et al. 2012, *MNRAS*, 425, 415
- Sanders, J. L. 2014, *MNRAS*, 443, 423
- Sanders, J. L., & Binney, J. 2013a, *MNRAS*, 433, 1813
- . 2013b, *MNRAS*, 433, 1826
- Sanderson, R. E., Helmi, A., & Hogg, D. W. 2014, in *IAU Symposium*, Vol. 298, IAU Symposium, ed. S. Feltzing, G. Zhao, N. A. Walton, & P. Whitelock, 207–212
- Saunders, W., Smith, G., Gilbert, J., et al. 2012, in *Proc. SPIE*, Vol. 8446, Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IV, 84464W
- Sawala, T., Frenk, C. S., Fattahi, A., et al. 2016, *MNRAS*, 457, 1931
- Schönrich, R. 2012, *MNRAS*, 427, 274
- Schönrich, R., Binney, J., & Dehnen, W. 2010, *MNRAS*, 403, 1829
- Searle, L., & Zinn, R. 1978, *ApJ*, 225, 357

- Sesar, B., Jurić, M., & Ivezić, Ž. 2011, *ApJ*, 731, 4
- Sesar, B., Ivezić, Ž., Grammer, S. H., et al. 2010, *ApJ*, 708, 717
- Sesar, B., Ivezić, Ž., Stuart, J. S., et al. 2013a, *AJ*, 146, 21
- Sesar, B., Grillmair, C. J., Cohen, J. G., et al. 2013b, *ArXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1308.0857
- Sesar, B., Bovy, J., Bernard, E. J., et al. 2015, *ApJ*, 809, 59
- Sesar, B., Price-Whelan, A. M., Cohen, J. G., et al. 2016, *ApJ*, 816, L4
- Shapley, H. 1918, *ApJ*, 48, 154
- Shen, J., Rich, R. M., Kormendy, J., et al. 2010, *ApJ*, 720, L72
- Siegal-Gaskins, J. M., & Valluri, M. 2008, *ApJ*, 681, 40
- Skrutskie, M. F., Cutri, R. M., Stiening, R., et al. 2006, *AJ*, 131, 1163
- Sofue, Y., Honma, M., & Omodaka, T. 2009, *PASJ*, 61, 227
- Spergel, D., Gehrels, N., Baltay, C., et al. 2015, *ArXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1503.03757
- Stanek, K. Z., Udalski, A., Szymański, M., et al. 1997, *ApJ*, 477, 163
- Steinmetz, M., Zwitter, T., Siebert, A., et al. 2006, *AJ*, 132, 1645
- Sugai, H., Tamura, N., Karoji, H., et al. 2015, *Journal of Astronomical Telescopes, Instruments, and Systems*, 1, 035001
- Tabor, M. 1989, *Chaos and integrability in nonlinear dynamics: an introduction* (New York, NY: Wiley)
- Totten, E. J., & Irwin, M. J. 1998, *MNRAS*, 294, 1

Towns, J., Cockerill, T., Dahan, M., et al. 2014, *Computing in Science and Engineering*, 16, 62

Unwin, S. C., Shao, M., Tanner, A. M., et al. 2008, *PASP*, 120, 38

Valenti, E., Zoccali, M., Gonzalez, O. A., et al. 2016, *A&A*, 587, L6

Valluri, M., Debattista, V. P., Quinn, T., & Moore, B. 2010, *MNRAS*, 403, 525

Valluri, M., Debattista, V. P., Quinn, T. R., Roškar, R., & Wadsley, J. 2012, *MNRAS*, 419, 1951

Valluri, M., Debattista, V. P., Stinson, G. S., et al. 2013, *ApJ*, 767, 93

Valluri, M., & Merritt, D. 1998, *ApJ*, 506, 686

van der Marel, R. P., Fardal, M., Besla, G., et al. 2012, *ApJ*, 753, 8

van Uitert, E., Hoekstra, H., Schrabback, T., et al. 2012, *A&A*, 545, A71

Varghese, A., Ibata, R., & Lewis, G. F. 2011, *MNRAS*, 417, 198

Vera-Ciro, C. A., Sales, L. V., Helmi, A., et al. 2011, *MNRAS*, 416, 1377

Vogelsberger, M., White, S. D. M., Helmi, A., & Springel, V. 2008, *MNRAS*, 385, 236

Wang, Y., Mao, S., Long, R. J., & Shen, J. 2013, *MNRAS*, 435, 3437

Wang, Y., Zhao, H., Mao, S., & Rich, R. M. 2012, *MNRAS*, 427, 1429

Watkins, L. L., Evans, N. W., Belokurov, V., et al. 2009, *MNRAS*, 398, 1757

Wechsler, R. H., Bullock, J. S., Primack, J. R., Kravtsov, A. V., & Dekel, A. 2002, *ApJ*, 568, 52

Wegg, C., & Gerhard, O. 2013, MNRAS, 435, 1874

Wegg, C., Gerhard, O., & Portail, M. 2015, MNRAS, 450, 4050

Weiland, J. L., Arendt, R. G., Berriman, G. B., et al. 1994, ApJ, 425, L81

Weinberg, M. D. 1992, ApJ, 384, 81

—. 2015, ArXiv e-prints, arXiv:1508.05959

Wolf, A., Swift, J. B., Swinney, H. L., & Vastano, J. A. 1985, Physica, 285

Wouterloot, J. G. A., Brand, J., Burton, W. B., & Kwee, K. K. 1990, A&A, 230, 21

Xenon100 Collaboration, Aprile, E., Arisaka, K., et al. 2012, Astroparticle Physics, 35, 573

Xu, Y., Newberg, H. J., Carlin, J. L., et al. 2015, ApJ, 801, 105

Xue, X.-X., Rix, H.-W., Ma, Z., et al. 2015, ApJ, 809, 144

Xue, X. X., Rix, H. W., Zhao, G., et al. 2008, ApJ, 684, 1143

Yencho, B. M., Johnston, K. V., Bullock, J. S., & Rhode, K. L. 2006, ApJ, 643, 154

York, D. G., Adelman, J., Anderson, Jr., J. E., et al. 2000, AJ, 120, 1579

Zemp, M., Diemand, J., Kuhlen, M., et al. 2009, MNRAS, 394, 641

Zemp, M., Gnedin, O. Y., Gnedin, N. Y., & Kravtsov, A. V. 2011, ApJS, 197, 30

Zhao, H., Spergel, D. N., & Rich, R. M. 1995, ApJ, 440, L13

Zhu, Q., Marinacci, F., Maji, M., et al. 2015, ArXiv e-prints, arXiv:1506.05537

Zoccali, M., Renzini, A., Ortolani, S., et al. 2003, A&A, 399, 931

Zolotov, A., Brooks, A. M., Willman, B., et al. 2012, ApJ, 761, 71

Zotos, E. E. 2012, Research in Astronomy and Astrophysics, 12, 500